

**STUDY OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRODUCT
DIVERSIFICATION AND CORPORATE PERFORMANCE IN
INDIAN PERSPECTIVE**

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the research reported in the thesis titles, “Study of Relationship between Product Diversification and Corporate Performance in Indian Perspective”, has been carried out by Dina Nath Jha Dinker under my supervision and guidance. The content of the thesis is in the conformity with the original synopsis duly approved by me and submitted by him at the time of registration for Ph.D. examination. To the best of my knowledge, this is an original piece of work.

I further certify that this thesis has not been submitted to any other university or institution for the award of any degree.

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AREA CERTIFICATE

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DECLARATION

I declare that the thesis entitled “Study of Relationship between Product Diversification and Corporate Performance in Indian Perspective” is my own work conducted under the supervision of Dr.Samson Moharana, Professor, Department of Commerce, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar and that this has been submitted to Utkal University, Vanivihar, Bhubaneswar for the fulfilment of the requirements of award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Business Administration.

I further declare that to the best of my knowledge, the thesis does not contain any part of any work which has been submitted for the award of any degree either in this University or in any other University/Deemed University without proper citation.

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CHAPTER-1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Diversification

Diversification is a corporate strategy under which a firm enters into an industry or market different from current industry or market. The corporate strategy makes the total value of corporate higher than the sum of the values of individual business units. The corporate strategy concerns what business a firm should be in and how to manage individual business units.

In product diversification, a firm creates new product, modifies existing product, or acquires other businesses to tap into their product markets. Post product diversification, a firm reports sales in at least one more industry segment. The industry segments are defined at the two digit Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) code level. Diversification can be expanded into a new segment of same industry that the firm is operating in, or in a new industry outside the scope of existing business. Diversification also occurs when a firm expands into a new market with existing product portfolio.

After World War II, firms witnessed growth opportunities and entered into new products or markets for a multitude of reasons. This led to rise of large corporations we know today. Since early 1960s, corporate diversification has been extensively studied by economists and strategy scholars. (Porter, 1987) [1]

1.2 Classification of Diversification

By relationship of different operating products, diversification strategy of a firm can be broadly categorized into four categories:

1.2.1 Horizontal Diversification

In horizontal diversification strategy a firm offers new unrelated products or services to existing customers. In horizontal diversification, a firm relies on distribution channel, marketing, or technological relations between new product line and existing product lines. A firm can adopt horizontal diversification through acquisition or internal development of new product or services. The horizontal diversification strategy is less risky than conglomerate strategy as this strategy offers a new product line to existing customers. For example, Coca-Cola was already selling soft drink. Coca-Cola expanded horizontally and added fruit juice in its product portfolio. Coca-Cola offers fruit juice to same customers using same distribution channel and marketing set up.

1.2.2 Vertical Diversification

In vertical diversification, a firm enters the upstream or downstream of production and operating activities of products. In vertical diversification, a firm adds new product lines complimentary to existing products. The vertical diversification can be of two types:

1. Diversification by backward integration: In this type of diversification, firm diversifies to previous stage of its production cycle. A textile manufacturer acquiring farmland to produce cotton is an example of diversification by backward integration. In this case, a textile manufacturer manufactures its own inputs rather than buying inputs from outside. The backward integration offers regular supplies of inputs to the firm.
2. Diversification by forward integration: In this type of diversification, firm diversifies forward to subsequent stages of production cycle. For example, a textile manufacturer

starting its own network of shops. The forward integration reduces dependence on customers or distributors.

1.2.3 Concentric Diversification

In concentric diversification, firm carries out operations around a centre with its technologies, strengths, resources, and experience. The concentric diversification can be related market, related technology, or both. The concentric diversification aims to fully utilize the potential of existing facilities, technologies, and marketing system.

1.2.4 Lateral or Conglomerate or Unrelated Diversification

In unrelated diversification, a firm adds new product line that are significantly different from the existing product lines offered by the firm. In conglomerate diversification, firm diversifies into an area entirely different from its current business. The new business has no connection with current technologies, markets, distribution channels, and products. Conglomerate diversification allows a firm to exploit new opportunities outside its line of business. A liquor manufacturer entering in airlines business is an example of unrelated diversification as an airlines business has no direct connection with technologies, markets, or distribution channels of a liquor business. In unrelated diversification, a firm does not enjoy the benefits of synergy.

1.3 Risks of Diversification

Risks of diversification is very important consideration for firms who decide to diversify business. A firm may face following types of risks of diversification:

1. Risk of cross-industry investment: A firm entering a new business faces entry barrier. Firms face risk of cross-industry market development, and cross-industry technology development.
2. Risk of cross-industry subsidy: A diversified firm has different investment efficiencies and profitability in different industries. A diversified firm may tend to subsidize loss in one business with the profit from another. This cross-industry subsidy may weaken the company as a whole.
3. Risk of over investment: The diversified operation creates internal capital market for a firm. A firm can allocate different capital flows arising from different businesses. As internal capital market provides more disposable income, a firm may tend to make over-investment.
4. Risk of operation and management: Diversified operation increases operational and management complexities, and give birth to more departments, divisions, and companies. This enlarges the management span of top level management. Sharing of resources across departments and businesses increases interdependence, and hence difficulties of monitoring and control.
5. Risk of information asymmetry: Due to large size of operation and wide scope of businesses, usually a diversified firm is run by distribution of power. As a result, managers of each department and at top level have to share asymmetric information. Cost of asymmetric information may be too high.

6. Risk of resource decentralization: A diversified firm has to reallocate resources (labor, material, and financial resources). Coupled with risk of cross-industry subsidy, resource decentralization may increase instability of business operation. (Lin, 2011) [2]

7. Financial risk: As compared to a single business firm, a diversified firm demands more financial resources. As a firm has limited power of equity financing, increasing capital requirement increases debt in capital structure. High debt in capital structure increases financial risk.

1.4 Motivations for Diversification

The motivations of corporate diversification can be internal or external.

Internal motivations of diversification:

1. Economies of scale/Scope: Through diversification, a firm tries to lower cost through achieving economies of scale and/or economies of scope.
2. Internal resource allocation: The diversification allows a firm to allocate internal resources more efficiently. Diversification also allows a firm to share resources among businesses and achieve higher utilization of resources.
3. Risk distribution: Diversification has been a popular strategy to mitigate risk. Through diversification a firm can mitigate diversifiable risk.

External motivations for diversification:

1. Effect of principal-agent: The agents (managers) use diversification strategy to expand span of power, employment opportunities, and financial benefits. Diversified operation could lower the risk of human capital for managers.

2. Effect of increasing or acquiring core competence: Diversified business provides opportunities to enhance core competence of a firm by application of current core competencies in new businesses. Diversification also improves the core competencies of the firm by integrating current core competencies with new competencies gained from new businesses. (Lin, 2011) [3]

To understand the performance of a diversified firm, understanding the motivation of diversification acts as a starting point. To assess if diversification has improved firm's performance, it is very important to understand why the firm has decided to diversify.

There are four theories that can explain motivation for diversification:

1. Transaction cost economic theory
2. Resource based view
3. Market power theory
4. Agency theory

1.4.1 Transaction cost economic theory

Transaction cost refers to the cost incurred in making an economic exchange. Transaction cost includes cost incurred in finding best suppliers, customers, and business partners; cost of drawing a tamper proof contract, and cost of monitoring and implementing these contracts. The transaction costs are coordination costs.

According to transaction cost economic theory, all economic activities are economic behaviour. All firms are indulged in an economic exchange. The behaviour of the agent is confined by

opportunism and bounded rationality. Market transactions induce costs. Firm is a contract structure that supplants imperfect exchange that try to lower the transaction cost to lower cost and improve competitiveness.

The vertical integration is a popular way of diversification. The transaction cost theory explains how vertical integration deals with ex-post contract cost. Firm's rent generating resources are exchanged through market process. The transaction incurs high contractual hazards such as secrecy, loyalty, licenses, learning curve advantage problems. A firm can avoid such hazards through vertical integration. (Silverman, 1999) [4] Internalization (through vertical integration) reduces transaction cost, but organization incurs economic cost in managing hierarchies. The transaction cost theory explains why firms do not market. If firms find diversification an efficient alternative to the market contracting, they choose to diversify.

When firm has to decide – “make or buy”, firms prefer to “make” if it wants to avoid contractual hazards and reduce transaction cost. This explains why firms diversify through vertical integration. However, transaction cost theory fails to explain diversification when diversification is not done through vertical integration. For example, if firm has excess resources, transaction cost theory fails to explain why firm should not specialize to exploit the excess resources.

1.4.2 Resource-based Theory

Resources are scarce. Firms compete with each other to acquire and control scarce resources. The resources play very important role in developing the strategy of a firm. The internal and external resources enable a firm to compete in competitive market. (Wernerfelt, 1984) [5]; (Barney et. al., 2001) [6].The resource based theory explains how a firm can exploit its

resources to achieve its goals and create sustainable competitive advantage over competitors. The resource based theory can explain diversification strategy of a firm as an attempt to profitably deploy and exploit its scarce resources.

Penrose (1959) [7] in her “theory of the growth of the firm” argues that firms diversify because of excess capacity in productive factors or resources. Early theories identified that firms adopted diversification strategy to exploit economic scope of excess resources. Later, researchers expanded the scope of resources and included intangible resources like services, human resources, knowledge etc. (Teece, 1980) [8]; (Nelson & Winter, 1982) [9]; (Lippman & Rumelt, 1982) [10] Firms adopt the strategy of merger and acquisition to buy or sell resources in bundle.

A firm’s resource base affects the choice of industry a firm diversifies into. Firms may either choose to diversify in related business or in unrelated business. Firms having excess resources tend to diversify into industries having similar R&D, marketing, production pattern, and other relatedness so that the resource requirement in that industry matches with the resource capabilities of the firm. (Silverman, 1999) [11] Diversification in related industry creates synergy and benefits the firm. The resource based theory helps to understand a firm’s motive to diversify in a particular industry.

1.4.3 Market Power Theory

Market power refers to the ability of a firm to influence price by influencing demand and/or supply of a product. The market power theory also explains why firms diversify. A firm having market power is able to influence the price to its benefit. In general, market power also measures the amount of influence firm has in the industry.

A large firm, especially conglomerate, has power to influence demand and supply of a product. The conglomerate mergers and acquisitions enhance the market power of the firms. The conglomerates diversify in new industry to have market power in that industry as well. As Hill (1985) [12] argues, greater the number of markets a firm has dominant position in, greater the market power a firm enjoys. Greater market power allows the firm to raise price in industries where it has dominant position, and earn higher profit. With this profit, firm can subsidize the cost of activities in competitive industries.

The researchers argue that diversification can increase the market power of a firm. But, there is no consensus on how diversification can increase market power. There are two types of views on this:

Structure point of view: According to this view, market structure determines the economic performance of a firm. This view focuses on influence of diversification on market structure variables. According to structure point of view, a firm may diversify in a market if diversification raises entry barrier and helps the diversified firms to achieve dominant position. If a firm can achieve dominant position in the market, firm can get supernormal rent.

Behaviour point of view: This view believes that corporate practice is much more important than the market structure. According to this theory, even a monopolist would not necessarily possess market power. Corporate practice and behaviour has great impact on the economic performance of a firm. To gain market power in an industry, a firm would focus on anti-competition strategic practice. A firm would diversify if diversification facilitates anti-competition strategic practices.

According to market power theory, there should be a positive relationship between diversification and corporate performance as a diversified firm may improve its market power in an industry and influence price to its benefit. However, Montgomery (1985) [13] argues that market power theory has put unnecessary emphasis on general market power and underemphasized specific market power that gives an undiversified firm competitive advantage in market. Montgomery (1985) argues that there exists slightly positive relationship between diversification and corporate performance because of economies of scope, not market power.

An industry having high concentration ratio (i.e. less competitive industry) expects more profitable economic performance. But, there are few large firms dominating the market. The relationship between concentration ratio and economic performance is clear for the industry, but same is not true for the firms. First, not all dominant firms achieve more profitable economic performance in a high concentration ratio industry. Second, if a firm diversifies into an industry dominated by few large firms, it does not guarantee that firm diversifying in this industry will also achieve dominant position and market power.

1.4.4 Agency Theory

Agency theory explains the relationship between principal and agents. In any organization, shareholders are the principals and managers are agents. The principals (shareholders) hire the agents (managers) to perform the services on principal's behalf. The Agency theory was given by Berle & Gardiner (1932) [14], which explains the conflict of interest between shareholders and managers. According to this theory, both principals and agents are opportunists who try to maximize their own benefits. The managers may not always act in the best interest of

shareholders. The agents (managers) tend to take decisions which can benefit the managers, even at the cost of interest of shareholders.

If diversification generates benefit for managers, the managers may take the decision of diversification even though it does not benefit the organization. If a firm diversifies into new business, more managers get opportunities to hold higher positions. They also get challenging role and opportunity to earn higher bonus. So, managers are motivated to diversify the firm.

Mueller (1972) [15] in his studies found that the managers (agents) enjoy lower marginal cost of capital curve than the principal, which motivates the managers to overinvest and make the firm bigger in terms of assets and revenue even at the expense of shareholder's wealth. The managers adopt growth-maximization strategy even if it does not maximize profit and shareholder's wealth. Mueller established that managers tend to build empire even at the cost of shareholder's interest.

Managers prefer to control more resources. Diversification allows the managers to have more resources under their control. Managers get more control over cash flows, human resources, and other resources. (Jensen, 1986) [16] Managers' compensation is directly linked to revenue growth. So, managers get higher compensation (Ueng & Wells, 2001) [17], or managers reduce their human capital risk (Denis & Denis, 1997) [18].

In general, researchers are of view that diversification is a result of agent-principal relationship which can be explained using Agency theory. However, there are some researches which show

that diversification reduces agency cost. Lubatkin & Chatterjee (1994) [19] argue that diversification is in the interest of shareholders as it reduces their risk that could not be diversified through investment portfolio. So, diversification actually aids to the wealth maximization of shareholders.

For decades, managers have been pursuing diversification as a strategy to achieve growth and competitive advantage. In developing countries also, large enterprises have diversified their businesses to achieve higher growth. In India, large businesses houses like TATA, Reliance, Birla, Adani, Ruia Group, etc have business interests in several industries. The diversification decision can either be a Related Diversification, or Unrelated Diversification.

There are several examples where diversification has been a bad decision for the firm. There has been continuous debate on effectiveness of diversification strategy. Many companies divested acquisitions as they were unable to create value for shareholders. Many companies realized their mistake of diversification and initiated large-scale restructuring programs. (Porter, 1987) [20] When a company diversifies into a new business, resources are allocated to new business. Same resources could be used by the firm in existing business to generate higher returns. Diversification in new business also requires additional financing. A firm may finance the diversification using debt or equity. Funding with debt requires the firm to pay interest on the debt, which increases financial burden. Diversifying in a business where firm has no prior experience, is risky. The related diversification may improve effectiveness of the firm because of synergy, but that argument does not apply to unrelated diversification. Still, there are companies around the world who go for unrelated diversification.

1.5 Rationale for Diversification for Indian Firms

1.5.1 Rationale for Related Diversification

The major rationale for related diversification is based on the concept that relatedness between different businesses create synergy. Businesses can exploit synergy to create competitive advantage over undiversified competitors. The concept of “relatedness” and competitive advantage can be explained through following approaches:

1. Relatedness based on tangible operation and market linkages
2. Relatedness based on competence and knowledge
3. Relatedness as a basis for *market power*

1.5.1.1 Relatedness based on tangible operational and market linkages

This approach is traditional industrial approach to find relatedness among businesses. Tangible relatedness arises from opportunities to share activities in the value chain of businesses due to presence of same set of buyers, distribution channels, marketing channels, technologies, production facility and other factors. (Porter, 1985) [21] The relatedness of businesses create “economies of scope”, which lowers per unit cost due to resource sharing.

Diversification into complementary products is one important type of market relatedness exploited by the managers in every industry. The buyers purchase complementary products together. For example, a notebook buyer purchases software and accessories such as headphone and wireless keyboard. There are three strategic practices to control complementary products:

1. Offering complementary products as standalone products.
2. Bundling complementary products to sell as a package. For example, a computer manufacturer sells computer preloaded with operating system, antivirus and other utility software as a bundle to the customers.

3. Cross-subsidization of complementary products is a practice where a firm deliberately sells a good at low profit or at loss so that firm can sell more numbers of complementary goods having higher profit margin. Hewlett Packard has adopted this strategy in printer business. The cartridge of printer has higher profit margin, and being a consumable, cartridges are purchased repeatedly. HP sells printers at lower price to create more demand for cartridges. By selling cartridges to the customers, HP earns higher profit.

(Porter, 1985) [22]

Traditionally, firms have been diversifying in businesses which are related based on tangible operational and market linkages. Such relatedness is clearly visible and hence synergy can be expected by diversifying in such related businesses.

1.5.1.2 Relatedness based on cross-business transfer of competences and knowledge

This type of relatedness among businesses is based on resource-based view of the firms which concern intangible resources. A firm can diversify in businesses where existing know-how and competence can be leveraged to create competitive advantage. (Penrose, 1959) [23] Knowledge and know-how of technology can be a core-competence, and can be shared among several businesses. If a firm has already developed knowledge competence, transferring these intangible resources to a new business can save costs and enhance competitiveness. The diversified corporations should be viewed as a collection of competitively important competencies that can be used in different product lines and markets. (Prahalad & Hamel, 1990) [24] As explained by transaction cost theory, a firm can lower the cost by diversifying business than through leasing or selling the underused assets as transaction cost is high. Applying the same concept, a firm should diversify into businesses where it can use its intangible assets.

1.5.1.3 Relatedness as the basis for market power

A firm may enhance profitability by creating market power and limit the competition in the market. Large diversified firms may have upper hand over specialized firms as:

1. Large firms are better placed to compete with global firms as large firms have capability to cross-subsidize. (Yip, 1992) [25] Through cross-subsidization, a large firm can artificially create high entry barrier in an industry to prevent new entrants from entering the market.
2. Presence in many businesses may allow a firm to get favorable rate from supplier. A business can also give preference to a supplier in one business who has become a loyal customer in some other business.
3. A large firm also have more power to influence the stakeholders as they have more options for actions.
4. By offering complementary products, a firm can position itself as “total solution” provider, and increase switching cost for customers.

However, often firms trying to increase market power ends up diversifying into unrelated business.

Firms diversify in related businesses as sharing of activities and resources lead to cost saving, better utilization of facilities and assets, and exploitation of interrelationships. But, diversification also brings with it several additional costs. Diversification increases requirement of coordination among businesses. Greater the complexity of shared resources and activities, higher the cost of coordination. Sharing of resources and activities also forces some

businesses to compromise as other businesses may require higher amount of resources. Limited information processing capability at higher level of organizational hierarchy, and inability to deal with large amount of contradictory information flowing from various sources limit the potential of a firm to benefit from diversification.

1.5.2 Rationale for Unrelated Diversification

While main rationale for related diversification is to create synergy, rationale for unrelated diversification is less clear. The rationales for unrelated diversification may be listed as follows:

1.5.2.1 Cognitive Relatedness

Some researchers argue that unrelated diversification may be successful because of “cognitive relatedness” of many businesses. At first sight, these businesses may seem to be unrelated. But, there may be elusive linkage between businesses. Prahalad and Bettis (1986) [26] argue that strategically similar businesses can be managed using single dominant logic. The managers can conceptualize the businesses and use same dominant logic to allocate resources to different businesses. Strategic similarities may be found between businesses having tangible form of relatedness as well as between unrelated businesses

1.5.2.2 Cluster Managers

The conglomerates own divisions and groups which are engaged in businesses in unrelated sectors. Within the groups or divisions, they have cluster of related businesses. The divisions of these conglomerates have high degree of autonomy. Each division manages a cluster of related businesses and create competitive advantage at division level. Though, at corporate level, conglomerates fail to create synergy. While making a decision to enter a new line of

business, a conglomerate looks for relatedness of the business with a division, and how this relatedness can create synergy.

1.5.2.3 Risk Management

Another argument in favour of diversification into unrelated business has been that unrelated business allows a firm to balance risk and return from independent businesses, and hence provide stability. Presence in many independent businesses provide a firm chance to pursue more flexible long-term strategies. Such firms are also able to raise cheaper capital as compared to a single business firm because well diversified firms are better placed to handle risks. Many researchers argue against this line of thought as investors can achieve diversification of portfolio simply by diversifying their investment in multiple firms.

1.5.2.4 Use of talent and management resources

This rationale is based on resource-based theory. If a firm has talent pool, know-how, and management resources that can be used in unrelated business, firm may choose to diversify in unrelated business. Diversification in unrelated business may also give a firm opportunity to develop human resources, attract best management talents, and get access to new technology and know-how.

1.6 Economic and Regulatory Framework in India

Economic development is one of the main objectives of any country. Post-independence, India was one of the few non-communist countries who implemented full-fledged industrial policy. During the period of 1950-1980, the industrial policy of India was centred on five-year plans, which was a state-directed model of industrialization. The state would decide the quantum of production, and grant businesses permission to produce goods. Government would issue

licenses and set quota on production. While five-year plan was instrumental in starting industrialization in India, by 1980, industrial growth dipped sharply. In the period of 1980s, first phase of industrial reform started. This period can be termed as a period of industrial recovery. Many branches of manufacturing (such as automobile, cement, food processing, and textile) witnessed modernization and expansion of scale. During this period, focus shifted from quota to tariff. (Sharma, 2014) [27] In Indian economy, after severe economic crisis, liberalization started in 1991 when government undertook policy reforms and implemented the New Economic Policy.

The balance of payments crisis in 1991, and need of reduction in fiscal deficit forced the government to undertake reforms. The policy reforms successfully reduced fiscal deficit of the central government from 8.3% of GDP in 1990-91 to 7.7% of GDP in 1993-94, which further fell down to 6.8% of GDP in 1994-95. (Source: Planning Commission Annual Report 1995-96) [28] The balance of payment crisis was also over by 1993. The long-term positive impact of policy reforms are on industrial policy of India. Prior to 1991, the industrial policy was characterized by multiple controls over private investments, government deciding areas where private investment was allowed, and scale of operation. This industrial structure was highly inefficient, and needed protective trade policy. The license raj also forced the businesses to look for opportunities outside related businesses to achieve growth. The pre-reform industrial policy encouraged unrelated product diversification and creation of conglomerates where diversification decisions were influenced by industrial policy rather than efficiency.

The New Economic Policy (NEP) of 1991 brought great changes. Government control was dismantled in most of the industries. Only 3 industries were reserved solely for public sectors – defence, atomic energy, and railway transport. Industrial licenses by government was

abolished except few hazardous industries. The import licenses were abolished and businesses were allowed to import technology. Switch to flexible exchange rate regime also supported globalization and attracted foreign direct investment (FDI). Foreign Direct Investment was a very important part of reform and it shaped Indian industries over next three decades. The NEP allowed 100% foreign investment in a large number of industries except banking, insurance, telecommunication, and airlines. Government also simplified the approval process and getting permissions. In certain sectors, foreign investment was capped up to 49%. (Ahluwalia, 2002) [29]

The post-reform period (1991-till now) has seen considerable fluctuation and a lack of consistency in industrial growth. In addition to industrial policy and macroeconomic condition of India, global economic conditions also had great influence on industrial growth of India. The industrial production started growing since 1992-93 and achieved a growth of 2.3% in 1992-93, 6% in 1993-94, 9.1% in 1994-95, and 13% in 1995-96. Industrial growth rate peaked in 1995-96 and slowed down to 6.1% in 1996-97. The downward trend of industrial growth continued. In 1998-99, industrial growth fell down to 4.1%. Decline in industrial growth had direct negative impact on demand and export of certain industries. The industrial growth witnessed turnaround in 1999-2000 and achieved a growth rate of 6.7%. But in 2000-01. Industrial growth dipped again to 5%. Between 1991-2000 period, average industry growth was 6% with 6.3% growth in manufacturing, 3.3% growth in mining, and 6.6% growth in electricity.

World economy witnessed dotcom bubble burst in 2001-02. Industrial growth rate dipped with great intensity with a significant deceleration across industries. After 2004, industrial production started improving and peaked in 2008. The global recession during 2008-10 had

adverse impact on Indian economy. The industrial growth rate turned negative in 2008. The year 2009-11 witnessed revival of world economy. In 2009-10, industrial growth rate shot up to 10.3% and in 2010-11 to 8.2%. Diagram-1.1 presents industrial growth rate of India between 1991 and 2016.

Diagram 1.1: Industrial Growth Rate between 1991 and 2016

Dasgupta & Singh (2005) [30] established that growth of manufacturing and services is closely related to GDP growth. This study also established positive correlation between growth of services and growth of manufacturing. Growth of services sector depends on growth of manufacturing sector. Especially certain types of services, like retailing and transportation have greater dependency on manufacturing. But export oriented services such as software services have greater dependency on global economic conditions.

Between 2000 and 2010, world economy witnessed two shocking events. The bubble burst in 2002 hit world economy hard. Indian economy was also affected by global slowdown. In 2001-02, Indian GDP dipped sharply. As world economy recovered, Indian economy also recovered sharply. In 2005, Indian GDP fell again. Between 2005 and 2008, Indian GDP registered

healthy growth. During this period, India was one of the fastest growing economies in world. In 2008, the United States of America, and some other developed economies were going through financial crisis. The financial crisis of 2008-09 had adverse impact on world economy. The Indian economy also felt the impact. There were clear indications of recession in Indian economy, especially in industrial sector. In line with global economy, Indian GDP growth rate also suffered. But, India still managed to record positive GDP growth rate when most of the strong economies were witnessing negative growth. The governments and central banks took drastic measures to revive the economy. In India too, government adopted expansionary fiscal policy, and RBI adopted liberal monetary policy to revive the economy. In 2009-10, Indian economy recovered fast and registered very impressive GDP growth. The GDP growth rate of India between 2001 and 2016 is shown in Table-1.2.

Diagram- 1.2: GDP Growth Rate of India between 2001 and 2016

Between 2000 and 2010, the economic and regulatory environment of India has been volatile. During this period, Indian economy has gone through two major slowdowns. Change in political environment (transfer of power from NDA to UPA in 2004) also added to uncertainty.

In India, change of government has significant impact on economic policies. Broadly, all governments pursued liberal economic policies, and encouraged FDI, lowered tariff, and encouraged competition across industries. Consistency in government policies installed confidence in foreign investors, and attracted foreign investment to India. Fuelled by foreign investment and growth in service industry, Indian economy registered impressive growth between 2000 and 2010. During this period, contribution of service sectors in Indian GDP increased significantly. Comparatively subdued growth in manufacturing companies forced the companies in these industries look for avenues where they can achieve high growth.

Based on changes in economic and regulatory environment, the period of study can be divided into three parts:

Period 2000-01 to 2002-03

During this period, economic growth peaked in 2001. Since 2001, economic growth declined. In 2002, impact of global slowdown was felt in India also. At that time, Indian economy was not very strong. Government took some steps for recovery of the economy. By the end of 2003, positive impact of government policies started to become visible. During this period, service sector was growing at much faster pace than manufacturing sector. High growth of service sector led companies to venture out in industries promising high growth, and having cognitive relation with existing business. For example, Power grid Corporation entered into wired telecommunication business which was one of the fastest growing businesses. Another such example of diversification was NTPC who entered into power trading and consultancy business. Maruti Suzuki entered into complementary business of selling motor insurance.

Period 2003-04 to 2006-07

During this period, Indian economy registered impressive growth. Government took several steps to liberalize the economy. During this period, India witnessed high foreign capital inflow which fuelled growth. The new government at centre in 2004 did not alter previous government's economic policy. This installed faith in domestic as well as foreign investors. Steps were taken to make regulatory system more effective. During this period, SEBI and other regulators gained more power to regulate the capital market. Indian GDP growth peaked in 2007. Companies in oil and gas sector diversified during this period as oil sector was deregulated on April 1st, 2002. (Thomas, 2002) [31] Traditionally, oil and gas sector was dominated by public sector companies. Deregulation of oil sector forced the oil companies to look for ways to create sustainable competitive advantage. The oil companies entered in new businesses to achieve vertical integration and create competitive advantage to mitigate the negative impact of competition from private players. Other companies diversifying during this period were mainly motivated by potential of leveraging resources to achieve higher growth.

Period 2007-08 to 2010-11

This period witnessed one of the deadliest recession and dramatic recovery. During the global recession of 2008, world economy nosedived. Across the world, government and central banks took several measures, including some untraditional steps to stimulate the economy. In the U.S., government had to bail out many giants including General Motors, Ford Motors, and Citi Bank. Many large companies went bankrupt which included Lehman Brothers. In India too, economic growth slowed down. RBI pursued liberal monetary policy to stimulate the economy. Interest rate came down sharply. Some Indian firms looked for merger and acquisition opportunities abroad. The coordinated action by governments and central banks stimulated the economy. In line with global economy, Indian economy also recovered sharply. Indian economy registered impressive growth during 2009-10 and 2010-11. This period is also

known as paradigm shift in regulatory environment. The regulators felt the need of more transparency in Indian businesses. Business ethics also found more support during this period, and played significant role in shaping Indian regulatory framework. Many companies diversified to create new line of business. Post-recession, companies identified some sectors where there were immense growth opportunities. During the recession, many old companies lost market power and new companies emerged as more powerful. Such companies tried to enter into new businesses and add more promising businesses to their portfolio. For example, Ashok Leyland entered into manufacturing of defence products, Amtek Auto entered into manufacturing of railway locomotives, and Apar Industries entered into manufacturing of automotive lubricants.

1.7 Relevance of the Study

For more than six decades, diversification has been a dominant strategy for firms to achieve growth and create competitive advantage. The second half of 20th century was an era of diversification. Large number of studies have been conducted to examine the effects of diversification on corporate performance. The empirical findings on corporate diversification show that diversified firms trade at a discount relative to undiversified firms. (Montgomery & Wernerfelt, 1988) [32] While diversification into related business creates synergy, unrelated diversification does not create synergy. Still, many firms diversify into unrelated businesses through unrelated acquisitions. Many of such acquisitions are divested subsequently. (Kaplan & Weisbach, 1992) [33] Unrelated diversification is widely believed to be inefficient. Majority of studies found negative relationship between diversification and corporate performance. (Agrawal et al., 1992) [34]; (Lang & Stulz, 1994) [35]; (Berger & Ofek, 1995) [36]; (Hyland & Diltz, 2002) [37] Empirical evidences imply that in general, unrelated diversification is not a beneficial practice for firms.

Though majority of the studies have established negative relationship between diversification and corporate performance, around the world many successful companies have diversified product portfolio. Diversification is widely considered as an effective strategy to achieve higher growth, better financial performance, and mitigate risk. Global conglomerates like GE and Samsung, and in India, TATA, Birla, Reliance and other conglomerates have been successful in creating wealth for shareholders. Several studies are conducted to establish relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. While majority of studies found unrelated diversification inefficient, few studies also supported the unrelated diversification.

Majority of studies finding negative relationship between diversification and corporate performance are conducted in the USA and other developed countries. However, many of successful American companies have diversified portfolio. Some studies argue that superior performance of diversified firms is not because of diversification per se. (Graham, Lemon and Wolf, 2002) [38]; (Christensen and Montgomery, 1981) [39]. The political and business environment of developing countries are different from those of developed countries. In developing countries, generally large enterprises are conglomerates. Especially in emerging markets such as India, most of the successfully companies have business interest in multiple industries. The developing countries like BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) are growing at very fast rate and they are poised to become economic super powers. China has already surpassed Japan to become the second largest economy in the world. The business, political, and social environment in a developing countries are quite different from the business, political, and social environment in developed countries. So, impact of diversification on corporate performance in developing countries may be different from the impact observed in developed countries.

In India, before 1991, there were licenses and quotas imposed on businesses. A firm could not exceed the quota of production even though there were demand. A company needed to get license to operate a business. This forced businesses to diversify in new businesses to achieve growth and earn higher profit. So, diversification became a popular practice for firms. But after liberalization in 1991, a firm could focus on its core business and achieve growth. This shifted focus from diversification to building competitive advantage in core businesses. There is no denying that diversification mitigates unsystematic risk. Shareholders can diversify their investment portfolio to mitigate unsystematic risk, but diversification of business further contributes to their risk mitigation strategy. However, more often than not, the agency cost outweighs the benefits from diversification. Majority of researches find negative relationship between diversification and corporate performance. But, very few researches studied impact of diversification on corporate performance in emerging markets.

The related diversification may generate synergy and improve effectiveness of firms. The empirical evidences could not conclusively establish positive or negative relation between diversification and corporate performance in emerging markets. Each emerging market has different business and regulatory environment. Hence, results of a study conducted in one emerging market may not be hold true in another emerging market. There is need to study the impact of unrelated diversification on corporate performance in individual emerging markets.

Indian economy is growing at near 7%. With large young population, high economic growth, business friendly government policies, and availability of natural resources, India is poised to become a global economic superpower. As social and business environment of India is different from those of developed countries, there is need to conduct study in Indian

perspective. The study of impact of unrelated diversification on corporate performance in Indian perspective will be useful in strategy formulation for Indian companies as well as global investors investing in Indian firms. It will also provide an insight for diversification in other emerging markets. This study will add new knowledge to this field that can be used by the firms to assess the pros and cons of diversification and what a firm needs to do to improve corporate performance through diversification.

1.8 Research Objectives

This research study conducts theoretical and empirical investigation of relationship between unrelated diversification and corporate performance in Indian perspective. First objective of this study is to determine if there exists a relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. Next objective is, to study the impact of unrelated diversification on financial performance of the firms. The financial performance has several dimensions. This research studies impact of unrelated diversification on liquidity, profitability, efficiency and solvency risk of the firms.

Evaluation of impact of unrelated diversification on corporate performance is not the final purpose of this study. The impact of diversification on corporate performance is not merely an empirical phenomena. It is very important to understand why a firm diversifies. Rationality of diversification serves as the starting point to evaluate the impact of diversification on corporate performance. There are various reasons behind diversification, and explanations to justify the financial performance of a firm. But, there is no general theory available that can explain the big picture. This study also conducts theoretical investigation into diversification and corporate performance with respect to various theories on diversification.

Objectives of the research are as follows:

1. First objective of this research is to explore relationship between unrelated diversification and corporate performance for Indian firms.
2. To examine the impact of unrelated diversification on corporate financial performance. The financial performance has mainly four aspects: liquidity, profitability, efficiency and solvency risk. The objective of this research is to examine the impact of unrelated diversification on the liquidity position, profitability, efficiency, and solvency risk of Indian firms.
3. Size of a firm has substantial influence on its financial performance. A large size firm may have greater market power. At the same time, managing large size firm is more difficult and costly than managing a small size firm. One major objective of this study is to examine the impact of size of the firm on financial performance of the unrelated diversified Indian firms.
4. Corporate performance of diversified firms may not be uniform across industries. Some industries may have better access to resources than other industries. One major objective of this study is to identify industry-wise variation in financial performance of the unrelated diversified Indian firms.

1.9 Research Questions

This study focuses on following issues:

1. Nature of relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance.
2. Impact of diversification on corporate financial performance.
3. Determine impact of size on financial performance.
4. Determining driving factors for firms to make diversification decision.

5. Impact of economic and regulatory environment on diversification decisions.

Accordingly, this study will answer following research questions:

Question-1: What is the nature of relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance in Indian market?

Question-2: How does unrelated diversification impacts corporate financial performance with respect to liquidity, profitability, efficiency and solvency risk?

Question-3: What is the relationship between size of firm and corporate performance in Indian market?

Question-4: Is there industry-wise variation in corporate performance of diversified firms?

1.10 Research Structure

The rest of the paper is organized in five chapters.

1.10.1 Introduction

This chapter covers meaning of diversification as a corporate strategy, classification of diversification, benefits and risks of diversification, internal and motivations for diversification. This chapter also discusses various theories that can explain the motivation for diversification. This chapter further discusses rationales for related and unrelated diversification for Indian firms, and economic and regulatory framework in India. Then, this chapter states the research problems, outlines the relevance of the study, and discusses how

this study will add new knowledge to the field that can help the management in making diversification decisions.

1.10.2 Review of Literature

This chapter covers detailed review of literature on diversification. This study arranged and reviewed the literature in chronological order. Literature review includes books, journals, doctoral thesis, and government websites providing authentic data and information. It was found that oldest literature available on this topic is the book "The Modern Corporation and Private Property" published in 1932. The newest article reviewed was published in year 2016. Most of the work in this field are done in the U.S.A and other developed countries.

1.10.3 Theoretical Framework, Hypothesis Development and Research Methodology

This chapter covers detailed research methodology including data set, sample design, data collection methods, sources of data, and tools and techniques used in data analysis. This chapter also discusses theoretical framework in details. The hypotheses to be tested are developed. This chapter discusses in detail how hypotheses are tested.

1.10.4 Data Analysis and Interpretation (aggregate study, Industry wise study and size-wise study)

This chapter covers data analysis using various statistical tools, and interpretation of results. This chapter includes determination of relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance for Indian firms. This chapter also studies the impact of unrelated diversification on financial performance of the diversified firms. The financial performance is measured on four parameters: liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and solvency risk. This chapter also conducts industry-wise and size-wise study.

1.10.5 Summary of findings, Conclusion and Suggestions

This chapter summarizes major findings of the study, and presents conclusions and general observations of the study. This chapter also includes major limitations of the study and scope for further studies in this field.

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CHAPTER-2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

Post-World War-II, diversification has been a popular strategy to achieve higher growth and more market power. Many scholars and researchers made efforts to understand the impact of diversification on corporate performance. Since late 1960s researchers have been trying to assess the impact of diversification on corporate performance. Most of the studies in this field are conducted in developed countries. Later, growing importance of emerging markets led to growing interest in investigation into diversification in developing markets. Majority of the studies conducted in developed countries found negative relationship between unrelated diversification and corporate performance. Some studies are conducted in China and other developing markets. The studies conducted in developing markets could not conclusively established negative relationship between diversification and corporate performance. In developed markets, cost of diversification exceeds the benefits, but same is not true for developing markets. The developing markets are characterized as less developed capital market, inadequate legal protection, lack of availability of perfect information, and not so effective regulatory bodies. Thus, unrelated diversification could be more beneficial in developing markets than in developed markets.

The literature review for this study has taken research articles and some government published reports. Majority of the studies in this field are conducted in the U.S. Apart from the studies in the U.S., this study has made an attempt to include research articles from other markets as well. In India, very few studies are conducted in this field. For this review of literature, only the articles published in reputed journals, government publications, and dissertations of other studies are included. The list of journals includes Strategic Management Journal, Journal of

Political Economy, Harvard Business Review, Journal of Financial and Strategic Decisions, The Journal of Finance, The International Journal on Media Management, Asia Pacific Management Review, Chinese Business Review, Economic Institutions of Strategy Advances in Strategic Management, and Indian Journal of Finance. This study has reviewed and arranged the articles in chronological order. The oldest article reviewed first according to the year of publication. The oldest article reviewed was published in year 1981 and the latest article was published in the year 2016.

2.2 Literature Review

Christensen and Montgomery (1981) [1] investigated the relationship between degree of diversification and financial performance of the firm. A sample of Fortune 500 firms was taken in study. This study divided the firms in different categories based on degree of diversification, and regressed against financial performance of the firm during the period under consideration in study. This study was mainly focused on comparison of financial performance of related diversified firms in comparison with unrelated diversified firms. This study examined possible relationships among the structure of the industry, firms within the industry, and level of performance of individual firms vis-à-vis their associated industry. This paper concludes that financial performance of firms who adopted related diversification outperformed the financial performance of the firms who adopted unrelated diversification.

The lower performance of unrelated diversified firms may not be a result of market structure variables alone. Lower performance of unrelated diversified firms may have been caused because of lack of skills or resources to participate in new markets. There is need to investigate

the management system and corporate strategy of each firm to understand the cause of underperformance of unrelated diversified firms.

Chatterjee and Wernerfelt (1991)[2] studied the impact of resource profile on type of diversification a firm engages in. Rumelt (1974) established that related diversified firms perform better than those who engage in unrelated diversification. Post Rumelt, many researchers conducted research in this area. While many researchers support Rumelt's findings, growing number of researches find the opposite or are indifferent. The authors argue that though on average, related diversification is superior choice, in specific instances unrelated diversification may be a better choice. This study tries to identify systematic factors that influence a firm's diversification decision.

If a resource can be used to produce only one type of end-product, a firm cannot use that resource for unrelated diversification. But, if a firm possesses flexible resource (i.e. resource that can be used to produce more than one end-product), firm can diversify into new businesses and maximize the utilization of flexible resources. There are three classes of resources: (a) physical resources, (b) intangible resources, and (c) financial resources. While physical resources and intangible resources are fairly inflexible, financial resources are the most flexible. The physical and intangible resources can be used to enter into only closely related businesses. But, financial resources can be used for related as well as unrelated diversification. The financial resources can be of two types: internal funds, and debt. In this study, authors have used DEMKT (Ratio of long-term debt to market value), and current ratio as measure of financial resources. Performance is measured in terms of return on assets (ROA).

This study establishes direct association between surplus resources a firm possess and pattern of diversification. Excess physical resources and tangible resources are associated with more

related diversification. Excess internal financial resources are more related to unrelated diversification. A firm's ability to raise equity has no significant impact on the pattern of diversification.

Lang and Stulz (1994)[3] investigated the correlation between degree of diversification and market's valuation. Their paper focuses on Tobin's q rather than on performance over time. Tobin's q is present value of future cash flows divided by the replacement cost of tangible assets. Advantage of using Tobin's q is, no risk adjustment or normalization is required to compare Tobin's q across firms. This study compared Tobin's q of diversified firms to the Tobin's q of specialized firms between 1970s and 1980s. The firms having assets less than \$100 million were excluded from the study.

This study countered the view that conglomerates can operate more efficiently than specialized firms as internal capital market is more efficient in allocating resources than the external markets. Instead of focusing on transaction cost, this study investigated correlation between market's value and degree of diversification. This study found Tobin's q of diversified firms are lower than that of specialized firms. The Tobin's q falls as diversification increases. The study concludes that diversification does not lead to higher performance. There is negative correlation between diversification and Tobin's q. The firms who chose to diversify performed poor relative to the firms who did not diversify. Diversification did not provide the firms valuable intangible assets that could improve their performance. But, there is not enough evidence to determine which diversification hurts performance. The firms who diversified were already performing poorly before diversification. It indicates that poor performance of diversified firms cannot be mainly because they diversify. There is need to investigate diversification at more disaggregated level.

During late 1960s and early 1970s, there was trend of diversification. Recently, trend has reversed and companies are becoming more focused. Servaes (1996)[4] investigated if diversification led to higher market value during 1960s and 1970s. This study used a sample of firms from 1961 to 1976, and examined if diversification adds value. Diversification would add value only if benefits of diversification outweigh costs.

This study finds no evidence that diversified firms are valued more than focused firms in 1960s and 1970s. For years, diversified firms were being sold at a substantial discount as compared to focused firms. Another important finding of this study is, diversified firms were selling at higher discount to focused firms when diversified firms had lower insider ownership. Thus, when diversification was costly to shareholders, insider ownership was an effective deterrent to diversification. However, this study does not suggest any impact of agency cost on discount.

This study tries to determine the factors that affect the diversification discount change over a period of time. Less profitable firms trade at a discount to similar firms with higher profitability. If diversified firms are systematically less profitable than focused firms, the diversified firms would trade at a discount to the single segment firms. Over time, if this difference in profitability between diversified firms and single segment firms changes, diversification discount will also change. Another important factor affecting diversification discount is difference in capital structure as valuation and level of leverage are related. Third important factor is investment level. The diversified firms are likely to overinvest as cash flows from profitable segments are used to finance poor investments in business segments generating negative cash flows.

In Western economies, firms are focused on creating and maintaining core competencies. But emerging markets are still dominated by large diversified firms. In emerging markets, focused companies are unable to raise adequate capital or acquire skilled manpower because of ineffective securities regulations, lack of venture capital firms, and lack of strong educational institutions.

Khanna and Palepu (1997)[5] argue that institutional context drives strategy. The institutional dimensions are: capital market, labor market, product market, government regulation, and contract enforcement. The institutional contexts of developed countries and emerging market are quite different. This paper compares institutional context of USA, Japan, and India. In USA, diversified groups have many disadvantages, in Japan diversified groups have some advantages, and in India diversified groups have many advantages. This study suggests that diversified business groups may be more suitable to the institutional context in many developing countries including India because of their underdeveloped capital market, inadequate regulatory protection, and different social structure. This study lists a number of reasons why focused strategies may be wrong in emerging markets. The emerging markets have underdeveloped and illiquid equity markets, nationalized banks, weak regulatory system, few good educational institutes that results in scarcity of skilled manpower, limited enforcement of liability laws, high government regulations, corruption, and unpredictable contract enforcement which result in advantages for diversified groups. The conglomerates can add value in emerging markets. This paper finds out the reasons why Chaebols of Korea, business houses of India, and the groups of Latin America are more successful than focused businesses in these countries. This paper also lists reasons why focused strategies may not be suitable for emerging markets.

The results of this paper is not based on empirical evidences. There is need to conduct empirical research to determine if diversification is more successful in emerging markets than focused strategies.

Method of financing also influences diversification strategy of a firm. Kochhar and Hitt (1998)[6] examined the relationship between diversification strategy and method of financing of diversification. Diversification strategy is costly to implement. It requires significant internal and external resources. A firm can use debt financing or equity financing to finance its corporate strategy. Another classification of financing is private financing and public financing. The mode of financing largely depends on the nature of business entered by a firm, relatedness of the new business with existing core business of the firm, and availability of resources controlled by the existing businesses of the firm.

This study argues that related diversification adds more specific assets as compared to unrelated diversification. The potential suppliers of funds bear higher risk in financing related diversification as they face greater expected risk of loss of value. If the firm becomes bankrupt, the suppliers of funds will lose more value. In case of unrelated diversification, suppliers of funds face less risk of loss of value as unrelated diversification adds less specific assets. Thus, equity financing is preferred in financing related diversification and debt financing is preferred in financing unrelated diversification. This study further argues that diversification through acquisitions are more likely to be financed through public sources of financing, and diversifications through internal development are more likely to be financed through private sources of financing.

Pandya and Rao (1998)[7] examined if firm level diversification has any impact of firm's performance. The authors conducted study on a sample of 1195 firms in single product

category, 280 firms in the moderately diversified groups and 23 firms in highly diversified groups. The firms are classified based on Rumelt's classification scheme which is based on Specialization ratio. In this paper, authors used Specialization Ratio (SR) to measure degree of diversification. Specialization ratio is ratio of a firm's revenues derived from its largest single business to total revenue.

- SR \geq 0.95 Firm is undiversified
- 0.95 < SR \leq 0.7 Firm is moderately diversified
- SR < 0.7 Firm is highly diversified

The authors have identified three measures of performance: Return on Equity (ROE), Return on Investment (ROI) and Return on Assets (ROA). The ROA is the most frequently used measure of performance in previous studies. This study used ROA as a measure of performance.

This study finds that diversified firms perform better than undiversified firms on risk dimension as well as on return. The undiversified firms generate higher return with higher variance. On the other hand, highly diversified firms report lower return and much lower variance. The authors argue that undiversified firms give better return but their riskiness is also very high. They can improve their risk-return balance through diversification.

This study does not examine the differences in performance caused by related or unrelated diversification, or impact of firm size or other factors.

Lins and Servaes (1999)[8] examined whether companies in developed markets (Germany, Japan, and United Kingdom) have been able to overcome costs associated with diversification

and enhance shareholder's wealth. The institutional environment in Germany and Japan is different from that of USA. But, in spite of overall similarities in institutional environment in Germany and Japan, there are differences in organizational structure and ownership structure. On the other hand, the institutional environment of UK is similar to USA.

In this study, data between 1994 to 1996 for publicly traded firms (excluding financial institutions) were studied. Data of 174 firms in Germany, 808 firms in Japan and 391 firms in UK was collected for study. In this study, firms are considered as diversified if they report sales in two or more segments. The industry segments are defined at the two digit SIC code level. The analysis is solely based on sales. The market to sales ratios are used to value diversified firms.

This study finds that diversification reduced shareholders wealth in UK and Japan. But, no evidence was found that diversification reduced shareholders wealth in Germany. The results may also be influenced by differences in accounting treatment of revenues in different countries. To overcome this problem, the authors removed all firms from sample who do not report consolidated financial statements. The findings of this study suggest that value of diversification is directly related to a country's institutional structure.

The institutional structure of emerging markets is different from those of the developed markets. Thus, the findings of studies conducted in developed markets may not be valid in emerging markets. There is need to conduct studies based on data from emerging markets alone where there are similarities in institutional structure.

The dissertation submitted by Pawaskar (1999)[9] studied the impact of diversification on firm performance of Indian private sector manufacturing firms. This paper studied a sample of 524 private sector manufacturing firms for a period from 1991 to 1995. The excess profitability of the diversified firms was compared with industry average profitability.

This study finds that diversification decision has differential impact on firm performance depending on asset utilization ratio. The new entrants performed better as the new entrants have more intangible assets or excess capacity in tangible assets that reduce opportunity cost to entry in new industries, and hence improves return. The firms who under-utilize assets perform poorly as compared to the firms who utilize assets more efficiently. The inefficient asset utilization can be attributed to various factors including policy influence, lack of use of modern technology. This study found that 34% of the firms who diversified into unrelated business performed better than industry average. The author argues that the firms who are not able to best utilize assets in existing business operations should diversify into unrelated business to achieve higher asset utilization.

Fan and Lang (2000)[10] aimed to develop a methodology to measure relatedness of business segments of a diversified firm. Traditionally, relatedness of diversified business segments has been measured using Standard Industry Classification (SIC) codes. The researchers consider two businesses unrelated if they do not share 2-digit, 3-digit, or 4-digit SIC codes. The major disadvantage of using SIC code based measure is, the SIC code does not tell about the type of relatedness. The SIC codes are discrete, and hence not suitable for measuring degree of relatedness. The SIC code gives misleading information about relatedness in case of vertical integration. For example, oil refining has 2-digit SIC code 29 and chemical has 2-digit SIC code 28. According to 2-digit SIC code classification, these two businesses are unrelated.

However, an oil refiner can vertically integrate and enter into chemical business. Thus, practically, these two businesses are not unrelated.

In this paper authors developed input-output (IO) based measures to capture inter-industry and intersegment relatedness and complementarity. Two businesses are vertically integrated if output of one industry is used as input in other industry. Two businesses are complimentary to each other if they can share marketing, distribution, or make joint procurements.

This study found strong relatedness between the IO based methods and SIC based methods to measure relatedness of businesses. In spite of several limitations, the SIC based method captures complementarity better than the IO based method. The IO based methods capture vertical relatedness better than the SIC based methods. This paper further investigates the relationship between relatedness and performance. The authors argue that vertical relatedness on average has negative impact on firm value and performance. On the other hand, in 1970s and early 1980s, complementarity was positively related with performance and firm value. After 1980s, the positive relatedness between complementarity and firm value declined. The vertical relatedness deteriorates value when firm operates in large number of segments. The complementarity relatedness increases firm value when firm operates in large number of industry segments. This study shows that the vertical and complementarity relatedness, both should be studied as two types of relatedness have opposite impact on firm value and performance.

Indian economy is dominated by large business groups. Kakani (2000)[11] investigated relationship between diversification and financial performance of large Indian business groups.

The shareholder value maximization is ultimate objective of a business organization. The shareholder value is a function of four determinants: profitability, growth, risk, and capital market conditions. The financial value creation is measured as Tobin's q and PBV. The profitability is measured as CFM, ROA and ROCE. The profitability components are measured as NPM and STA. The growth is measured as Compounded annual growth in total assets (CAGR_{TA}) and Compounded annual growth in fixed assets (CAGR_{FA}). The risk is measured as Coefficient of variance in return on total assets (VROA) and Coefficient of variance in return on capital employed (VROCE).

Tobin's q = (Market value of equity + book value of preferred stock + book value of debt)/Book value of assets

PBV = market value of equity / book value of equity

CFM = (Net income + depreciation)/total assets

ROA = [Net income + interest*(1-tax rate)]/Total asset

ROCE = (net income + interest + tax)/(Net worth + long term liabilities)

NPM = Net income/ Total sales

STA = Total sales/total assets

Kakani (2000) conducted study on a sample of 240 publicly traded Indian companies between 1987 to 1999. This study found negative relationship between product diversification level and shareholder value creation. However, positive relationship between international diversification and financial performance was observed during early days of diversification only. The positive relation was not clear in longer period. This study also found that large sized group's growth was higher than that of small sized groups during same period.

Some researchers tried to find why some firms diversify in unrelated business, and when they take decision to diversify unrelated businesses, why do they fail to create a supportive organizational structure. Kock and Guillen (2001)[12] tried to answer two questions: (a) why do firms prefer to diversify in unrelated businesses, and (b) why do firms fail to create the organizational structure that can efficiently manage unrelated businesses.

Primary reason for creation of business groups is found in the selection of environment. Unrelated diversification is more prevalent and successful in late-industrialization countries where economic development is in early stages. In such countries, domestic firms are encouraged to participate in economy, and they are protected from foreign competition. In such environment, contacts used to get official or unofficial access to resources become a strength. These contact capabilities allow the domestic firms to innovate and create new markets and new sources of supply. The firms having contact capabilities tend to enter into new businesses that show no apparent relatedness in terms of product or technology. The firms entering into new unrelated businesses form business groups and manage bundle of businesses with relatively loose organizational structure. Over a period of time, contact capabilities reach a peak and then decline over time. After the locals create firms based on contacts, entrepreneurial survival comes into play. Ultimately, only effectiveness and efficiency play very crucial role in survival of firms. This study proposes a new theory of creation of business groups. Earlier theories believed that creation of business groups was a result of inefficient markets. The authors argue that foreign multinational companies can also take advantage of inefficient market unless there is protectionism. Thus, the authors propose that creation of domestic business groups is a result of both, inefficient market and protectionism.

This paper argues that differences in timing and pattern of industrialization among countries have direct influence on how firms acquire capabilities, and what organizational structure firms adopt. In spite of not adopting M-form of organizational structure, and unrelated diversification, business groups display sustainable profitability for long period of time. This paper presents a view that apparently unrelated diversifications of business groups are actually logical extension of their core capabilities, and in late economic development conditions, loose group structure adopted by the business groups are more appropriate in order to respond to the strategic contingencies. Another important argument made in this paper is, companies in late-developing countries enter in mature industries. Countries that have just started economic development do not have any technological capabilities. The entrepreneurs do not command skills or capabilities to enter in technologically superior industries. They do not have capability to innovate, ability to take high risk, or possession of intellectual property such as patents. Thus, in late-developing countries, entrepreneurs usually enter into mature industries.

The economic reform of 1991 changed the business environment and gave new direction to economic policy in India. Ahluwalia (2002)[13] studied economic indicators post economic reforms in India since 1991, and evaluated if the reform had been able to achieve its objectives, and what is needed to be done to achieve the objectives. This paper is very useful to understand the impact of economic reforms of 1991 on Indian economy and management strategies of businesses.

The economic reform of 1991 fuelled growth in India. The average growth rate from 1992-93 to 2001-02 was around 6%, one of the fastest growing economy in world. During the same period, poverty also declined. The combined fiscal deficit of central and state governments declined from 9.4% of GDP in 1990-91 to 7% in 1991-92 and 1992-93. By 1993, balance of

payment crisis was over. Public savings declined from 1.7% of GDP in 1996-97 to 0.7% of GDP in 2001 which was in line with the rise in fiscal deficit which went up to 9.6% in 2000-01 again. The author argues that these trends show that India may not achieve higher growth in future. In order to achieve higher growth, India needs to increase investment up to 29-30% of GDP and foreign direct investment of at least 5% of GDP. There is also need of reducing central government subsidies. Another suggestions made by author to fuel growth are tax reform and reform in trade policy. Government needs to make heavy investment in infrastructure development. The public sector is the only credible source of investment. India can achieve sustainable growth only if government opens up more industries, reform trade policy and reduce trade barriers, attract foreign direct investment, and reduce control on public sector enterprises through privatization.

This paper gives an insight into the impact of economic reform of 1991 on Indian economy and government policies, and trend in economic factors and government policies. This paper is also helpful in predicting the direction of government policies, and how businesses can respond to changing government policies. The economic condition and government policies affect diversification strategies of companies.

The studies conducted in late 20th century and early 21st century found that diversification destroys value. Very few studies could find contradicting results. A study conducted by Graham, Lemmon and Wolf (2002)[14] examines if diversification destroys value. A sample of firms involved in merger and acquisitions was taken for study. Study was conducted on listed firms making acquisitions of another listed firms between 1978 through 1995. The firms in financial services industry or with total sales less than \$20 million were excluded from the study. There were 356 firms in the final sample.

The excess value is defined using two step methodology. In first step, imputed value for each division of a diversified firm is calculated by multiplying each segment's sales by median market-to-sales ratio of single segment firm in the same industry in same year. In second step, excess value is calculated as the log of the ratio of the firm's actual market value to the sum of its division's imputed values. In this study, SIC code is used as measure of diversification. If two firms have no common four digit SIC codes, the acquisition is classified as unrelated. Another measure of diversification is increase in the number of reported business segments as a result of acquisition.

This study showed that mean excess value of acquiring firm declined by 7% over two year period after acquisition. The target firms have excess value of approximately 10%. This study evaluated the only those firms that increased their number of industry segments via merger and acquisition. The findings of this study cannot be generalized for the firms that entered into a new industry segment without merger or acquisition.

Park (2002)[15] investigated the reverse relationship between diversification strategy and performance. This paper investigated the effect of firm's prior performance on choice of diversification strategy.

A firm can pursue diversification through either acquisition or internal development. This paper is focused on diversification through acquisitions only. For this study, total 229 acquisitions were identified, which consisted of 121 related acquisitions and 108 unrelated acquisitions. The profitability was measured in terms of three year average return on assets (ROA) of the primary industry as defined by 3-digit SIC code.

When an industry is structurally unattractive, and has low profit, related industries are also likely to be unattractive. The firms in such industries tend to have strong incentives to improve performance by diversifying in more attractive industries, and hence pursue unrelated diversification strategy. The firms in structurally attractive industries are likely to pursue related diversification strategy as related industries are also structurally attractive. The firms in a high-profit industry develop strong resources and capabilities (such as patents, brand image, distribution network) that cannot be easily imitated. These resources and capabilities can be easily transferred to related businesses, but not to unrelated industries. Thus, the managers have strong motivation to diversify into related businesses.

Jung (2003)[16] examined the degrees of product diversification of media conglomerates and assesses the impact of product diversification on financial health of the media conglomerates. This study used sample of 26 media firms who diversified between 1996 and 2002. To measure unrelated degree of product diversification, the author has used the Herfindahl measure based on sum of the squared proportion of industry involvements relative to total number of operations. Subtracting the sum from one gives an index that represents product un-relatedness. As the value of index increases, product un-relatedness also increases.

$$\text{Degree of unrelated product diversification } D = 1 - \sum P_i^2 / (\sum P_i)^2$$

Where P_i = Proportion of number of operations in industry i to total number of operations.

The third and fourth digit of SIC code identify industry, and first two digits (first and second) of SIC code identify business in that industry.

This study proposed to use a quadratic equation to determine the relationship between the financial performance and direction of diversification.

$$\text{Financial Performance} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\text{direction of diversification}) + \beta_2 * (\text{direction of diversification})^2$$

Regression analysis was conducted to assess the impact of product diversification on financial health of the media firms. This study found U-shaped relationship between performance and diversification. When a firm shifts from concentrated business strategy to related diversification, performance measured in terms of sales and EBITDA decreases, but when firms change from related diversification to unrelated diversification, performance improves. There is inverted U-shape relationship between financial efficiency (ROS, ROA, and ROE) and diversification. This study concludes that unrelated diversification leads to decrease in financial efficiency.

The scope of this study is limited to media companies in the U.S. that diversified since the Telecommunication Act of 1996. The findings of this study may not be applicable to other industries and firms in emerging markets.

In 1960s and 1970s, there was trend of diversification. Later in 1980s to 2000s, many researches were conducted in this field, and common wisdom was, corporate diversification, especially unrelated diversification, destroys shareholder's wealth. However, recent researches suggest that diversification does not necessarily destroy shareholder's wealth. Martin and Sayrak (2003)[17] attempted to survey recent developments in the literature on corporate diversification. The recent literature has focus on two broad issues: (a) impact of diversification

on firm value, and (b) general trend in diversification. This paper has focus on domestic diversification.

The authors argue that there is general consensus among researchers that corporate diversification deteriorates firm's value as diversified firms tend to have lower Tobin's Q, share price is up to 15% lower than comparable focused firm, they are more likely to be broken up through reorganization, and stock market respond favorably to increase in corporate focus. The reasons behind poor performance of diversified firms are: (a) inefficient allocation of internal resources, and/or (b) deliberate poor allocation of resources due to agency problems. Some researchers argue that diversification discount is caused because of lower efficiency, not agency problem.

Recently, more and more researchers have started challenging the common wisdom that conglomerate diversification destroys shareholder's value. The recent studies argue that diversification discount is not because of diversification, but attributable to other factors. The most compelling argument made by these researchers is, the conglomerate firms or acquired firms are already performing poorly and trading at discount before diversification.

Some of the recent researches argue that diversified firms do not trade at discount but at significant premium. These researchers argue that previous researches have measurement errors. The sources of errors include:

- (a) Definition of business segment is flexible which allows the firms to combine two or more business segments into one.
- (b) Reported business segment data is not reliable. While at aggregate level the reported data is reliable, segment financial reporting is flawed.

(c) Some industries are actually composed of segments of diversified firms.

The researchers further argue that, the diversified firms have better access to capital market than single-segment firms, which results in diversification premium.

Rajan (2003)[18] examined corporate diversification and restructuring activities of American firms in the 1980s and 1990s. The author has broken down the measures of corporate diversification into two categories:

1. SIC-based measures
2. Typology based measures

In SIC based measures, author has used two commonly used indices:

1. Modified Berry's Herfindahl index of diversification
2. Jacquemin-Berry entropy measure of diversification

The modified Berry's Herfindahl index of diversification measures diversification as:

$$\text{Index of Diversification} = 1 - \sum P_i^2$$

Where, P_i = relative share of each SIC code's sales to total sales

The Typology based measures include: Specialization ratio, Vertical ratio, and Related ratio.

The 1980s and 1990s were era of restructuring for American firms. This study supports the general belief that corporate America responded to changing business environment in 1980s and 1990s by restructuring. Type-1 firms moved back to their core by increasing the size of their primary segment. The Type-2 firms changed their primary business segment and became

less reliant on primary segment. This study does not investigate the performance-diversification of American firms. The performance of the firms before restructuring could have been a motivation for restructuring.

Most of the studies in this field are conducted in developed countries. Some studies are conducted in emerging market, especially in China. Li (2004)[19] explored the relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance for Chinese firms. He also studied relationship between the level of diversification and corporate performance moderated by diversification factors. The diversification factors considered in this study are efficiency achieving factors, internal capital market building factors, manager wealth maximization factors, and competition advantage pursuing factors.

Li conducted this study on a sample of 270 companies chosen randomly from 1000 publicly traded companies in China. Li found U-shape relationship between diversification and corporate performance. This study revealed that generally, specialized firms performed better than diversified firms. However, this study could not conclusively established that diversification destroy firm's value. This study further investigated the motivations for diversification, and found that wealth maximization motivation of managers have negative influence on corporate performance. He found that the efficiency-achieving incentives are the only factors that contribute to positive impact of diversification on corporate performance.

Corporate performance can only be compared based on same level of risk. The Risk Adjusted Return on Capital (RAROC) is a better measure of performance than ROA and ROE. This study used ROA and ROE as measure of performance. These measures ignore influence of risk on performance. Another important limitation of this study was, this study was conducted on

randomly chosen sample of 270 companies. Many of the chosen companies could not be right candidates for study. A stratified sampling technique could produce a better sample for study. This study focused only on degree of diversification. Form of diversification also needs to be studied as form of diversification is closely related to corporate performance.

Lins and Servaes (2004)[20] examined if corporate diversification is beneficial to firms in emerging markets. In emerging markets, diversification brings benefits such as economies of scope, and access to larger internal capital market that can help the firms to overcome the inefficiencies of capital market. Major drawback of diversification is agency cost associated with inefficient resource allocation. Studies show that in developed markets, cost of diversification is higher than the benefits. But in emerging markets, because of inefficient capital market, labor market, product market, contract enforcement, and business and political environment, the relative costs and benefits may not be of same size. The firms can take advantage of the imperfections, and diversify at firm level. This study investigates 1,000 firms from 7 emerging markets in 1995.

This study found that in emerging markets, diversified firms trade at 7% discount to single segment firms. The diversified firms are also less profitable than single-segment firms. The lower profitability explains diversification discount partially only. The diversification discount is also attributed to membership of industrial groups, and management ownership concentration. The diversification discount is higher in firms that are part of industrial groups, or have management ownership concentration between 10% and 30%. Diversification discount is 15% for firms that are members of industrial groups. Reason is, industrial groups are already diversified. As a member of industrial groups, firms do not need to diversify themselves.

Shareholders view any diversification undertaken by firms who are part of industrial groups as negative.

This study was conducted on data from seven emerging markets: Hong Kong, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, South Korea, and Thailand. These emerging markets differ in terms of institutional structure, political control, and stage in economic development cycle. Singapore, South Korea and Hong Kong are far ahead on economic development cycle than India, Indonesia, Malaysia and Thailand. The findings of this study may not be true in Indian perspective as the findings may be biased because of data from economically advanced countries. In order to understand the impact of diversification in India, there is need to conduct study on sample from India only.

Many researchers established that diversification has negative impact on firm value. The diversified firms trade at discount (called diversification discount) as compared to focused firms. Villalonga (2004)[21] examined if diversification actually causes diversification discount.

This empirical study finds that diversification discount cannot be attributed to diversification itself. The diversified firms were already trading at discount before diversification was undertaken. The firms diversify based on some characteristics of origin and target industries. The diversified firms differ from focused firms on many characteristics. Comparison of performance of diversified firms with comparable focused firms where comparable firms are determined based on size and industry only is a source of bias. This paper also argues that performance of diversified firms and diversification discount also depend on pre-diversification characteristics. This study found that, mostly diversified firms were already

trading at a significant industry-adjusted discount before firms diversified into other businesses.

This paper helps to understand why diversified firms trade at a discount to single segment firms, and whether diversification itself can be attributed for diversification discount. The findings of this paper go against the common wisdom that argues that diversification deteriorates firm value.

Pelg (2006)[22] examined the effect of diversification on liquidity of the firm. Liquidity may have many dimensions such as state of liquidity, quality of readily convertibility into cash, cash position, or capacity of obtain cash on demand. This paper reviews literature in this area and explains impact of diversification on various aspects of liquidity.

Majority of studies suggest positive impact of diversification on liquidity. One reason why diversification improves liquidity is, diversification increases analyst's coverage, which leads to trading volume. But, this positive effect of liquidity is limited to liquidity of stock on exchange. This does not translate into liquidity position of the firm. The merger and acquisition improves liquidity position of the firm as firm has more liquidity from various business segments. The total liquidity of the diversified business post-merger is higher than sum of pre-merger liquidity position of individual firms. The merger and acquisitions also improves a firm's capability to obtain cash on demand because larger size of firm improves firm's capacity to raise short-term debt. However, this study does not differentiate between related and unrelated diversification. This study does not explain why for some firms liquidity falls after merger. This paper also does not explain the link between liquidity of stock and liquidity position of the firm.

Peng and Delios (2006)[23] tried to answer the question - "what determines the product and geographic scope of firm?" This study further investigates the relationship between the scope of firm and performance. In earlier era, unrelated product diversification was found to add value. In post-Rumelt (1974) era, in developed countries, unrelated product diversification was found to destroy value. But in Asia, unrelated product diversification continue to be popular and add value. The authors argue that time and location are two important dimensions to be incorporated in diversification research.

The cost and benefits of diversification can be described in terms of marginal bureaucratic costs (MBCs) and marginal economic benefits (MEBs). The MBCs are incurred as a firm has to create additional structure to manage new activities. The MEBs are created from synergy between business units. Synergy is per unit reduction in cost. Unrelated diversification may be beneficial for Asian firms as compared to American firms because Asian firms have lower MBCs than American firms. The MEBs for Asian firms are also higher because of lower cost of financial transactions and increase in availability of information to individual investors. The conglomerates are created because of institutional imperfections. In Asia-Pacific, government continues to influence resource allocation, and capital market is still imperfect. Thus, conglomerates are likely to be more successful than in developed countries.

This study provides a base for understanding Asia-Pacific markets, and why unrelated diversification may succeed in Asian markets. Further investigation in individual markets having same institutional structure may give an insight into diversification strategy adopted by firms.

Sen (2006)[24] in his Ph.D. dissertation attempted to analyze the nature of relationship between diversification and performance across business groups in India, and provide a unified theoretical framework. The author argues that "strategic fit" plays very important role in making a diversification successful. "Strategic fit" has positive effect on the relationship between diversification and performance. However, impact of "strategic fit" on overall group performance is negative. This study also examines the impact of size, industry characteristics, resources and capabilities, internal transactions, and inertia on overall group performance.

This study finds that:

- 1) Size of firm has negative effect on group performance. Smaller diversified firms perform better than larger diversified firms.
- 2) Industry characteristics has positive effect on group performance.
- 3) Resources and capabilities has positive effect on performance. A business group commanding large resources are likely to perform better.
- 4) Internal transactions have negative effect on performance. Larger the number of internal transactions, poorer the performance.
- 5) Inertia has negative effect on group performance.
- 6) Market imperfection has positive effect on group performance. Market imperfection is a major reason why conglomerates may create value for shareholders.

This study has focus on theoretical study of relationship between diversification and performance of business groups.

Laeven and Levine (2007)[25] investigated if there exists a diversification discount in financial conglomerates. The financial conglomerates are engaged in many lending and non-lending

activities, investment banking, and activities usually performed by financial intermediaries such as underwriting of securities and brokerage services. The financial conglomerates enjoy economies of scope. At the same time, engagement in multiple activities intensify agency problems. This paper conducted study on 3,415 banks-years in 43 countries. In this study, authors have considered that lending is the core activity, and interest income is the main revenue stream of banks.

This study finds that diversification reduces firm value. The financial conglomerates trade at a discount as compared to specialized financial firms. The related diversification mitigates value loss from diversification. Thus, the financial conglomerates diversifying within the financial services industry experience lower diversification discount.

The findings of this study are in line with the findings of majority of studies that conclude that diversification causes loss to firm value. But, this paper did not study the firms before diversification. The diversification discount might have been caused by factors other than diversification.

Singh, Nejadmalayeri and Mathur (2007)[26] investigated the impact of group affiliation on performance of Indian firms. In India, large business houses have been extremely successful in achieving higher scale and scope, but not always higher profitability. This paper argues that powerful business houses are able to generate higher profits through their rent-seeking activities, stifling competition, and getting access to permits and licenses. Post-liberalization, profitability of business houses declined as rent-seeking opportunities declined. In emerging markets, due to underdeveloped legal and contracting institutions, information asymmetries, poor accounting standard, absence of market based checks and balances, and inefficiencies,

firm level diversification can improve performance by lowering transaction cost. Especially in India, family dominated big business houses have been very successful because they enjoy unchecked political power and financial strength.

Study was conducted on 889 firms between 1998 and 2000 (for three years period). Based on Jacquemin and Berry entropy measure of diversification, firms were classified as (1) focused or (2) diversified. Three metrics are used to measure performance: return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and profit margin (PM). The impact of group affiliation on sources of diversification discount is measured in terms of cost inefficiencies using ratio of COGS to sales, and Asset turnover ratio. Two proxies are used to measure growth opportunities: market to book ratio of firm's equity (MB), and price-to-earnings ratio (P/E). Tangibility is measured as ratio of long-term assets to total assets.

This study found that diversified Indian firm significantly underperformed the focused firms. This study also established negative relationship between degree of diversification and performance. This result is supported by the fact that post-liberalization of 1991, market imperfections are eliminated and hence rent-seeking opportunities declined. This study further investigates the impact of group affiliation on performance. The MBC affiliation results in agency conflict driven negative impact on performance while domestic affiliation results in cost inefficiencies that deteriorate the performance of diversified firms.

In most of the studies, degree of diversification is determined based on SIC code. In India, the Central Classification Organization (CSO) assigns SIC code to business activities. The National Industrial Classification-2004 (NIC-2004) was revised in 2008 and NIC-2008 came into effect. The National Industrial Classification classified the industries in various groups and

assign Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) code to each activity. The SIC code is a 5 digit code.

The activities are grouped into several activity groups, also called "categories". In NIC-2008, activities are grouped into "Sections" and coded from Alphabet A to U. Each section is divided into 2-digit "divisions". Divisions are divided into 3-digit "group". Groups are divided into 4-digit "class". The classes are divided into 5-digit "sub-class". (CSO, 2008)[27]

The structure of SIC code is as:

Division (2 digit) --> Group (3 digit) --> Class (4 digit) --> Sub-class (5 digit)

The SIC classification is base to understand relatedness of business activities. Many researchers used SIC code to determine degree of diversification. Most popular measures of degree of diversification are based on SIC code.

Globalization has changed business dynamics and competitive conditions firms face. Wiersena and Bowen (2008)[28] developed a theoretical framework to understand how globalization, foreign competition, and product diversification influences international diversification decisions. In this study, researchers have focused on firm specific factors rather than global economic factors.

This study shows that firms whose core business industry has more market openness and higher degree of global market linkage are more likely to diversify internationally. Another important finding of this research is, firms facing more foreign competition are more likely to adopt international diversification. Product diversification has negative relation with degree and

scope of international diversification. Higher degree of product diversification limits a firm's ability to increase its international diversification. Firms trade-off between product diversification and geographical diversification. Pursuing both product diversification and geographical diversification leads to subpar performance as firms which are highly product diversified may not pay adequate managerial attention to international diversification. This finding is very important to understand which firms may not prefer high degree of product diversification. The firms which are highly internally diversified may have limited managerial attention to product diversification. In Indian perspective, there is need to analyze if the firms aggressively pursuing international diversification also pursue product diversification.

Klein and Lien (2009)[29] tried to find out why firms diversify. This study uses transaction cost approach to related and unrelated diversification. A diversification is called related if resources in one industry are substitutes for complement to resources in other industry. The potential sources of efficiency gain are resource substitutability and resource complementarity. Resource complementarity exists when investment in one industry leads to increase in value of resources in another industry. The diversified firm can exploit benefits of resource substitutability or complementarity only if transaction cost prevents specialized firms from realizing these benefits through contracts. This argument does not apply to unrelated diversification. This study also examines the consequences of diversification for industry structure.

This study finds that there is strong correlation between concentration level and related industries. A concentrated neighbour industry is good and a fragmented neighbour industry is bad to the focal industry. Any technological and other advancements that concentrate (or fragment) a neighbouring industry is also likely to concentrate (or fragment) the focal industry.

This study is important for two reasons: (1) Unlike other researches that focus on impact of industry structure on diversification, this study focuses on impact of diversification on industry structure. This study shows that some industries are susceptible to diversification while some industries are not. (2) Diversification, merger and acquisition, divestment, and decisions taken by firms in one industry that change concentration in that industry influences diversification decisions in neighbouring industries. Thus, study of diversification should also investigate neighbouring industries.

Guruswamy (2009)[30] in his book “Financial Services”, discusses Indian scenario of merger and acquisition, and legal and regulatory framework of merger and acquisition in India. During the licensing era, firms adopted unrelated diversification strategy depending on the ability to get licenses. In spite of inefficiencies, these firms prospered as licenses restricted total capacity of the industry. But after the economic reform of 1991, firms were exposed to severe domestic and global competition. The recessionary trend further accentuated the problem for unrelated diversified firms as demand fell which resulted in overcapacity. Changing economic and regulatory environment forced the firms to consolidate themselves and focus on core business. As a part of restructuring, firms started divesting the businesses where they have no competitive advantage. The mergers and acquisitions have attempted to restructure the firms so that firms can focus on core business where they have competitive advantage, and achieve economies of scale.

The objective of laws and regulations controlling M&A is to mitigate the dangerous effects of M&A. These laws and regulations ensure that M&A does not stifle competition and encourage monopoly. There are a host of regulations and guidelines in India that govern M&A include

MRTTP Act 1969, Income tax Act 1961, Companies Act 1956, Security Contracts Act 1956, Sick Companies (Special Provisions) Act 1985, SEBI Act 1992, and Listing Agreement of the Stock Exchanges. These Acts and government policies form a legal and regulatory framework that dictate M&A activities.

This information on legal and regulatory framework is useful for firms diversifying through merger and acquisition. The diversification strategy of a firm is also influenced by legal and regulatory environment. Another important point to note is, when firms divest non-core businesses, it opens up opportunities for other firms to enter into unrelated businesses.

Some studies in this field were conducted outside developed markets and Asian emerging markets. Njuguna (2009)[31] studied the effects of diversification on growth of listed firms in Nairobi. The focus on this paper is to investigate the relationship between diversification and growth. This study used regression analysis to find relationship between the divarication factors and growth.

The author argues that a firm's growth is also affected by factors other than diversification. This paper found positive relationship between size of firms and growth. The profitable firms are more motivated to grow as they have financial strength and ability to generate profit to sustain growth. The size of firms is directly correlated with net income. Hence, firms with higher income grow faster. The regional expansion has positive effect on growth. Liquidity has negative relationship with growth.

This study shows that there are factors driving diversification strategies that affect growth of the firm. So, study of relationship between diversification and firm's growth should also consider other factors that affect growth of firm.

The degree of product diversification, and direction of diversification influence financial behavior of firms. Choice of related or unrelated diversification (direction of diversification) has opposite effect on capital structure. A firm finances related and unrelated diversification differently. The related diversification is associated with lower debt usage. It means, related diversification has negative influence on leverage. On the other hand, unrelated diversification is associated with higher debt usage, and hence related diversification has positive effect on leverage (Rocca, 2009).

Rocca, Rocca, Gerace, and Smark (2009)[32] also explains high usage of debt to finance unrelated diversification through coinsurance effect and the transaction cost theory. The coinsurance effect explains that diversified firms reduce operating risk because of imperfect correlation between different cash flows. The unrelated diversified firms have more capability to raise debt. In unrelated diversified firms, different cash flows are less related than in related diversified firms. The unrelated diversified firms possess more general purpose assets which can be kept as collateral to raise debt. So, unrelated diversified firms prefer debt as a financing tool. The capital structure decisions of unrelated diversification firms aim to achieve optimal capital structure. On the other hand, related diversified firms have less capability to raise debt, and hence they tend to adjust slowly towards optimal capital structure. This study is useful in understanding the relationship between direction of diversification and the financing tool a firm uses.

A thesis by Tangtrakulporn and Messap-lak (2010)[33] examines whether corporate governance mitigates agency cost and alleviate value-destroying diversification strategies in East Asia. This thesis conducts case studies from Thailand to understand how corporate governance influences agency costs. This study finds the correlation between value of diversified firms and range of corporate governance indications. Study was conducted on 19 diversified firms in Thailand.

The authors argue that agency cost may deprive the firm from getting benefits of corporate diversification. because of different institutional context and ownership structure, agency cost in East Asia is different from the agency cost in the U.S. Corporate governance can significantly lower the negative effects of agency problems. The author argues that different corporate governance models are suitable at different locations and in different contexts. So, corporate governance models designed for developed countries may not be successful in East Asian countries.

This study finds that agency cost of free cash flow is one of the main reason behind value loss from diversification. Agency conflicts drive firms to pursue diversification strategies which has potential of capital misuse. Corporate governance can reduce diversification discount and minimize the value loss due to diversification by safeguarding the firm against agency conflicts. The concentric ownership, managerial ownership, and board of directors are some corporate governance mechanisms designed for developed countries. These mechanisms cannot be effective in East Asian countries as these countries have predominant family-based ownership structure. A corporate governance mechanism that reduces agency problems between controlling and minority shareholders can reduce agency costs in East Asian countries.

Lin (2011)[34] studied 58 companies listed on Shanghai and Shenzhen Stock Exchanges for five successive years between 2003 and 2008. This study discusses internal and external motivations of diversification. Internal motivations of diversification are: economies of scale, effect of internal resources allocation, and effect of risk distribution. External incentives for diversification are: effect of principal-agent, acquiring core competencies, risk mitigation. Internationally accepted method of measuring diversification is using Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) code. In this study, degree of overall diversification is calculated as:

$$\text{The degree of overall diversification } DT = \sum_{i=1}^N P_i * \ln(1/P_i)$$

Where:

P_i = Proportion of the sales of i^{th} segment of company to total sales

N = No. of total segment in business

The same segment should have same four SIC code.

The company's economic performance (Y) is a function of ROE, EPS, and Tobin's Q . The relationship between diversified operation and profitability can be determined by a multi-regression model as follows:

$$Y = b + b_1 * DT + b_2 * \text{Asset}$$

This study found that there was strong negative correlation between the degree of diversification and business performance of companies in China. This study was conducted in China, and hence represents emerging markets. But, market structure of India is different from

the market structure of China. The findings of this result may not hold true in Indian perspective.

Kotwal, Ramasami and Wadhwa (2011)[35] surveyed the literature and investigated how economic liberalization in India influenced economic growth. By the end of 1970s, India was one of the most protected and regulated economies. In 1980s, some tentative steps were taken to liberalize the economy. In 1991, extensive reforms took place. Post 1991, more policy changes in various sectors were implemented and economy was opened up to more private participation. Growth in post-reform era has been higher than pre-reform era. India has been able to achieve stable growth. With economic growth, poverty also declined.

This study found certain distinct aspects about India's economic growth. The Indian economic growth was supported by access to new technologies and skilled manpower, which could be possible only because government opened up the economy. Indian growth experience was dominated by service sector. Manufacturing sector uses unskilled manpower while service sector uses skilled manpower. So, economic growth of India could bring down unemployment of skilled manpower only. The economic growth of India was not accompanied by a fast improvement in the legal system of functioning of institutions. In spite of fast economic growth, institutional structure did not change. So, firms in India remained motivated to diversify into unrelated businesses and achieve higher growth. Even after reforms, conglomerates continue to dominate Indian economy. Another important take away of this study is, economic growth was dominated by service sector. The manufacturing sector did not experience very high growth. This could have been a motivation for manufacturing firms to diversify into service industries.

Picone (2011)[36] studied the major variables that play significant role in creating or destroying value in conglomerate diversification strategy. Study was conducted on American conglomerates. This paper studies the relationship between breadth of business portfolio and performance of the conglomerate.

Picone (2011) found that the breadth of business portfolio has no correlation with corporate performance. This study found that when the amount of diversification is low, the firm's coherence is not linked with corporate performance, but when the amount of diversification is large, the firm's coherence is positively linked with corporate performance. This study also reveals that related diversification is preferred to unrelated diversification.

Conglomerate diversification strategy may fail because of managerial complexity. Executives may not be able to manage complex conglomerate firms. Misallocation of resources is another factor which may lead to failure of diversification strategy. There is negative relationship between unrelated diversification and innovation.

Tong (2011)[37] analyzed the effect of firm diversification on corporate cash holding. Corporate cash holding is positively correlated with firm value. The diversification has direct impact on magnitude of corporate cash holding, and through this diversification can indirectly affect the firm value.

This paper also summarizes the criteria of financial constraint: firm size, pay out, and credit rating. Large firms have better access to capital market, hence they face fewer constraints in raising external capital to finance diversification than smaller firms. The firms having higher pay outs are likely to possess sufficient internal resources to finance diversification. Firms

having higher credit rating have better access to public debt market as compared to firms having poor credit rating. These three criteria influence the diversification decision, and use of financing tools.

This study finds that diversification reduces value of cash in firms. The deterioration of value of cash is more for diversified with more constraints than the diversified firms with less constraints. The author argues that post-diversification reduction in the value of corporate cash holding is through agency problem.

Findings of this study imply that diversification has negative impact on firm value. However, this study does not differentiate between related and unrelated diversification.

Guo and Cao (2012)[38] examined the relationship between the degree of diversification and firm's performance. The gains from diversification arises from economies of scale, efficient allocation of resources in internal capital market, and exploitation of existing resources in other industries. The costs of diversification arises from agency problem, inefficient allocation of resources in internal capital market, and inability to motivate divisional managers.

The authors argue that a firm diversifies as a response to two interacting factors: (a) agency problem, and (b) economies of scale. Whether a diversification creates value or deteriorates value depends on how these two factors interact. This study found that diversification premium decreases if a firm engages in more than three business segments. This is very important finding which suggests that diversification can create value if a firm operates in 2-3 industries. As

degree of diversification increases, after a point, each new business segment added to the portfolio adds less value than previously added business segment.

Arikan and Stulz (2014)[39] studied role of corporate acquisition and diversification during a firm's life cycle. Firm's acquisition rate changes as the firm progresses on life cycle. This paper studied 6,548 public firms that came out with IPO from 1975 and 2002 and investigated their acquisition behavior through their lifecycle.

This paper finds that the acquisition rate is higher when firm is young (first three years from IPO date). During middle age, (4-10 years from IPO date), acquisition rate falls. Again, during maturity phase (10-20 years from IPO), acquisition rate goes up. Thus, acquisition rate of IPO cohorts follow a U-shape. Another important finding of this paper was the difference in the nature of acquisition of young firms and mature firms. While young firms acquire more private firms, mature firms acquire more public firms. The authors argue that high acquisition rate during young age and maturity age cannot be attributed to the general belief that firms run out of internal growth opportunities that force them to acquire other firms. If this theory were true, market would have reacted adversely to acquisition by young firms. This paper does not explain why acquisition rate of IPO cohort is U-shaped. One important observation made by this study is, market react adversely to acquisition of related public firms for equity.

This paper is helpful in understanding the acquisition and corporate diversification behavior of firms at different stages of life cycle. While young and mature firms tend to make more acquisitions, this phenomena is less visible among middle aged firms.

Manrai, Rameshwar and Nangia (2014)[40] investigated how diversification influences financial performance and capital structure of Indian firms, and in turn how capital structure influences systematic risk of the firms. In this paper, the authors test: (1) effect of corporate size on capital structure, (2) effect of capital structure on systematic risk, (3) effect of corporate profitability on systematic risk, (4) effect of corporate size on corporate systematic risk, (5) relationship between growth opportunities and corporate performance, and (6) relationship between corporate size and corporate performance. Finally, this paper formulates a mathematical model to express capital structure in as a function of diversification index, profitability, growth, and size. This paper studies a sample of 44 companies listed on National Stock Exchange (NSE) who diversified between 2006 and 2011.

General wisdom is, there is positive relationship between capital structure and leverage in systematic risk. But, this paper could not find any relationship between leverage in capital structure and systematic risk. There is weak relationship between systematic risk and corporate profitability, and systematic risk and corporate size. This paper found strong negative relationship between corporate growth and systematic risk. The authors argue that diversification reduces operating risk, but not systematic risk as diversification increases financial leverage which increases systematic risk and hence nullify the positive impact of diversification on systematic risk. Increase in financial leverage has positive effect on profitability and corporate size (measured in terms of assets).

This study presents interrelationship among various financial variables. Diversification has positive impact on certain financial variables and negative impact on certain other variables.

The net effect on systematic risk and corporate performance depends on the quantum of effect of diversification on the factors that influence systematic risk and performance.

Boschma and Capone (2015)[41] investigated the impact of institutions on the direction of diversification process. Institutions play very important role in solving complex coordination problems between firms and other economic actors in product market, labor market, and financial market. According to the varieties of capitalism approach, a firm needs to establish positive relations with other economic actors and solve coordination problems in industrial relations, corporate governance, product market, labor market, and financial market. A firm can either use market coordination mode, which is based on competitive and fluid market, or strategic coordination mode, which is based on network coordination. The institutions, because of its important role in coordination among economic actors, have significant impact on the diversification decisions made by firms.

This paper examines the diversification process in 23 developing countries based on available product trade data of the period of 1995-2019. This study demonstrates strong relationship between institutions and direction of diversification in developed countries. The countries with institutions associated with Coordinated Market Economies (CMEs) adopt related diversification while the countries with institutions associated with Liberal Market Economies (LMEs) usually diversify into unrelated products. This study did not consider presence of sectorial institutions. In some cases, sectorial institutions may have stronger influence than national institutions. Similarly, this study did not consider regional institutions. The regional institutions may have different structure than national institutions, and regional institutions may

have greater impact than national institutions on the direction of diversification chosen by firms.

Gaur and Delio (2015)[42] investigated the role of ownership structure on international diversification in emerging economies. This study was conducted on a sample of over 5,000 publicly traded Indian companies for a period of 1995 to 2005. This paper further investigates the relationship between degree of international diversification and performance of the firms in emerging economies. The emerging markets such as China and India, are late entrants to the international marketplace. After 2000, they expanded into international markets aggressively. The emerging markets differ from developed markets in terms of resource configurations, internal governance standards, and institutional environment. The preferences and motivations of the managers and owners in emerging markets are influenced by these factors. Unlike developed markets, the emerging markets have weak institutional environments, and weak external governance structures, which lead to predominance of business groups. Weak external governance also results in agency problems for business groups. Such challenges have impact on internationalization choice.

This study demonstrates that in emerging economies, higher degree of domestic or foreign ownership leads to higher level of international diversification. This study also finds that there is negative relationship between degree of international diversification and firm's performance. This relationship can be positively moderated by ownership concentration and group affiliation. This study argues that higher concentration of foreign ownership has more positive effect on performance as compared to higher concentration of domestic ownership.

This paper studies impact of ownership structure and group affiliation on international diversification. But, the factors influencing internationalization decisions, and performance of internationally diversified firms are valid for product diversification also.

Berg (2016)[43] investigated impact of diversification and financial crisis on publicly listed Indian firms between 2006 and 2012, and explained the factors that influence diversification decisions of Indian firms. The author conducted this study on a sample of 1,061 publicly listed firms in India. Financial data was gathered for a period of seven years, from 2006 to 2012. This period included the period of financial crisis of 2008-09, and post-crisis recovery period. The performance of firms are measured using two variables: ROA and Tobin's Q.

The author reasons that in absence of well-developed and integrated capital markets, and lack of effective intermediary institutions, use of internal capital market generates more efficiency. This contributes to better performance of diversified firms over non-diversified firms. During crisis, a firm has limited ability to raise capital from external sources. A conglomerate is more able to finance its activities than related diversified firms who face higher financial constraints. So, during crisis, a conglomerate is likely to generate greater value (or less value deterioration) than related diversified firms. This study finds that diversified firms perform better than non-diversified firms. However, there is no evidence to show that diversified firms performed better than non-diversified firms during financial crisis. This study suggests that during crisis, both diversified and non-diversified firms perform poorly, but a non-related diversified firm is more likely to recover faster. Post-crisis period witnesses more firms diversifying into unrelated businesses. This paper does not explain the phenomena of increase in unrelated diversification post-crisis.

Bhatia and Thakur (2016)[44] studied extent of diversification on Indian firm. This study was conducted on a sample of 536 Indian firms listed on BSE using Jacquemin-Berry Entropy-Index measure. The study period was 2001 to 2011. This period includes dot com bubble burst of 2002 and global recession of 2008-09. The period of study begins after 10 years of liberalization reforms so that impact of liberalization does not influence the result. This study is one of the very few studies conducted in India that studies the nature, extent, and pattern of diversification during the global recession of 2008-09. The authors conducted study only on manufacturing companies, and service sector was excluded from study because performance of firms that produce tangible products cannot be compared with the performance of the firms that produce intangible services.

The Jacquemin-Berry Entropy-Index measure is based on following three elements:

- (a) Number of product segments a firm operates in,
- (b) Distribution of firm's total sales across product segments, and
- (c) Degree of relatedness among product segments.

The SIC code was used to determine relatedness of product segments. The product segments having same 2 digit industry group are treated as related product segments. The products from different 2 digit industry groups in SIC codes are considered as unrelated product segments.

The authors list a number of benefits of diversification for Indian firms including:

1. Diversification reduces impact of business cycle on performance and improves profitability.

2. Diversification strategy helps to mitigate risk.
3. Diversification achieves synergy.
4. Firms use diversification strategy to seek growth and capture value added opportunities.
5. Diversification strategy allows the firms to get more control over supply and distribution channels.
6. Diversification prevents competitors from gaining ground.

This study suggests that diversification is the best tool available to firms in the maturity phase of product life cycle. In maturity phase, firm stops to grow, and sales start to decline. Diversification provides an opportunity to revive the firm. Unrelated diversification helps poor performing firms to survive and improve performance.

This study find that related diversification is the most favored diversification strategy for Indian firms. The pattern of diversification suggests that Indian firms favor both forward and backward integration.

Castaldi, Milakovic and Sechhi (2016)[45] explored relationship between firm size and diversification level in Italian manufacturing firms. This study finds that there is direct relationship between firm size and degree of diversification. Large firms are more diversified than smaller firms, but elasticity of diversification has no relationship with firm size. In Italy, manufacturing firms are able to pass on 33% of their growth into diversification activities. Another important finding of this study is, level of risk is independent of degree of

diversification. More diversified firms are as risky as less diversified firms. The authors argue that entry of a firm into a new business is not completely independent of existing business activities. A firm undertakes diversification in line with previously acquired competences. This argument can be explained by resource-based theory and capability-based theory of diversification.

The scope of this study was limited to manufacturing firms in Italy. The manufacturing industry is in maturity stage or decline stage. The findings of this study may not be true for industries which are in early stage of their lifecycle. Another limitation of this study is, findings of this study may not be true in other countries which differ in institutional structure, and political and business environment. However, findings of this study give a new perspective to the motivation of diversification. If the findings of this study are true, firms should not diversify to mitigate risk.

Furrer (2016)[46] in his book “Corporate Level Strategy: Theory and Applications”, discussed various measures of relatedness based on product market attributes and resource allocation. This book summarizes the findings and works of previous researches on measurement of relatedness. The most categorical measures of relatedness are based on product market and technology attributes. Earlier studies were conducted by Wrigley (1970) and Rumelt (1974). Both studies use two broad dimensions to measure diversification: specialization ratio, and related ratio. Specialization ratio (SR) is a firm's revenue in major business activities as a proportion to total revenue. A well diversified business has lower SR value. For a single business, SR value is greater than 95%.

The Rumelt's classification is strongly correlated with SIC based measures of relatedness. The SIC based measures are based on the assumption that the businesses having same 2 digit SIC code share similar production and technology attributes, and hence they are related. The Narrow Spectrum Diversification (NSD) is diversification in other than vertical integration. The NSD is diversification outside four digit industry SIC code but within 2 digit group. The NSD is closely related diversification. The Broad Spectrum Diversification (BSD) is diversification into different two digit SIC code. The BSD is less closely related diversification than NSD.

The Jacquemin-Berry developed entropy measure of diversification was also based on SIC method as relatedness of business segments are determined based on SIC code. Another important SIC based method of measurement of diversification is Herfindhal index.

The product attribute based measurements of diversification are more widely used methods. The product attribute based measures are based on SIC code. In spite of some limitations, the SIC code based measures offer more reliable and robust measurement of degree of diversification.

2.3 Relevance of Study

In 1960s and early 1970s, diversification was a very popular corporate strategy to achieve growth. In late 1980s, researchers started questioning wisdom of diversification. The studies found that diversified firms trade at significant discount than single-segment firms. Many studies also questioned the general belief that diversification reduces risk.

The literatures identify that excess resources and agency problem are two major reasons why firms diversify into businesses that destroy value. The direction of diversification is also influenced by type of excess resources, capital structure, industry and institutional structure, the stage in life cycle of the firm. The literatures also provide information on how diversification affect performance, capital structure, liquidity position, profitability and risk.

A firm uses physical and intangible resources to diversify into closely related businesses, while excess internal financial resources are more related to conglomerate diversification. The related diversification creates synergy and hence found more value creating strategy than unrelated diversification. Still, firms diversify into unrelated businesses because they can get access to internal capital market. Unrelated diversification also improves the ability of a firm to raise capital as they possess more general assets that can be kept collateral. As a result, equity is major source of financing of related diversification, and unrelated diversification is mainly financed by debt.

Majority of earlier studies created a notion that diversification destroys firm value. These studies found that diversified firms traded at a discount to the focused firms. These studies further established that unrelated diversification was more value destroying strategy than related diversification. The undiversified firms give higher return with higher variation. Firms may diversify to improve risk-return balance.

Some recent studies argue that diversification discount is not caused by diversification itself. The poor performance of diversified firms is because of inefficient allocation of internal

resources and deliberate poor allocation of internal resources. The poor performance of diversified firms prior to diversification also contribute to diversification discount. These researches argue that diversified firms perform poorly because of lower inefficiency and industry structure. Some researches argue that diversified firms actually trade at premium. The result of previous researches that showed diversified firms trade at discount were due to measurement errors. The sources of measurement errors include: flexible definition of business segment, and unreliable reported business segment data. Another limitation of previous studies was, they compared diversified and undiversified firms without risk adjustment. The performance can be compared based on same level of risk only.

The institutional structure (capital market, labour market, product market, government regulation, and contract enforcement) of emerging markets are different from those of developed markets. In emerging markets like India, large businesses are still held by business houses or block shareholders. The capital market is not very efficient. Perfect information is not available in public domain. Firms can take advantage of privileged information. Government regulations are not as effective as in developed countries. Contract enforcement is not effective. These factors make emerging market different from developed markets. In emerging markets, conglomerate diversification can still create value. Lately, many researchers have found that diversification does not destroy value. They argue that diversification discount is not caused by diversification but the firm was already performing poorly and trading at discount before diversification. Some researches clearly shown that diversification did not reduce shareholders wealth in some countries including developed countries like Germany.

Majority of researches in this area are conducted in developed countries. Few researches conducted in emerging markets found contradictory results. While there is consensus among researchers that institutional structure of emerging markets is different from developed markets, and the findings of developed markets may not be applicable to emerging markets, there is no consensus on how diversification affects corporate performance in emerging markets.

In India, post-independence large firms diversified into new businesses and that is how large business houses were created. The licensing policy adopted by government further encouraged diversification. Before the economic reforms of 1991, Indian companies entered into any business they could manage license. Because of licenses, there was cap on production. So, firms did not focus on improving competitiveness and creating competitive advantage. But post liberalization, licenses were abolished and Indian firms were exposed to domestic and foreign competition. Like other markets, Indian firms also needed to focus on improving efficiencies and building competitiveness.

India has unique institutional structure. The business houses and conglomerates dominate Indian market. In India, firms may tend to diversify in unrelated businesses to get access to large internal capital market, take advantage of contact capabilities, and excess resource allocation. The marginal bureaucratic costs (MBCs) of firms in India are lower than the MBCs in developed countries, and marginal economic benefits (MEBs) are higher than those of the developed countries. This creates opportunities for conglomerates. The ownership structure also influences direction of diversification strategy. India is one of the few countries which had mixed economy and adopted economic liberalization late. Even after liberalization, the

industrial policies of India continue to have socialist inclination. Public sector enterprises are dominant players in all major industries. In post-1991 era, firms needed to focus on their core area of business and create competitive advantage. However, Indian firms continued to diversify in unrelated business. There is need to study the impact of diversification in performance in Indian market specifically.

2.4. Research Gap

In India, very few researches are conducted in this area. Many earlier researches were focused on determining what drives diversification strategy in India. Some researches that studied impact of diversification on performance, did not differentiate between related and unrelated diversification. The impact of unrelated diversification on corporate performance is not same as the impact of related diversification. This research further extends the scope of the study by analysing the impact of unrelated diversification on four aspects of financial performance: liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and capital structure. The previous researches did not study the effect of diversification on different industries. Either they used randomly drawn data, or studied one particular firm or industry. This research studies top five firms from top five industries in terms of revenue who diversified into unrelated business between 2001 and 2010. This window is chosen to ensure that effect of economic reforms of 1991 has been faded after 10 years. Between 2000 and 2010, Indian economy witnessed two major recessions. So, this time window includes the time when economy was growing fast as well as when economy was going through recessionary phase.

Earlier researches did not identify the relationship between degree of product diversification and corporate performance. It is widely accepted in developed economies and there exists negative relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. Institutional structure of India is very different from those of developed markets, and some East Asian markets where similar researches are conducted. The present study attempts to identify the relationship between degrees of diversification on corporate performance in Indian market. Further, this study investigates the impact of unrelated product diversification on financial performance in terms of liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and solvency risk. This study also investigates the impact of size of diversified firms on corporate performance.

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CHAPTER-3

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK, HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research study is designed to explain unrelated diversification and its impact on corporate performance in Indian market. This study answers related research questions: is there positive or negative relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance? How diversification can be measured? How corporate performance can be measured? What are the factors contributing to the nature of relationship? What is the impact of unrelated diversification on financial performance? How do size and industry structure affect performance of diversified firms?

Relevant variables are identified to measure degree of diversification, corporate performance, size of firm, and various aspects of financial performance. This study investigates the relationship between unrelated diversification and post diversification corporate performance; and unrelated diversification and post diversification various aspects of financial performance of the firm as compared to the base year, which is the year of diversification.

3.1 Relationship between Degree of Diversification and Corporate Performance

The first part of this paper investigates the relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. For this purpose, dependent and independent variables are as follows:

Table 3.1 List of Variables

Type of Variable	Variables
Dependent variables	Corporate Performance
Independent variable	Diversification
Control variables	Size of firm, industry effects

There are two control variables in this study: size of firm and industry effects. By choosing equal number of firms from many industries, impact of industry effects can be minimized. To minimize the impact of size on study, only large firms from each industry are selected for study.

Majority of studies found negative relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. However, most of the studies are conducted in developed countries. Some researchers argue that institutional structure of emerging markets differ from those of developed countries. In emerging markets, firms can take advantage of underdeveloped capital market and information asymmetry to create value through conglomerate diversification. Indian market, a rapidly growing emerging market, is dominated by conglomerates and business houses. In order to find the relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance, measure of degree of diversification and corporate performance are identified.

3.2 Measurement of Degree of Unrelated Product Diversification

Measurement of diversification has always been a challenge for researchers. Successive measurements of level of diversification are based on Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) codes.

The Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) code distinguishes between related and unrelated diversification. The SIC based indices of diversification rely on level of aggregation of industrial classification. There are some drawbacks of SIC based measure of diversification. The SIC based measures ignore differences in marketing and distribution channels between two industries. Another drawback of this approach is, SIC based measure of diversification considers only the potential relatedness based on industries. The actual relatedness requires additional information beyond SIC code. (Cantwell, Gambardell, & Granstrand, 2004) [1] In spite of some drawbacks, the SIC based measure of diversification has found wide acceptance. The advantage of SIC based measure of diversification is, availability of national industry classification data published by the government. The 2 digit (Division), 3 digit (Group), 4 digit (Class), and 5 digit (Subclass) SIC can be used to measure the degree of diversification. (CSO, 2008) [2]

The SIC codes are easy to use, but fail to account for the proportionality of various businesses a firm is operating in. Thus, use of SIC code does not give right picture of degree of diversification. Another limitation of use of SIC code is, it does not consider cognitive relatedness among businesses of a firm. Usually, SIC code exaggerates the extent of diversification. (Rajan, 2003) [3]

Most of the researchers used SIC code based measures to measure degree of diversification.

The most popular measurements of degree of diversification using SIC code are Herfindahl index and Entropy.

The Herfindahl index is a powerful measure of degree of diversification which measures the breadth of diversification. (Montgomery, 1985) [4] The Herfindahl index is calculated as follows:

$$H = \sum S_i^2$$

Where,

n = No. of unrelated segments in the company

S_i = Proportion of sales of business segment i to the total sales of company

i is measured by third and fourth number of SIC code. (Lin, 2011) [5]

The value of HHI is between 0 and 1. Lower value of HHI indicates higher degree of diversification. The value of HHI calculated as above is multiplied by 10,000 so that value of HHI lies between 0 and 10,000.

Other popular measurement is Jacquemin-Berry entropy measure of diversification.

(Jacquemin & Berry, 1979) [6]

The degree of diversification $DT = DR + DU$

Where,

DT = Degree of total diversification

DR = Degree of related diversification

DU = Degree of unrelated diversification

$$DT = \sum P_i \ln(1/P_i)$$

Where,

P_i = Proportion of sales in business segment i to the total sales of the company

The value of i determines the relatedness of diversification. To determine degree of diversification into unrelated business, i should be third and fourth number of SIC code.

Another important factor to consider in study of diversification is direction of diversification. Direction of diversification refers to the breadth of diversification. Varadarajan and Ramanujan (1987) [7] developed a framework to measure diversification movements of firms. Varadarajan (1986) [8] used two measures to describe the direction of diversification: Narrow Spectrum Diversification (NSD) and Broad Spectrum Diversification (BSD). The Narrow Spectrum Diversification is the diversification into new business in current industry. NSD is defined within the two digit SIC grouping. The BSD is the diversification outside the existing industry i.e. unrelated product diversification. BSD is defined as diversification into a different two digit SIC industry. A firm can achieve higher degree of diversification by choosing broad spectrum diversification.

In Indian perspective, use of Herfindahl index and Entropy may lead to measurement errors.

The sources of errors include:

(a) Definition of business segment is flexible. Firms combine more than one business segments into one. There is no uniformity in defining business segments by firms.

(b) Reported business segment data is not reliable. Firms either do not report segment-wise data, or segment financial reporting is flawed.

(c) Some industries are actually composed of many segments of diversified firms.

(Martin & Sayrak, 2003) [9]

It is difficult to find product-wise reliable and consistent sales data from secondary sources of information. Different firms provide product segment revenue in different ways. In some cases, firms treat a business as internal and do not disclose data to outside world. For example, iron and steel manufacturer SAIL does not disclose sales revenue of captive mines as they do not treat captive mines as a separate business segment as per ‘Accounting Standard 17- Segment Reporting’. As a result, using a measure that requires business segment-wise revenue is problematic.

This study has adopted Herfindahl based calculation as used by Jung (2003) [10] in measuring direction of diversification. This measure is based on Berry’s Modified Herfindahl Index and in line with the BSD developed by Varadarajan and Ramanujan (1987) [11] to measure diversification movements of firms.

Degree of unrelated product diversification $D = 1 - \sum P_i^2 / (\sum P_i)^2$

Where P_i = Proportion of number of operations in industry i to total number of operations.

The third, fourth and fifth digits (i.e. three digits from left) of SIC code identify groups, and first two digits (first and second) of SIC code identify class and subclass in that group. In this study, each group is treated as a distinct industry, and classes and subclasses in a particular

group are related businesses. Industrial activity codes a company is engaged in are declared in the annual report of the company, and press releases. For this study, the annual report of FY 2013-14 is used to identify the sectors companies are engaged in.

Following example explains the use of Herfindahl calculation to measure the direction of diversification:

Let there are two companies X and Y. Company X operates in four businesses with SIC codes: 23512, 23522, 25515 and 25516. It means, company X operates in two unrelated businesses as identified by first two digits of SIC (235 and 255). In each industry, company X has operation in two businesses (in Industry 35 two businesses are 12 and 22. In industry 55 two business are 15 and 16).

Total number of operations = 4

No. of operations in industry 35 is 2.

No. of operations in industry 55 is 2.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Degree of diversification} &= 1 - (2^2 + 2^2)/4^2 \\ &= 1 - (4+4)/16 = 1 - 8/16 = 1 - 0.5 = 0.5 \end{aligned}$$

Based on Herfindahl calculation, company X has degree of unrelated product diversification value of 0.50.

The company Y operates in four businesses: 21711, 22722, 23733 and 24744. Here, firm operates in four different unrelated industries, and in each industry firm has operation in one business.

Total number of operations = 4

No. of operations in industry 17 is 1

No. of operations in industry 27 is 1

No. of operations in industry 37 is 1

No. of operations in industry 47 is 1

$$\text{Degree of diversification} = 1 - (1^2 + 1^2 + 1^2 + 1^2) / 4^2$$

$$= 1 - 4/16 = 1 - 0.25 = 0.75$$

Based on the Herfindahl calculation, the degree of unrelated product diversification of company Y is 0.75. Thus, higher value of Herfindahl calculation of company Y indicates that company Y has higher degree of diversification than company X.

Advantage of using Herfindahl based calculation is, it does not depend on segment-wise data reported by firms. The Herfindahl calculation only uses the SIC codes of the industries a firm operates in, and based on SIC code it calculates degree of diversification. The main limitation of this method is, it does not give different weightage to different segments based on proportion of sales revenue contributed by the segments. All segments are given equal weightage, which ignores the fact that a firm may be more focused on one or more segments. In spite of this limitation, Herfindahl calculation based measure is appropriate to measure degree of diversification as this measurement is not influenced by flawed segment-wise reporting.

3.3 Measurement of corporate performance

Three most important measures of corporate performance in empirical studies are Return on Sales (ROS), Return on Assets (ROA), and Return on Equity (ROE). (Li, 2007) [12] Each of the three measures have advantages and disadvantages. Geringer et al (1989) [13] argued that

sales measure of performance can bias the result. The return on sales is influenced by accounting bias. Another problem with ROS is, a firm may report higher sales because of one time sales generated from sale of assets. Only sustainable revenue is the revenue from operation.

Another measure of corporate performance is Return on Equity (ROE). Return on equity depends on the choice of capital structure. If two firms are not having similar percentage of debt and equity in capital structure, their ROE are not comparable. For this reason, ROE is not a suitable measure of corporate performance to compare firms with dissimilar capital structure.

On the other hand, ROA keeps the decision variables under the control of management. (Hoskisson et al, 1993) [14] A firm uses funds to create assets. All funds raised through debt or equity are used to create assets. So, return on assets is a better measure of performance as it tells how efficiently a firm has been able to use its assets to generate profit. Other studies also found ROA more suitable to measure corporate performance as it eliminates accounting bias. (Hitt et al 1997([15]; (Ruigrok and Wagner, 2003) [16]

This research will use ROA to measure corporate performance.

3.4 Measurement of Firm Size

A firm's size can be measured in three ways: total assets, total sales, and total number of employees. A technology driven firm is likely to generate more business per employee as compared to a manufacturing firm or labour intensive firms which employ more workers. For example, e-commerce company Flipkart is able to generate more sales than many manufacturing firms with much lower number of employees. Thus, number of employees is

not a suitable measure to measure firm's size. Another problem with total number of employees is, labour input is also driven by locality of firm and state labour laws. Thus, it is difficult to make comparison between businesses located in different states.

Total assets is also not suitable to size of firms. Problem with total asset is, a capital intensive firm requires more capital investment to generate same amount of business as compared to a labour-intensive firm.

On the other hand, total sales is more suitable measure to measure size of firm. All inputs (capital and labor) are used to increase revenue. Irrespective of the nature of business of firms, total revenue can be used to compare the size of firms. Thus, revenue is a robust measure to compare size of two firms.

3.5 Aspects of Corporate Financial Performance

Financial performance is evaluation of financial health and financial performance of a firm. Financial performance of a firm can be assessed in terms of firm's liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and risk. Financial ratios provide effective measures of a firm's financial performance and indicate clues about firm's financial position. Financial ratios are calculated using values from firm's financial statements. The financial statements are primary sources of financial information of any firm. The stakeholders use financial statements to evaluate financial health and financial performance of a firm, and make informed decisions. The corporate financial performance of a firm can be measured based on four aspects: liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and financial risk.

Liquidity

The liquidity ratios are used to measure liquidity position of a firm. The liquidity ratios tell if a firm is likely to face difficulties in meeting its short term obligations. Some popular liquidity ratios are: current ratio, quick ration, and cash ratio. Current ratio is most widely used liquidity ratio to measure the liquidity position of a firm.

Current Ratio = Current Assets / Current Liabilities

The quick ratio focuses only on those current assets that can be easily converted to cash. The quick ratio does not include inventory. There are industries where inventory level is high. Thus, quick ratio is not a right metric to compare firms from industries where inventory level is inherently high with firms from industries where inventory level is inherently low.

This study uses current ratio as a measure of liquidity position because current ratio takes all current assets and current liabilities into consideration.

Profitability

Profitability ratios tell about a firm's ability to generate profit. In other words, profitability ratios measure a firm's ability to generate return on equity, assets, capital employed, or profit margin. Some popular profitability ratios are: ROE, ROA, profit margin, ROCE.

The disadvantage of using profitability ratios to measure profitability of a firm is, these ratios ignore quality of earnings.

Efficiency

Financial efficiency of a firm refers to firm's ability to use its assets and liabilities to generate profit. The efficiency ratios are used to measure how efficiently a firm is using its assets and liabilities to generate income. The efficiency ratios include: Fixed Asset Turnover, Total Asset Turnover, and Inventory Turnover.

Risk

Solvency risk refers to a firm's ability to meet its debt and other obligations. If proportion of debt increases in capital structure, firm's solvency risk also increases as the firm may face difficulties in paying interest on time and repay the debt. The solvency ratios measure solvency risk of a firm. The solvency ratios indicate if a firm is generating enough cash flow, or possess enough assets to meet its short-term and long-term obligations. Popular solvency ratios are: debt-to-equity ratio, debt-to-assets ratio, debt ratio, and interest coverage ratio.

3.6 Hypothesis Development

With the help of theoretical framework, this research will use two types of empirical studies to answer the research questions: exploratory research and hypothesis testing. Exploratory research is conducted when problem is not clear or more information is required. Exploratory research makes an attempt to further examine the subject and get further insight. Exploratory research helps in developing the best research methodology. Hypothesis testing is a statistical test that tells if there is enough evidence infer that certain proposition is true for entire population.

First research question is to establish a relationship between degree of unrelated diversification and corporate performance. Based on the review of existing literature, this study proposes that

there is negative relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance.

Thus, first hypothesis can be stated as:

Hypothesis 1: In Indian market, corporate performance is negatively related to the degree of diversification.

Second research question is to determine impact of diversification on corporate financial performance with respect to liquidity, profitability, efficiency and solvency risk. As existing literatures propose that diversification and corporate performance are negatively related, in this study we assume that diversification has negative impact on each of the four aspects of financial performance. Thus, four hypotheses are developed to assess the impact of diversification on corporate performance as follows:

Hypothesis 2a: In Indian market, unrelated diversification has negative impact on liquidity of the firms.

Hypothesis 2b: In Indian market, unrelated diversification has negative impact on profitability of the firms.

Hypothesis 2c: In Indian market, unrelated diversification has negative impact on efficiency of the firms.

Hypothesis 2d: In Indian market, unrelated diversification has negative impact on solvency risk of the firms.

Third research question is to identify the relationship between size of firm and corporate performance in Indian market. This study assumes that size of firm has no significant impact on corporate performance. Hence, hypothesis can be developed as:

Hypothesis 3: There is no relationship between size of firm and corporate performance.

Fourth research question is to find out if there is any industry-wise variation in corporate performance of diversified firms. Fourth hypothesis is developed as:

Hypothesis 4: There is no industry-wise variation in corporate performance of diversified firms.

3.7 Type of Data and Data Sources

For this study following data are collected for each company selected in sample:

Turnover, net profit, operating income, total asset, current asset, long term asset, total liabilities, current liabilities, long term liabilities, stock holder's equity, business segments a firm operates in.

For the purpose of this study, secondary sources of data are used. Annual report of the companies act as major source of data. The financial data and annual reports are obtained from public domain viz NSE/BSE website, SEBI website, and corporate website of respective companies. The financial data are also be obtained from database maintained by Center for Monitoring the Indian Economy (CMIE). Other important sources of information are: SEBI

website, Exchange (NSE/BSE) website, moneycontrol.com, Press releases issued by company, and exchange information published in leading financial newspapers.

3.8 Criteria for Selection of a Company for Study

The scope of this study is limited to large size publicly traded companies. The publicly traded companies need to make certain disclosures and make their financial reports public. These companies are regulated by SEBI. One can expect more transparency and higher level of corporate governance at large firms. By choosing only large firms in sample, outliers are excluded from the study.

The companies chosen for study must satisfy all of the following criteria:

1. Turnover of company should be at least 500 Crores in the reporting year company is diversifying.
2. Firm should report sales in two or more unrelated businesses.
3. The company must be listed on NSE/BSE.
4. The event of diversification must have been occurred between FY 2000-01 and FY 2009-10.
5. Company should have been remain listed at least for 4 years after diversification.

Sample and Size

For the purpose of this study, stratified sampling technique is used. In stratified sampling technique, population is divided into subgroups or strata. The strata should be mutually exclusive. It means, a company can be a member of one strata only. The researcher obtains sample from each strata. In this study, the population is divided into various industries. Any firm will belong to only one industry based on largest revenue contributor business. According

to resource based theory, firms can deploy resources and exploit its resources to achieve its goals and create sustainable competitive advantage over competitors. (Wernerfelt, 1984) [17]; (Barney et. al., 2001) [18] Large companies have access to large resources that enable them to deploy resources in new businesses to achieve competitive advantage. So, this study is limited to large companies from leading industries. Top 5 industries in terms of turnover are chosen for study. From each chosen industry, five largest diversified firms in terms of turnover who fulfil set criteria are chosen for this study. Limiting the scope of study to large industries and large firms of each industry controls the impact of disproportional size of firms on study. By choosing equal number of firms from each industry, impact of industry specific events on study is minimized. This way, this study minimizes the impact of control variables on study.

According to the turnover reported in financial year 2013-14, ten largest sectors are:

Oil and Gas, Information Technology, Steel, Automobiles, Engineering, Power, Financial Services, Telecommunication, Pharmaceuticals, and Textile.

In each industry, top 15 firms in terms of turnover reported in FY 2013-14 are considered. Top five firms in terms of turnover who diversified into unrelated business between FY 2000-01 and FY 2009-10 are selected in sample.

In Oil and Gas industry, Hindustan Petroleum, Oil & Natural Gas Corporation Ltd. (ONGC), and Mangalore Refineries & Petrochemicals Ltd (MRPL) did not diversify into unrelated businesses during FY2000-01 and FY 2009-10. Hence, these firms are excluded from sample.

Following firms are selected in sample from oil and gas industry:

1. Indian Oil Corporation Ltd
2. Reliance Industries Ltd.

3. Bharat Petroleum Corporation Ltd.
4. Essar Oil Limited
5. GAIL (India) Ltd.

In Information Technology Sector, no top 15 firms in terms of revenue diversified into unrelated business between FY 2000-01 and 2009-10. Hence, no firm from Information Technology sector is chosen in sample.

In Steel sector, largest firm in terms of turnover, JSW Steel Ltd, did not diversify into unrelated business during the said period. Firms chosen in sample from this industry are:

1. Steel Authority of India Ltd.
2. Tata Steel Ltd.
3. Jindal Steel & Power Ltd.
4. Jindal Stainless
5. Bhushan Steel ltd.

In Automobile industry, large firms not included in sample are: Hero Motocorp Ltd., Bajaj Auto Ltd., TVS Motor Company Ltd., Escorts Ltd., Force Motors Ltd., and Eicher Motors Ltd., as these firms did not diversify into unrelated business during FY 2000-01 and FY 2009-

10. The firms chosen in sample from this industry are:

1. Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.
2. Mahjindra & Mahindra Ltd.
3. Tata Motors Ltd.
4. Ashok Leyland
5. Amtek Auto

In Engineering sector, large firms who did not diversify into unrelated business during the specified period are: Bharat Heavy Electricals Ltd., Bharat Electronics Ltd., Voltas Ltd., and Havell's India Ltd. The firms chosen in sample from this industry are:

1. Larsen & Turbo Ltd.
2. Punj Lloyd Ltd.
3. Crompton Greaves Ltd.
4. Apar Industries Ltd.
5. Thermax Ltd.

In Power Generation and Transmission sector, firms chosen in sample are:

1. National Thermal Power Corporation
2. Power Grid Corporation
3. Reliance Infra
4. PTC India Ltd
5. Tata Power

In this study, a sample of size 25 is selected choosing five companies from top five industries.

3.9 Analysis of Diversification Decision of Sample Firms

3.9.1 Sector: Oil and Gas

Indian Oil Corporation is the largest firm operating in refining and marketing of petroleum products. In 2004, company diversified into manufacturing of petrochemical products. This diversification can be explained through resource-based theory. Indian Oil already has facility to produce petrochemicals at refineries. Indian Oil can leverage existing distribution network, brand image, and human resources in petrochemical business. Bharat Petroleum, another

refiner and marketer of oil and gas diversified into E&P business in 2003. The E&P business is entirely new line of business where Bharat Petroleum cannot leverage its tangible or intangible resources. However, this diversification can be seen as backward integration. Diversification of Bharat Petroleum in E&P business can be seen as an attempt to mitigate risk by having more control on supply chain. Essar Oil was in oil exploration business. Company diversified in refining and marketing of oil business. This diversification decision also can be seen as an attempt to mitigate risk through forward integration. Similarly, GAIL, a dominant player in oil and gas transportation, and manufacturing of petrochemicals, diversified into extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas. This diversification decision can be seen as an attempt to mitigate risk through backward integration. The transaction cost theory explains why firms diversify through vertical integration.

Reliance Industries, the largest private company in India, was a dominant player in oil exploration and refining. Company diversified into a number of unrelated businesses including oil marketing, retail trade, and telecommunication. The diversification decision of Reliance Industries is unlikely to find cognitive relatedness, or seen as an attempt to mitigate risk. This diversification decision may be a part of management's vision to create a conglomerate where different clusters of related businesses are controlled and operated by different divisions. In future, Reliance Industries can spin off different divisions into independent companies. The diversification decision of Reliance Industries can be explained through market power theory.

3.9.2 Sector: Steel

SAIL is a leading company in production of iron and steel. SAIL has diversified into cement business through joint ventures with Jaypee Associates. SAIL manufactures cement using slag

generated by blast furnace during the process of manufacturing of steel. This diversification decision can be explained through resource-based theory and transaction theory. SAIL has scarce resources. Company can profitably deploy and exploit its scarce resources by entering in cement business. Through diversification, SAIL can lower transaction cost. Another steel manufacturer, Tata Steel, diversified into coal mining and mining of lignite. The diversification decision of Tata Steel can be explained through transaction cost theory and seen as an attempt to mitigate risk through backward integration. Backward integration ensures supply of inputs, and reduces dependency on suppliers. Jindal Steel & Power Ltd, a leading company in manufacturing of steel and steel products, diversified into generation of power. Jindal Steel was already generating power for own consumption through captive power plant. Company used existing tangible and intangible resources, including technology, human resources, and know-how to enter in power generation business. This diversification decision can be explained through resource-based view. There is relatedness based on cross-business transfer of competences and knowledge between the businesses. Similarly, diversification of Jindal Stainless into architectural and design solutions for stainless steel companies can be explained through resource-based view.

3.9.3 Sector: Automobile

Maruti Suzuki India Ltd., the largest manufacturer of passenger vehicles in India, diversified into selling motor insurance under Maruti Insurance brand name. Though there is no tangible relatedness between two businesses, both businesses have cognitive relationship. Motor vehicles and motor insurance are complementary products. The buyers who buy motor vehicle also purchase motor insurance. Maruti Suzuki can sell motor vehicle and vehicle insurance as a bundle, and cross subsidize products to sell more vehicles. Mahindra & Mahindra was a leading player in agricultural equipment and SUVs. Company leveraged its tangible and

intangible resources to enter in manufacturing of passenger cars. This diversification decision can be explained through resource-based view. Tata Motors entered into the business of pre-owned vehicles through “Tata Motor Assured” in 2008. Tata Motors can leverage its existing distribution network to sell pre-owned vehicles. This diversification decision can be explained through resource-based view as Tata Motors aims to leverage its resources to achieve higher growth.

Diversification of Ashok Leyland, a leading truck manufacturer, in development of defence system through JV Ashok Leyland Defence System Ltd. In March 2008, and diversification of Amtek Auto into manufacturing of railway wagon in 2009 cannot be explained through resource-based view or transaction cost theory. There are no visible cognitive relationship between the businesses these companies operate in and diversified into. These diversification decisions can be explained either through agency theory or market power theory.

3.9.4 Sector: Engineering

Larsen & Turbo Ltd is a conglomerate having business interest in engineering, construction, consultancy, and information technology. In 2007, L&T diversified into power generation and distribution. There is no direct tangible relatedness between the businesses L&T operate in. Another similar diversification decision is by Crompton Greaves Ltd, an engineering company, into power distribution in 2007-08. The rationale of these diversification decisions is to create a new line of business, which can be explained through market power theory or agency theory. Punj Loyd Limited, another leading engineering company, diversified into petrochemicals, and development of urban infrastructure projects such as airports, rail transit system, jetties and developments of hotels and resorts. Diversification decision of Punj Loyd into development of

urban infrastructure projects can be explained through market power theory and resource-based view as company can leverage its existing resources in new business. But, diversification of Punj Loyd in petrochemical business does not seem to have any cognitive relatedness. This diversification decision can be explained through Agency theory. Another example of diversification of engineering company in unrelated business is by Apar Industries into manufacturing of automotive lubricants under license agreement with ENI, Italy in 2007. While ENI is the world's eighth largest automotive lubricant manufacturer, Apar Industries does not have any tangible or intangible relatedness with lubricant manufacturing business. Thermax Limited diversified into construction and maintenance of power plants. There is cognitive relatedness between existing line of business of Tehrmax and the new business firm entered in. Termax can leverage its know-how, and talent pool in new business.

3.9.5 Sector: Power Generation and Transmission

NTPC is the largest power generation company in India. In 2002-03, NTPC diversified into power trading and consultancy business. Tata Power, another power generation company, also diversified into power trading business in 2004-05. These diversification decision can be explained through transaction cost theory. Through diversification, NTPC and Tata Power aim to reduce transaction cost and have more control on distribution network. Reliance Infra diversified into construction and maintenance of power plants business in 2004-05. Reliance Infra has entered into a business where it can leverage its know-how and intangible resources.

Power Grid, the largest owner of electric grid, entered into wired telecommunication activities through its telecom venture PowerTel in 2001. While there is no direct relationship between two businesses, Power Grid leverages its existing infrastructure in new business. Power Trading Corporation, a leading provider of power trading solutions, diversified into financial

services in 2006 through its arm PTC India Financial Services Ltd. Though in first glance there seems to be no relatedness between two businesses, close examination of business of PTC India Financial Services Ltd. reveals that company provides total financial services to the entities in energy value chain. The activities of the new business of PTC include extending credit to projects in the field of power generation, transmission, distribution, and developing other fuel related infrastructure. So, there is cognitive relatedness between the existing business and new business of PTC. However, this diversification decision can be seen as creation of a new line of business which can be explained through market power theory.

Table-3.2 lists the companies, its existing line of business, diversification into new business, year of diversification, possible rationale for diversification, and appropriate theories that can explain the diversification decision.

Table-3.2: List of companies, diversification area, year of diversification, and applicable theory

Company	Existing Businesses	Diversified Into	Year of Diversification	Remarks	Theory used to Explain Diversification Decision
Sector: Oil & Gas					
Indian Oil Corporation Limited	Crude refining, oil and gas marketing, and oil and gas transportation	Petrochemicals	2004-05	Forward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
Reliance Industries Limited	Oil Exploration, Refining, and Marketing	Retail Network	2006-07	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory

Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited	Oil and gas refining and marketing	Oil exploration	2006-07	Backward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
Essar Oil Limited	Oil Exploration, Refining, and Marketing	Oil refining, oil marketing	2008-09	Forward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
G A I L (India) Limited	Gas transportation, petrochemicals	Oil Exploration	2006-07	Backward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
Sector: Steel					
Steel Authority Of India Limited	Iron and Steel manufacturing	Cement manufacturing	2007-08	Forward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
Tata Steel Limited	Iron and Steel manufacturing	Mining of hard coal, Mining of lignite	2007-08	Backward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
Jindal Steel & Power Limited	Iron and Steel manufacturing	Power Generation	2007-08	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
Jindal Stainless	Iron and Steel manufacturing	Architectural and design solutions for stainless steel companies	2006-07	Leverage of intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
Bhushan Steel Limited	Iron and Steel manufacturing	Power Generation	2005-06	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
Sector: Automobile					
Maruti Suzuki India Limited	Manufacturing of motor vehicles	Selling motor insurance	2002-03	Selling complimentary product, cross-subsidizing	Market Power Theory

Mahindra & Mahindra Limited	Manufacturing of agriculture equipment, Manufacturing of commercial vehicles	Manufacturing of passenger vehicles	2007-08	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
Tata Motors Limited	Manufacturing of commercial vehicles, utility vehicles, and motor parts	Selling pre-owned vehicles	2008-09	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
Ashok Leyland	Manufacturing of heavy vehicles	Manufacturing of tanks, reservoir, and defense products	2007-08	Creation of new line of business	Market Theory, Power Agency Theory
Amtek Auto	Manufacturing parts and accessories for motor vehicle	Manufacturing of railway locomotives	2009-10	Creation of new line of business	Market Theory, Power Agency Theory
Sector: Engineering					
Larsen & Toubro Limited	Construction of building, construction of rail, roads and bridges	Power generation and distribution	2007-08	Creation of new line of business	Market Theory, Power Agency Theory
Punj Lloyd Limited	Construction of roads and railways, Manufacturing of electric equipment	Construction of urban infrastructure	2006-07	Creation of new line of business	Market Theory, Power Agency Theory
Crompton Greaves Limited	Manufacturing of electric equipment, Manufacturing of domestic appliances, Electrical and other construction activities	Electric power generation, transmission, and distribution	2007-08	Creation of new line of business	Market Theory, Power Agency Theory

Apar Industries Limited	Manufacturing of electric equipment	manufacturing of automotive lubricants	2007-08	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory, Agency Theory
Thermax Limited	Manufacturing of fabricated metal products	Construction and maintenance of power plants	2003-04	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
Sector: Power Generation and Transmission					
NTPC	Electric Power Generation	Power trading, Consultancy	2002-03	More control on distribution network	Transaction Cost Theory
Power Grid	Electric Power Transmission	Wired Telecommunication	2001-02	Leverage of tangible resources	Resource-based Theory
Reliance Infra	Electric Power Generation	Construction and maintenance of power plants	2004-05	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
PTC India Ltd	Power Trading Solution	Financial Services	2006-07	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory
TATA Power	Electric Power Generation	Power trading	2004-05	More control on distribution network	Transaction Cost Theory

3.10 Control variables

A firm's performance is influenced by various factors other than diversification strategy. This study includes following variables: Turnover, Total asset (size), Leverage of the firm, Short-term solvency position, Long-term solvency position, Return on Assets, and Profitability.

The short term and long term solvency positions are largely influenced by the type of industry a firm is operating in. (Rees, 1990) [19]; (Varazdin, 1999) [20] So, by including these variables in regression, influence of industry type on the performance of the firm can be captured.

3.11 General Analytical Model

In order to test hypotheses, empirical study is conducted. Microsoft Excel and SPSS are used for data analysis.

3.11.1 Hypothesis -1 Testing

To test Hypothesis-1, a linear regression is implemented. A linear regression function is represented as:

$$y=b_1+ b_2X \quad \text{-----} \quad (3.1)$$

Where,

y is corporate performance. ROA is used as a measure of corporate performance. Post-diversification five year average of ROA is considered as post-diversification corporate performance of firms.

X is the level of diversification. Herfindahl index based calculation is used as measure of level of diversification. Higher value of Herfindahl index represents higher degree of diversification. Hence, null hypothesis will be accepted if coefficient b_2 is significantly positive.

Regression analysis is used to find the relationship between unrelated product diversification and corporate performance.

3.11.2 Hypothesis 2 Testing

Second hypothesis determines impact of diversification on financial performance of diversified firms. The financial performance is evaluated from four perspectives: liquidity, efficiency, profitability, and solvency risk. In order to test this hypothesis, average of post-diversification five years value of financial measures are calculated. The hypothesis test will test if post-diversification five years average of financial measures deteriorated as compared to base year financial measures. Base year is considered as the year of diversification.

To test second hypothesis, one-tailed t- test is used. Null hypothesis assumes that financial performance of diversified firms deteriorated post-diversification. Hence, alternate hypothesis will be, financial performance of diversified firms improved post-diversification. We are interested in one side of probability distribution only. In this hypothesis test, there are two sample means: base year sample means and post-diversification five years average sample means. In this hypothesis test, t-test is used to compare two sample means. Formula of t is given by:

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} \text{-----} (3.2)$$

T

he number of degrees of freedom is computed using the formula

$$d.o.f. = \frac{\left(\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}\right)^2}{\left(\frac{s_1^4}{n_1^2(n_1-1)} + \frac{s_2^4}{n_2^2(n_2-1)}\right)} \text{-----} (3.3)$$

If degree of freedom value is in fraction, result is rounded to the nearest whole number. The

hypotheses are tested with 95% confidence level.

Testing Hypothesis 2a

This hypothesis assumes that in Indian market, diversification has negative impact on liquidity of the firms. Liquidity is measured in terms of current ratio and quick ratio. Quick ratio has focus on cash and cash equivalents which can be easily converted to cash. Current ratio is better measure of liquidity as it includes all current assets and current liabilities. In this hypothesis testing, current ratio is used as measure of liquidity. Higher the value of current ratio, better the liquidity position. The null hypothesis assumes that current ratio has deteriorated post-diversification. Hence, null hypothesis can be expressed as:

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$$

Where, μ_1 = mean of post-diversification five year average of current ratio of firms.

μ_2 = mean of base year current ratio of firms.

We define alternate hypothesis as:

$$H_1: \mu_1 > \mu_2$$

This hypothesis test is right-tailed test.

Testing Hypothesis 2b

This hypothesis assumes that in Indian market, diversification has negative impact on profitability of the firms. There are several measures of profitability viz net profit margin, .

operating income margin, return on equity, and return on asset. Ultimate goal of a firm is to maximize long-term value for shareholders. ROE measures return on shareholder's equity. In this hypothesis test, ROE is taken as measure of profitability. Operating profit margin and net profit margin completely ignore a company's strategy. For example, if a company aims to earn profit from volume, company can operate on lower profit margin. ROA is not considered as a measure of profitability in this test because industries vary on utilization of assets. Higher the value of ROE, better the profitability of the firm. The null hypothesis assumes that ROE has deteriorated post-diversification. Hence, null hypothesis can be expressed as:

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$$

Where, μ_1 = mean of post-diversification five year average of ROE of firms.

μ_2 = mean of base year ROE of firms.

Alternate hypothesis is defined as:

$$H_1: \mu_1 > \mu_2$$

This hypothesis test is right-tailed test.

Testing Hypothesis 2c

This hypothesis assumes that in Indian market, diversification has negative impact on efficiency of the firms. Popular measures of efficiency are: fixed asset turnover, total asset turnover, and inventory turnover. In this test, inventory turnover is not considered as a measure

of efficiency as some industries operate at lower inventory while in some industry inventory level is high. Inventory turnover is not a true measure of efficiency for service industry. Similarly, fixed asset turnover is not considered as true measure of efficiency in this case because some industries use fixed asset extensively. Total asset turnover is used as a measure of efficiency in this test. Total asset represents use of total capital (debt and equity). Hence, total asset turnover is true representative of efficiency across industries. Higher the value of total asset turnover, more efficient a firm is in utilizing its assets. The null hypothesis assumes that total asset turnover has deteriorated post-diversification. Hence, null hypothesis can be expressed as:

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$$

Where, $\mu_1 = \text{mean of post-diversification five year average of total asset turnover of firms.}$

$\mu_2 = \text{mean of base year total asset turnover of firms.}$

Alternate hypothesis is defined as:

$$H_1: \mu_1 > \mu_2$$

This hypothesis test is right-tailed test.

Test of Hypothesis 2d

This hypothesis assumes that in Indian market, diversification has negative impact on solvency risk of the firms. Popular measures of solvency risk are debt-to-equity ratio and debt-to-asset

ratio. Debt-to-equity (D/E) ratio is widely used as a measure of solvency risk. In this hypothesis test, D/E ratio is used as a measure of solvency risk. Higher the value of D/E ratio, greater the solvency risk. The null hypothesis assumes debt-to-equity ratio has deteriorated post-diversification. Hence, null hypothesis can be expressed as:

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$$

Where, $\mu_1 = \text{mean of post-diversification five year average of D/E of firms.}$

$\mu_2 = \text{mean of base year D/E of firms.}$

Alternate hypothesis is defined as:

$$H_1: \mu_1 < \mu_2$$

This hypothesis test is left-tailed test.

3.11.3 Hypothesis 3 Testing

Hypothesis 3 assumes that size of firm has no significant impact on corporate performance. i.e. there is no relationship between size of firm and corporate performance. Corporate performance is measured using ROA. Post-diversification five year average of ROA is considered as measure of post-diversification corporate performance of firms. Size of firm is measured in terms of total sales. Post-diversification average of five year total sales is considered as a measure of size of firm.

To test Hypotehsis-3, a linear regression will be implemented. A linear regression function is represented as:

$$y=b_1+ b_2x \quad \text{-----} \quad (3.4)$$

Where,

y is corporate performance. ROA is used as measure of corporate performance. Post-diversification five year average of ROA is considered as post-diversification corporate performance of firms.

X is the size of firms. Post-diversification five year average of total revenue is used as measure of size of firms. Higher the value of total average sales, larger the size of firm. Null hypothesis will be accepted if coefficient b_2 is insignificant. If b_2 is significant, null hypothesis is rejected.

3.11.4 Hypothesis 4 Testing

This hypothesis assumes that post-diversification corporate performance does not vary from one industry to other. Corporate performance is measured in terms of Return on Asset (ROA). Higher the value of ROA, better the corporate performance. To test this hypothesis, post-diversification five year average ROA is taken as a measure of corporate performance.

The null hypothesis is stated as: All population means are equal

$$H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4 = \mu_5$$

Where:

μ_1 = Mean post-diversification five year average of ROA for Oil & Gas industry

μ_2 = Mean post-diversification five year average of ROA for Steel industry

μ_3 = Mean post-diversification five year average of ROA for Automobile industry

μ_4 = Mean post-diversification five year average of ROA for Engineering industry

μ_5 = Mean post-diversification five year average of ROA for Power generation and transmission industry

Alternative hypothesis can be stated as:

H1: At least one mean value is different

The Single Factor ANOVA (also called One-way ANOVA) technique is used to test the null hypothesis that the means of several populations are equal.

The ANOVA technique provides F value. Null hypothesis is rejected when F value is significantly large. The p-value is also used to determine whether null hypothesis should be accepted or rejected. If p-value is less than the significance level α , null hypothesis is rejected.

Using F value

If $F < F_{crit}$, the null hypothesis is accepted.

if $F > F_{crit}$, the null hypothesis is rejected. It means, at least one of the means is different.

Using p value

If $p \text{ value} < \alpha$, null hypothesis is rejected.

If $p \text{ value} > \alpha$, null hypothesis is accepted.

The ANOVA technique does not tell where the difference lies. If null hypothesis is rejected, t-test is conducted to test each pair of means.

3.12 Summary

In this study, a sample of 25 companies is selected, choosing five companies from each of the top five industries in terms of turnover. Out of the sample of 25 companies, 6 companies took diversification decision driven by vertical integration. Diversification decisions of 8 companies were driven by creation of new line of business to have more market power. Diversification decision of 8 companies were driven by leveraging tangible and intangible resources. In power sector, two companies diversified to have more control over distribution network. The diversification decision of Maruti Suzuki was to sell complimentary product and create opportunities for cross subsidizing. In oil and gas sector, vertical integration has been major rationale behind unrelated diversification. Creation of new line of business has been a motivation for unrelated diversification mostly for private sector companies, especially in engineering sector. There is no single dominant rationale for unrelated diversification among Indian firms. The unrelated diversification decisions of Indian firms are mainly driven by vertical integration, leveraging tangible and intangible resources, and having more market power through creation of new line of business.

This study answers four major research questions. To answer the research questions, four major hypotheses are developed. Answer of first research question establishes relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. Regression analysis is used to establish relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. The answer of second research question studies impact of unrelated product diversification on financial performance of firms. The financial performance of firms has four aspects: liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and solvency risk. To answer second research question, four hypotheses are developed. As sample size is less than 30, t-test is used to test these hypotheses. The answer of third research question studies impact of size of firm on financial performance. Post-diversification five year average of total revenue is used as measure of size of firms. Post-diversification five year average of ROA is considered as post-diversification corporate performance of firms. A linear regression analysis between size and corporate performance is used to establish the relationship between size and corporate performance. The answer of fourth research question studies industry-wise variation in post-diversification corporate performance. Mean post-diversification five year average of ROA is used to measure corporate performance of firms in each industry. The One-way ANOVA is used to test this hypothesis.

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CHAPTER 4

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION (AGGREGATE STUDY, SIZE-WISE STUDY, AND INDUSTRY-WISE STUDY)

This chapter conducts aggregate study, industry-wise study, and size-wise study on a sample of 30 firms. As a part of aggregate study, impact of unrelated diversification on firms on various financial parameters is studied. Aggregate study also tests Hypothesis 1, which aims to establish relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. The aggregate analysis also tests Hypothesis 2, which studies impact of unrelated diversification on financial performance of firms. The Hypothesis 2 is divided into four parts, and tests impact of unrelated diversification on liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and solvency risk of the firms. In size-wise study, hypothesis 3 is tested. Hypothesis 3 studies the relationship between size of firm and post-diversification corporate performance. In industry-wise study of impact of unrelated diversification on corporate performance, Hypothesis 4 is tested. Hypothesis 4 studies industry-wise variation in post-diversification corporate performance of diversified firms.

4.1 Data

For this study, stratified sampling technique is used. Population for this study is the Indian firms who entered into unrelated businesses. The population is divided into subgroups based on industry. The subgroups (strata) are mutually exclusive. A firm can belong to one industry only. In case a firm operates in more than one industry before diversification, the primary business of the firm is used to determine the industry to which firm belongs to. For example, Reliance Industries Ltd operates in oil refining and marketing, retail, and telecommunication.

The primary business of Reliance Industries is oil refining and marketing. So, Reliance Industries is considered under Oil and Gas industry.

The large firms have stable business and access to more resources. They are able to deploy resources in new businesses more prudently than small businesses. For this reason, this study is conducted on large size firms only. Another requirement to be included in population is, firm should be a publicly traded firm. The publicly traded firms have to make several financial and business disclosures. The regulators require publicly traded firms to comply with many regulations that ensure high degree of transparency and better corporate governance. The sample for this study includes five largest diversified firms in terms of turnover who diversified into unrelated business between 2001 and 2010 from five largest industries in terms of turnover. No firm among ten largest firms in Information Technology industry diversified into unrelated business during event window. So, no firm from Information Technology industry is included in this study. The five largest industries who contributed to sample are: Oil and Gas, Steel, Automobiles, Engineering, and Power. Five largest firms in terms of turnover who fulfill the criteria are selected from each of the five industries. This study is conducted on a sample of 25 firms.

4.2 Aggregate Study

Aggregate data refers to numerical information collected from multiple sources on multiple measures and variables. The collected data is summarized for the purpose of statistical analysis. The aggregates represent a group average instead of individuals. Data is aggregated to summarize the data. In aggregate analysis, group level statistics are used for individual level variables. (Fisher et. al., 2016) [1].

In this study, aggregate analysis presents summary statistics of grouped data. The individual level variables are financial ratios of the firms. The financial ratios are ratios of financial data obtained from financial statements. The financial ratios allows the managers, creditors, investors and other stakeholders better understand the overall financial health of a firm. (Gitman, 2009) [2] The financial ratios are categorized according to various aspects of business. In this study, liquidity, profitability, efficiency, risk, and cash flow position of firms are studied. The liquidity financial ratios used in this study are current ratio and quick ratio. The profitability ratios used are net profit margin, operating profit margin, return on asset, and return on equity. The efficiency ratios used are fixed asset turnover, total asset turnover, and inventory turnover. The risk measures used in this study are debt-to-equity ratio, debt-to-asset ratio, and time interest earned. The cash flow indicators used are FCF/OCF, and operating cash flow ratio.

Central tendency is the statistical measure used to identify a single value that represents entire distribution. A central tendency provides accurate description of the distribution. Arithmetic mean is a measure of central tendency which is actually arithmetic average of a set of numbers. (Manikandan, 2011) [3] The mean uses every value of in the data set. So, mean is a good representative of data. Disadvantage of using mean is that it is sensitive to outliers. If sample size is small, outliers can have significant impact on mean value.

In this aggregate analysis, financial ratios of individual firms are calculated for base year. Base year is the year of diversification. The financial ratios for each year after diversification are also calculated for each firm in the sample. In aggregate analysis, mean (average) of the financial ratios are calculated. All members of the sample are market leaders of five largest industries in terms of turnover, which minimizes the probability of a data value being outlier.

The mean uses each value of the data set. So, use of mean in aggregate analysis ensures that the aggregate value represents each member of sample.

The mean value of each financial ratio for base year is calculated, which is arithmetic average of corresponding financial ratio for each firm for base year. The average value for base year is compared with mean value of post-diversification average of financial ratios for each firm for five years post-diversification.

Table -4.1 shows average of measure of average of five years under study for all 25 firms vis-à-vis average of the measure for base year.

Table- 4.1 : Post-diversification five year average Vs. base year

	Mean (base Year)	Mean (post-diversification average)
Liquidity		
Current ratio	1.08	0.86
Quick Ratio	0.64	0.48
Profitability		
Net profit margin	0.096	0.099
Operating Profit Margin	0.182	0.177
Return on Asset	0.118	0.101
Return on Equity	0.179	0.136
Efficiency		
Fixed asset turnover	10.73	11.37

Total asset turnover	2.06	1.79
Inventory turnover	9.55	10.74
Risk		
Debt-to-equity ratio	1.74	2.07
Debt-to-asset ratio	0.36	0.38
Time-interest-earned	13.41	14.00
Cash Flow indicator		
FCF/OCF	0.66	1.29
Operating cash flow ratio	0.23	0.30

4.2.1 Liquidity

Current ratio and quick ratio are measures of liquidity position of a firm. Post-diversification average current ratio as well as quick ratio declined as compared to the average current ratio and quick ratio of the base year. Decline in liquidity ratios show that unrelated diversification had negative impact on the liquidity of position of firms.

4.2.2 Profitability

Post-diversification average net profit margin of firms slightly improved as compared to average base year net profit margin, but all other profitability measures, operating profit margin, ROA and ROE declined. It shows that on average post-diversification profitability of firms declined. Slight improvement in net profit margin may be on account of lower taxation.

4.2.3 Efficiency

Post-diversification average fixed asset turnover and inventory turnover improved as compared to average base year fixed asset turnover and inventory turnover. It shows that post diversification, firms have been able to utilize fixed assets more efficiently. Improvement in inventory turnover shows that firms have been able to move inventory faster. However, Post-diversification average total asset turnover declined as compared to average base year total asset turnover. It shows that, firm's ability to utilize short-term assets declined post-diversification.

4.2.4 Risk

Risk is measured on three parameters: debt-to-equity ratio, debt-to-asset ratio and time-interest-earned. Post-diversification average debt-to-equity ratio and debt-to-asset ratio increased as compared to average base year debt-to-equity ratio and debt-to-asset ratio. It shows that firm's solvency risk increased. However, Post-diversification average time-interest-earned improved slightly as compared to average base year time-interest-earned, which means firm's ability to pay interest on time improved. This may be because firm's funded diversification using debt as well as equity. Hence, there is more increase in profit as compared to increase in interest, which led to improvement in TIE.

4.2.5 Cash Flow Indicator

The cash flow indicators used in this study are: FCF/OCF ratio and operating cash flow ratio. Post-diversification average FCF/OCF ratio improved as compared to average base year FCF/OCF ratio, which shows that firm's ability to generate free cash flow improved. The Post-diversification average operating cash flow ratio also improved as compared to average base

year operating cash flow ratio, which shows that firm's ability to generate operating cash flow improved.

4.2.6 Summary

The aggregate descriptive analysis shows that post-diversification, on average firm's efficiency, ability to generate operating cash flow and free cash flow improved, but liquidity position and profitability declined. Post-diversification, on average firm's solvency risk (measured in terms of percentage of debt in capital structure) increased, but firm's ability to pay interest also improved. Decline in liquidity ratio and solvency ratio can be attributed to investment in new business. A firm needs to make investment in new business it enters into which eats up cash. This leads to decline in current assets. As a result, liquidity position of firm deteriorates. A firm can raise capital using debt or equity. Financing diversification with debt is a common practice. So, when a firm enters into new business, firm borrows to finance this strategy, which increases proportion of debt in capital structure. As a result, post-diversification debt-to-equity ratio goes up. Higher debt-to-equity ratio shows that post-diversification a firm is exposed to higher degree of risk. The business a firm is entering into generates additional revenue, profit, and cash flow, which improves financial performance on certain parameters. There is no uniform impact of unrelated diversification on all aspects of corporate performance. While on average firm's efficiency, ability to generate operating cash flow, free cash flow, and ability to pay interest improves, firm's liquidity position deteriorates and solvency risk increases.

4.3 Hypothesis 1: Relationship between Degree of Diversification and Corporate Performance

The first hypothesis assumes that there is no relationship between the degree of diversification of firm and corporate performance. A linear regression function is used to test this hypothesis.

Diagram 4.1 Degree of diversification vs Corporate performance

The linear regression function is represented as:

$$y = b_1 + b_2X \quad \text{-----} \quad (4.1)$$

Where,

y is corporate performance. Post-diversification five year average of ROA is used as post-diversification corporate performance of firms.

X is the degree of diversification. Herfindahl calculation based degree of diversification as explained in section 3.2 is used as a measure of degree of diversification.

Thus, linear regression function is written as:

$$ROA = b_1 + b_2 * D(I) \text{ ----- (4.2)}$$

If coefficient b_2 is insignificant, null hypothesis is rejected.

Result of regression analysis is presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Regression Analysis between Degree of Diversification and Corporate Performance

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.252423
R Square	0.063718
Adjusted R Square	0.02301
Standard Error	0.07128
Observations	25

Table 4.3 ANOVA (Degree of Diversification and Corporate Performance)

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	0.007952609	0.007952609	1.56523643	0.223477103
Residual	23	0.116857755	0.005080772		
Total	24	0.124810364			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.028783246	0.059523135	0.483564021	0.633267189
Degree of Diversification (X)	0.117770534	0.094134034	1.251094093	0.223477103

R square value of regression analysis is 0.063718 which is very low. Adjusted R square value, which stands at 0.02301, is also low. R-square supposes that the independent values in the model explain the variation in the dependent variable. The R-square tells what proportion of variation in dependent variable can be explained using the independent variables. The adjusted R-square value gives the percentage of variation explained by only significant independent variables. The independent variables in this model explain only 6.37% variation in corporate performance. There is only one independent variable used in this model which explains 6.37% variation in corporate performance.

Since the coefficient b_2 is significant, Null hypothesis cannot be rejected. The relationship between degree of diversification of firm and corporate performance is further investigated using correlation coefficient.

$$\text{Correlation Coefficient} = 0.2524$$

The correlation coefficient shows that there is moderately positive correlation between degree of diversification of firm and corporate performance.

Based on the regression analysis, linear regression function can be written as:

$$\text{Corporate Performance} = 0.0288 + 0.1178 * \text{Degree of diversification}$$

Result

Degree of diversification alone does not explain the variability in corporate performance. Regression analysis shows that degree of diversification has significant impact on corporate performance. Majority of studies conducted in developing countries found negative relationship between diversification and corporate performance. (Agrawal et al., 1992) [4]; (Lang & Stulz, 1994) [5]; (Lins & Servaes, 1999) [6] Many large firms diversify into unrelated business through unrelated acquisitions. But, very few such acquisitions are successful. Most of the unrelated acquisitions are divested subsequently. (Kaplan & Weisbach, 1992) [7] Unlike those studies, this study found moderately positive relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. The positive relationship can be attributed to underdeveloped capital market, inadequate regulatory protection, and different social structure in India than in developed countries. Diversified business groups find favorable environment in developing countries including India.

4.4 Study of Impact of Unrelated Diversification on Financial Performance of Firms

Hypothesis 2 tests impact of unrelated diversification on financial performance of firms who entered into unrelated business between 2001 and 2010. The financial performance has four important dimensions: liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and solvency risk. To study the impact of unrelated diversification on firms on four financial parameters, hypothesis 2 is divided into four parts. Hypothesis 2a tests impact of unrelated diversification on liquidity position of diversified firms, Hypothesis 2b tests impact on profitability of diversified firms, Hypothesis 2c tests impact on efficiency of diversified firms, and Hypothesis 2d tests impact of unrelated diversification on solvency risk of diversified firms.

4.4.1 Hypothesis 2a

Hypothesis 2a studies impact of unrelated diversification on liquidity position of diversified firms. Current ratio is chosen as the measure of liquidity. The null hypothesis assumes that current ratio has deteriorated post-diversification. The alternative hypothesis assumes that current ratio improved post-diversification. To test this hypothesis, one-tailed t-test is used at significance level of 0.05.

Post Diversification five year average of current ratio of firms

N_1 : 25

$$df_1 = N - 1 = 25 - 1 = 24$$

M_1 : 0.86

SS_1 : 4.28

$$s^2_1 = SS_1 / (N - 1) = 4.28 / (25 - 1) = 0.18$$

Base year current ratio of firms

N_2 : 25

$$df_2 = N - 1 = 25 - 1 = 24$$

M_2 : 1.08

SS_2 : 14.93

$$s^2_2 = SS_2 / (N - 1) = 14.93 / (25 - 1) = 0.62$$

t-value Calculation

$$s_p^2 = ((df_1/(df_1 + df_2)) * s_1^2) + ((df_2/(df_1 + df_2)) * s_2^2) = ((24/48) * 0.18) + ((24/48) * 0.62) = 0.4$$

$$s_{M1}^2 = s_p^2/N_1 = 0.4/25 = 0.016$$

$$s_{M2}^2 = s_p^2/N_2 = 0.4/25 = 0.016$$

$$t = (M_1 - M_2) / \sqrt{(s_{M1}^2 + s_{M2}^2)} = -0.22 / \sqrt{0.032} = -1.245$$

t- value = -1.245

p- value = 0.1096

Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

p-value $> \alpha$, so we fail to reject the null hypothesis. i.e. the result is not significant.

Result : The one tailed t-test could not find enough evidence to prove that unrelated diversification improved liquidity position of the firms. The null hypothesis assumed that unrelated diversification deteriorates liquidity position of firms. The t-test could not find enough evidence to reject this claim. Thus, this study accepts the assumption made by null hypothesis that unrelated diversification deteriorates liquidity position of firms. This result is in line with findings of studies conducted in developed countries. Majority of studies conducted in developed markets found that unrelated diversification has negative impact on liquidity position of firms. This study substantiates those findings. Diversification into new business needs funding. A firm entering into a new business uses liquidity of existing businesses to

finance diversification. The new business may not start generating enough liquidity immediately. As a result, unrelated diversification deteriorates liquidity position of firms.

4.4.2 Hypothesis 2b

Hypothesis 2b studies impact of unrelated diversification on profitability of diversified forms. Return on equity (ROE) is chosen as the measure of profitability. The null hypothesis assumes that ROE of firms has deteriorated post-diversification. The alternative hypothesis assumes that ROE improved post-diversification. To test this hypothesis, one-tailed t-test is used at significance level of 0.05.

Post Diversification five year average of ROE of firms

$N_1: 25$

$df_1 = N - 1 = 25 - 1 = 24$

$M_1: 0.14$

$SS_1: 0.35$

$s^2_1 = SS_1/(N - 1) = 0.35/(25-1) = 0.01$

Base year ROE of firms

$N_2: 25$

$df_2 = N - 1 = 25 - 1 = 24$

$M_2: 0.18$

$SS_2: 0.26$

$s^2_2 = SS_2/(N - 1) = 0.26/(25-1) = 0.01$

t-value Calculation

$s^2_p = ((df_1/(df_1 + df_2)) * s^2_1) + ((df_2/(df_1 + df_2)) * s^2_2) = ((24/48) * 0.01) + ((24/48) * 0.01) = 0.01$

$s^2_{M1} = s^2_p/N_1 = 0.01/25 = 0$

$s^2_{M2} = s^2_p/N_2 = 0.01/25 = 0$

$t = (M_1 - M_2) / \sqrt{(s^2_{M1} + s^2_{M2})} = -0.04 / \sqrt{0} = -1.3$

t- value = -1.3

p- value = 0.10007

Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

p-value $> \alpha$, so we fail to reject the null hypothesis. i.e. the result is not significant.

Result

The one tailed t-test could not find enough evidence to prove that unrelated diversification improved profitability of the firms. The null hypothesis assumed that unrelated diversification deteriorates profitability (measured by ROE) of firms. The t-test could not find enough evidence to reject this claim. Thus, this study accepts the assumption made by null hypothesis that profitability of firms has deteriorated post-diversification. This result is in line with findings of studies conducted in developed countries.

4.4.3 Hypothesis 2c

This hypothesis testing studies the impact of unrelated diversification on efficiency of firm. Efficiency is measured by total asset turnover. The null hypothesis assumes that *total asset turnover* has deteriorated post-diversification. The alternative hypothesis assumes that *total asset turnover* improved post-diversification. To test this hypothesis, one-tailed t-test is used at significance level of 0.05.

Post Diversification five year average of total asset turnover of firms

N_1 : 25

$$df_1 = N - 1 = 25 - 1 = 24$$

M_1 : 1.79

SS_1 : 56.16

$$s^2_1 = SS_1 / (N - 1) = 56.16 / (25 - 1) = 2.34$$

Base year total asset turnover of firms

$N_2: 25$

$$df_2 = N - 1 = 25 - 1 = 24$$

$M_2: 2.06$

$SS_2: 150.95$

$$s^2_2 = SS_2 / (N - 1) = 150.95 / (25 - 1) = 6.29$$

t-value Calculation

$$s^2_p = ((df_1 / (df_1 + df_2)) * s^2_1) + ((df_2 / (df_1 + df_2)) * s^2_2) = ((24 / 48) * 2.34) + ((24 / 48) * 6.29) = 4.31$$

$$s^2_{M1} = s^2_p / N_1 = 4.31 / 25 = 0.17$$

$$s^2_{M2} = s^2_p / N_2 = 4.31 / 25 = 0.17$$

$$t = (M_1 - M_2) / \sqrt{(s^2_{M1} + s^2_{M2})} = -0.27 / \sqrt{0.35} = -0.462$$

t- value = -0.462

p- value = 0.3232

Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

p-value $> \alpha$, so we fail to reject the null hypothesis. i.e. the result is not significant.

Result

The one tailed t-test could not find enough evidence to prove that unrelated diversification improved efficiency of the firms. The null hypothesis assumed that unrelated diversification has negative impact on efficiency of firms. Total asset turnover is a measure of efficiency of

firms. The t-test could not find enough evidence to reject this claim. Thus, this study accepts the assumption made by null hypothesis that efficiency of firms has deteriorated post-diversification. This result is in line with findings of studies conducted in developed countries.

4.4.4 Hypothesis 2d

This hypothesis establishes relationship between unrelated diversification and solvency risk. The null hypothesis assumes that solvency risk has increased post-diversification. It means, debt-to-equity ratio has increased post-diversification. The alternative hypothesis assumes that *debt-to-equity ratio decreased* post-diversification. To test this hypothesis, one-tailed t-test is used at significance level of 0.05.

Post Diversification five year average of debt-to-equity ratio of firms

N2: 25

$df2 = N - 1 = 25 - 1 = 24$

M2: 2.07

SS2: 56.09

$s22 = SS2/(N - 1) = 56.09/(25-1) = 2.34$

Base year debt-to-equity ratio of firms

N1: 25

$df1 = N - 1 = 25 - 1 = 24$

M1: 1.74

SS1: 11.31

$$s_{21} = SS1/(N - 1) = 11.31/(25-1) = 0.47$$

t-value Calculation

$$s_{2p} = ((df1/(df1 + df2)) * s_{21}) + ((df2/(df2 + df2)) * s_{22}) = ((24/48) * 2.34) + ((24/48) * 0.47) \\ = 1.4$$

$$s_{2M1} = s_{2p}/N1 = 1.4/25 = 0.06$$

$$s_{2M2} = s_{2p}/N2 = 1.4/25 = 0.06$$

$$t = (M1 - M2)/\sqrt{(s_{2M1} + s_{2M2})} = 0.33/\sqrt{0.11} = 0.99$$

$$t\text{-value} = 0.99$$

$$p\text{-value} = 0.16345$$

Significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

p-value $> \alpha$, so we fail to reject the null hypothesis. i.e. the result is not significant.

Result

The one tailed t-test could not find enough evidence to prove that unrelated diversification decreased debt-to-equity ratio of the firms. The null hypothesis assumed that unrelated diversification increases solvency risk of firms. The t-test could not find enough evidence to

reject this claim. Thus, this study accepts the assumption made by null hypothesis that solvency risk of firms has increased post-diversification. This result is in line with findings of studies conducted in developed countries.

4.5 Size-wise Study of Impact of Unrelated Diversification on Corporate Performance

The size-wise study of impact of unrelated diversification on corporate performance studies the relationship between size of firms and corporate performance. The third hypothesis studies the relationship between size of firm and corporate performance.

4.5.1 Hypothesis 3

The third hypothesis assumes that there is no relationship between size of firm and corporate performance. A linear regression function is used to test this hypothesis.

The linear regression function is represented as:

$$y=b_1+ b_2x$$

Where,

y is corporate performance. Post-diversification five year average of ROA is used to measure post-diversification corporate performance of firms.

X is the size of firms. Post-diversification five year average of total revenue is used as a measure of size of firms.

Diagram 4.2: Size of firm vs Corporate performance

Thus, linear regression function is written as:

$$ROA = b_1 + b_2 * Revenue \quad \text{----- (4.3)}$$

If coefficient b_2 is significant, null hypothesis is rejected.

Result of regression analysis is presented in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4 Regression Analysis between Size of Firm and Corporate Performance

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.091700939
R Square	0.008409062
Adjusted R Square	-0.034703587

Standard Error	0.073354656
Observations	25

Table 4.5 ANOVA (Size of Firm and Corporate Performance)

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Regression	1	0.001049538	0.00105	0.195049
Residual	23	0.123760826	0.005381	
Total	24	0.124810364		

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.105158355	0.017329343	6.068225	3.45E-06
Average Revenue (X)	-1.12874E-07	2.55577E-07	-0.44164	0.662872

The R square and Adjusted R square values of regression analysis are very low. The adjusted R square value is 0.0347 which means significant independent variables explain only 3.47% variation in the dependent variable. There is only one independent variable – size of firm. The dependent variable is corporate performance. Thus, size of firm explains only 3.47% variation in corporate performance. The size of firm alone is not a major determinant of corporate performance. Further, this regression analysis produced coefficient 1.12874E-07 which is insignificant.

Based on the regression analysis, linear regression function can be written as:

$$\text{Corporate Performance} = 0.1052 - \text{Size} * (1.12874E-07) \quad \text{-----} \quad (4.4)$$

Since the coefficient b2 is insignificant, we accept Null hypothesis. i.e. There is no significant relationship between size of diversified firms and corporate performance.

The relationship between size of firm and corporate performance is further investigated using correlation coefficient.

$$\text{Correlation Coefficient} = -0.092 \quad \text{-----} \quad (4.5)$$

The correlation coefficient shows that there is weak negative correlation between size of firm and their corporate performance.

Result

The resource-based theory of diversification argues that firms diversify because of excess capacity in productive factors or resources. (Penrose, 1959) [8] Later, researchers also included intangible resources like services, human resources and knowledge that influence diversification decisions of firms. (Nelson & Winter, 1982)[9]; (Lippman & Rumelt, 1982)[10] Firms having excess tangible or intangible resources tend to diversify in industries having similar marketing, R&D or production pattern where firm can utilize excess resources to create value. (Silverman, 1999) [11] In general, large firms tend to have excess resources. So, large firms have tendency to enter into new businesses where they can utilize excess resources. The new business where resources can be utilized may not have close relationship with existing line of business. The new business may have some similar processes where a firm can utilize resources, but overall this new business may not have any direct relationship with existing line of business.

The regression analysis found very weak negative relationship between size of firm and corporate performance. As value of coefficient is insignificant, there is not enough evidence to prove any relationship between size of firm and corporate performance. However, weak negative correlation is observed between size of diversified firms and their corporate performance. Based on the results of regression analysis it can be concluded that large size firms do not get more benefits from diversification than small size firms. Though relationship between size of firm and corporate performance is weak, there is negative relationship between two. It means, large size firms are less likely to improve corporate performance by entering into new businesses than small firms. However, there is no conclusive evidence to establish that large size firms are at more disadvantageous position.

4.6 Industry-wise Study of Impact of Unrelated Diversification on Corporate Performance

The industry-wise study of impact of unrelated diversification on corporate performance studies if there is any variation in post-diversification corporate performance of firms in various industries. Hypothesis 4 studies the industry-wise variation in post-diversification corporate performance of diversified firms.

4.6.1 Hypothesis 4

The fourth hypothesis assumes that there is no industry-wise variation in post-diversification corporate performance of diversified firms. The sample is divided in five industries. Each industry has five firms. The null hypothesis assumes that post-diversification average corporate

performance of each industry is same. The ROA is used as a measure of corporate performance. Post-diversification five year ROA for companies are grouped industry-wise. Single Factor ANOVA is used to test the null hypothesis that the means of several populations are equal.

Result of ANOVA is presented in Table 4.6 and Table 4.7.

Table- 4.6: Single Factor ANOVA (Industry Analysis)

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Oil & Gas	5	0.407147	0.081429	0.005508
Steel	5	0.43819	0.087638	0.002537
Automobile	5	0.500183	0.100037	0.004127
Engineering	5	0.854683	0.170937	0.01022
Power gen & Trans	5	0.32692	0.065384	0.000409

Table 4.7 ANOVA (Sources of Variation)

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	0.03361	4	0.008403	1.84267	0.160255	2.866081
Within Groups	0.0912	20	0.00456			
Total	0.12481	24				

F value: 1.843

F crit: 2.866

P value: 0.16

The F value < F crit

Also, at 95% confidence level, significance level $\alpha = 0.05$

p value > α value

As F value is less than F crit value, and p value is greater than significance level 0.05, Null hypothesis is not rejected.

Result

There is not enough evidence to prove that there is any industry-wide variation in post-diversification corporate performance of diversified firms. It means, there is no industry-wide variation in post-diversification corporate performance of diversified firms. No industry is at comparatively advantageous or disadvantageous position in getting benefits of unrelated diversification. The unrelated diversification has similar impact across industries.

4.7 Summary

In aggregate analysis, mean value of financial ratios of firms in sample for the year of diversification are compared with the mean value of financial ratios for five years post diversification. The aggregate study shows that there is no uniformity in impact of unrelated corporate diversification on performance of firms. Unrelated diversification resulted in decline in liquidity ratios. In general, average post-diversification profitability of firms also declined, however, slight improvement in net profit margin was observed which may be on account of lower taxation. Post-diversification, fixed asset utilization of firms improved. Improvement in fixed asset utilization may be a result of synergy crated due to entering in new business. A firm can use some of its existing fixed assets in new business even if new business is unrelated to

existing line of business of the firm. In general, improvement in inventory turnover was also observed. However, post-diversification total asset utilization of firms declined. Entry into unrelated business increased firm's solvency risk. But, firm's ability to pay interest improved. Entering into a new business also improved firm's ability to generate operating cash flow. This study shows that on average firm's efficiency, ability to pay interest, and ability to generate cash flows improved after entering into a new business, but firm's liquidity position deteriorated and solvency risk increased.

One major premise of this study is to determine relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. If a firm has diversified into related businesses, degree of diversification would be less. A firm having business interests in unrelated businesses would have higher degree of diversification. Regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. Herfindahl calculation based degree of diversification was used to measure degree of diversification. Return of Assets (ROA) was used as a measure of corporate performance. R square value of regression analysis is 0.063718, which was quite low. Correlation coefficient between degree of diversification and corporate performance was 0.2524. The linear regression analysis shows that there is moderately positive relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. This finding was different from the findings of studies conducted in developed countries, which found negative relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. The positive relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance can be attributed to different institutional structure of developing countries. Developing countries such as India have underdeveloped capital market, inadequate regulatory protection, and different social structure than in developed countries. This structure creates incentives for firms entering in unrelated business. Low value of R square shows that degree

of diversification alone cannot fully explain the variability in corporate performance. There are other dominant factors that influence the corporate performance of firms.

This research also studied impact of unrelated diversification on financial performance of firms. The financial performance is measured on four important parameters: liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and solvency risk. In line with findings of major studies conducted in developed countries, this study found that unrelated diversification deteriorated firm's liquidity position. A firm entering in a new business exhaust its excess current assets to finance diversification and operation of new business. But, new business does not immediately start generating enough liquidity. So, unrelated diversification deteriorates a firm's liquidity position. To study the impact of unrelated diversification on profitability of firms, Return on equity (ROE) was used as a measure of profitability. In line with findings of major studies conducted in developed countries, this study also found that unrelated diversification deteriorated profitability of firms diversifying into unrelated business. To study impact of unrelated diversification on efficiency of firms, total asset turnover was used to measure efficiency. This study found that unrelated diversification has negative impact on efficiency of firms. This finding is in line with the findings of major studied conducted in developed countries. To study the impact of unrelated diversification on solvency risk, debt-to-equity ratio was used to measure solvency risk. This study found that unrelated diversification increases debt-to-equity ratio of firms. Thus, unrelated diversification increases solvency risk of firms. This finding is also in line with the findings of major studies conducted in developed countries. The findings of this study substantiate the findings of major studies conducted in this field that found that unrelated diversification has negative impact on financial performance of firms.

This research also studied relationship between size of firms and corporate performance. Post-diversification five year average of ROA was used as measure of corporate performance of firms. Post-diversification five year average of total revenue was used to measure size of firm. Linear regression analysis was conducted to determine relationship between size of firm and corporate performance. The adjusted R square value is 0.0347 which means significant independent variables explain only 3.47% variation in the dependent variable. This shows that size of firm has very less impact on corporate performance of firms. The relationship between size of firm and corporate performance is further investigated using correlation coefficient. The correlation coefficient between size of firm and corporate performance was -0.092 which shows weak negative correlation between size of firm and corporate performance. This study shows that large size firms are less likely to improve performance by entering into unrelated businesses than small size firms. However, very weak negative correlation indicates that large size firms may not be at much disadvantageous position than small size firms. This finding contradicts the finding of studies that found higher growth for large sized diversified groups of firms than small sized groups of firms. (Kakani, 2000) [13] However, premises of study of Kakani (2000) were different. Kakani's study was focused on large business groups rather than individual firms diversifying into unrelated business.

This research also conducted industry-wise study of impact of unrelated diversification on corporate performance. This study tried to find out if there were any variation in post-diversification corporate performance of firms in various industries. The sample of 25 companies consisted of five firms from each of top five industries in terms of revenue. ROA was used as measure of corporate performance. Single factor ANOVA was used to study the variation in post-diversification corporate performance of firms in five industries. This study could not find any industry-wide variation in post-diversification corporate performance of

diversified firms. It means, being in a particular industry has no advantage or disadvantage in getting benefits of unrelated diversification. Individual firms can extract more benefits from unrelated diversification by virtue of position in market, nature of new business firm is entering into, individual financial strengths, and management strengths.

This research study found that, unlike in developed countries, unrelated diversification is not avoidable in developing countries. In developing countries like India, unrelated diversification has mixed impact on various aspects of performance. This study found moderately positive correlation between degree of diversification and corporate performance. It means, a well-diversified firm is likely to perform better than a less diversified firm. Majority of studies conducted in developed countries had found that unrelated diversification deteriorates corporate performance. The developing countries have different institutional structure and business environment than developed markets. In developing markets, motivation for unrelated diversification can be explained using market power theory. Firms diversify into new businesses to enhance market power. A firm having dominant position in greater number of markets enjoy greater market power. (Hill, 1985) [12] Greater market power allows a firm to raise price in industries where it has dominant position, and use this excess profit to subsidize the cost in other businesses.

This study further investigated impact of unrelated diversification on four aspects of financial performance and found that unrelated diversification has negative impact on liquidity position, efficiency, profitability, and solvency risk position. The findings of this study are in line with major studies conducted in this area. This research study also investigated impact of size on corporate performance of diversified firms. This study found slightly negative correlation

between size of firm and corporate performance. It means, a large size firm diversifying into unrelated business is less likely to be more successful than a small size firm diversifying into unrelated business. Study of variation in post-diversification corporate performance in various industries revealed that industry has no impact on post-diversification performance of the firms. Some findings of this study do not support the findings of major studies conducted in other countries. The difference in findings can be explained using structure point of view of market power theory. According to structure point of view, market structure determines the economic performance of a firm. (Montgomery, 1985) [14] Similar studies conducted in emerging markets could not conclusively establish negative relationship between unrelated diversification and corporate performance. (Li, 2004) [15] The market structure of India is different from the market structure of America, Europe, and other developed markets. The market structure of India is closer to emerging markets.

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CHAPTER-5

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Introduction

Product diversification is a corporate action under which a firm creates a new product, modifies existing product or acquires other businesses to add new products in product line. After product diversification, firm reports sales in more than one industry segment. The industry segment is identified by Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) code. Product diversification has been one of the most dominant corporate strategy for several decades. Firms adopt product diversification strategy to mitigate risk, utilize underutilized resources, gain market power, or get access to more resources. Through product diversification, a firm aims to achieve total value of corporate more than the sum of the values of individual business units.

After World War II, diversification strategy was adopted by large firms across the world. This resulted in formation of large corporations in 1960s and 1970s. Like developed countries, diversification was adopted by large corporations in developing countries also. In India, large business houses such as TATA, Birla, Dalmia, Ruia, Reliance have business interests in many industries. But, not all diversifications have been successful. Diversification into a new business has inherent risks. When a company diversifies into a new business, resources are diverted to new business that could have been used in existing businesses to create more value for shareholders. Diversification also requires additional financing. Firms can finance diversification using debt or equity. Use of debt to finance diversification increases solvency risk. Firms realized that diversification does not always create value for shareholders. Many companies realized their mistake and initiated large scale corporate restructuring programs. (Porter, 1987)

Failure of many diversification decisions propelled debate on whether diversification improves corporate performance and creates value for shareholders. Related diversification may create synergy and hence improve efficiency and profitability of a firm. But, same is not true for unrelated diversification. Entering into a new business where firm has no prior experience is riskier than entering into a related business where firm can leverage its existing resources and experience. Rationales for unrelated diversification are not very clear. Prahalad and Bettis (1986) argue that unrelated diversification can be successful because of “cognitive relatedness”. There may be some elusive linkage between businesses. If businesses are strategically similar, they can be managed using single dominant logic. Conglomerates also form divisions which are cluster of related businesses. Firms also adopt unrelated diversification strategy to balance risk and return from independent businesses. Diversification into unrelated business also gives a firm access to new technologies and develop human resources.

In India, economic and regulatory framework has been conducive to unrelated diversification. Post-independence, the industrial policy of India was centred on five-year plans where state would decide quantum of production and issue licenses to companies to produce goods. State would also set quota on production. For any business, getting license to produce goods determined what they could produce. The license raj encouraged unrelated product diversification and creation of conglomerates. The diversification decisions were influenced by ability to get license to produce certain products rather than efficiency. After several economic crisis, government implemented New Economic Policy in 1991. With NEP, liberalization started in India. Government control was dismantled in most of the industries. In post-liberalization era, businesses started focusing on efficiency in making diversification decisions.

The studies conducted in this field found that diversification into related business creates synergy, but unrelated diversification does not create synergy. Unrelated diversification is widely believed to be inefficient. Majority of studies found negative relationship between diversification and corporate performance. Montgomery & Wernerfelt (1988) found that diversified firms trade at a discount as compared to undiversified firms. Though majority of studies found negative relationship between diversification and corporate performance, there are firms like GE, TATA, Reliance and other conglomerates that created value for shareholders through unrelated diversification.

Most of the studies in this field are conducted in developed countries. The structural, social, and regulatory environment of developing countries are different from those of developed countries. In developing countries like India, most of the successful businesses are conglomerates. The findings of researches conducted in developed countries may not be applicable to India.

In the light of above background, the present studies attempts to:

4. Explore relationship between unrelated diversification and corporate performance for Indian firms.
5. Examine the impact of unrelated diversification on four aspects of corporate financial performance: liquidity, profitability, efficiency and solvency risk.
6. Examine impact of size of unrelated diversified Indian firms on financial performance.

7. Identify industry-wise variation in financial performance of the unrelated diversified Indian firms

The Industry Standard Code (SIC) are used to determine relatedness between two businesses. The SIC code is five digit code. The 2 digit (Division), 3 digit (Group), 4 digit (Class), and 5 digit (Subclass) SIC can be used to measure the degree of diversification. (CSO, 2008) The SIC codes do not account for the proportionality of various businesses of the firm. This study has adopted Herfindahl based calculation as used by Jung (2003) in measuring direction of diversification.

Degree of unrelated product diversification $D = 1 - \sum P_i^2 / (\sum P_i)^2$

Where P_i = Proportion of number of operations in industry i to total number of operations.

This study uses Return on Assets (ROA) as measure of corporate performance. Revenue is used as measure of size of firm as all inputs to production (capital and labor) are used to increase revenue. Financial ratios are used to measure financial performance of firms. Current ratio is used as measure of liquidity, ROE is used as measure of profitability, total asset turnover is used as a measure of efficiency, and debt-to-equity ratio is used as measure of solvency risk.

For this study, population was publicly traded companies listed at NSE and/or BSE having turnover more than 500 cr in the reporting year company diversified into unrelated business. The unrelated diversification event must have occurred between FY 2000-01 and FY 2009-10, and company should have remained listed for at least four years after diversification. In this study, stratified sampling technique is used. The strata are mutually exclusive. The sample consists of top five companies in terms of turnover who diversified into unrelated business

between 2000 and 2010 from top five industries in terms of turnover. According to turnover reported in FY 2013-14, Information Technology was the second largest industry in terms of turnover. No firm from top 15 firms in terms of turnover in information technology industry diversified into unrelated business between FY 2000-01 and FY 2009-10. So, no firm from information technology industry is included in sample. Out of sample of 25 companies, five firms are taken from each of oil and gas, steel, automobiles, engineering, and power industries.

From Annual Reports of companies, the relevant information of each company have been collected. This study used data from financial statements (balance sheet, income statement, and statement of cash flows) of the companies. This study also used information from annual reports, press releases, and declarations made by companies to stock exchanges and SEBI.

This study has used statistical tools like central tendencies, standard deviation, correlation, and regression analysis. Some other statistical tools such as t test, F test and ANOVA have also been used.

The financial performance of firms on various parameters such as liquidity, efficiency, solvency risk, and profitability are calculated using financial ratios such as current ratio, total asset turnover ratio, debt-to-equity ratio, return on assets, and return on equity. To calculate degree of diversification, this study has adopted Herfindahl based calculation which is based on SIC code. This method is easy to calculate, yet more powerful than basic SIC based method to calculate degree of diversification as this method considers proportion of number of operations in industry in calculation of degree of diversification.

5.2 Findings

The findings and conclusions have been divided into four five broad categories: Aggregate study, Relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance of firms, Impact of unrelated diversification on financial performance of firms, impact of size on corporate performance of firms, and industry-wise variation in corporate performance of firms.

5.2.1 Aggregate Analysis

In aggregate analysis, group level statistics are used for individual level variables. The aggregate analysis presents summary statistics of aggregated data. In this study, financial ratios of individual firms in sample are calculated for base year, which is the year of diversification. Then, mean of each financial ratio for base year is calculated. Next, financial ratios for each firm for post-diversification for five years are calculated and for each firm average of each financial ratio for post-diversification five years are calculated. Then, mean of average of each financial ratio is calculated. The mean value for base year is compared with mean value of post-diversification average of financial ratios for each firm for five years after diversification.

This study analyses liquidity ratios, profitability ratios, efficiency ratios, solvency ratios, and cash flow indicators of firms. The post-diversification average current ratio was 0.86, lower than base year average current ratio which stood at 1.08. The post-diversification average quick ratio also declined from 0.64 in base year to 0.48. Both major liquidity ratios declined after diversification into unrelated business. This study finds that at aggregate level, unrelated diversification deteriorates liquidity position.

In this study, four profitability ratios are used: net profit margin, operating profit margin, return on asset, and return on equity. The net profit margin of firms improved after diversification,

but operating profit margin, return on assets, and return on equity declined. The average post-diversification net profit margin improved from 0.096 in base year to 0.099 after diversification. The operating profit margin improved from 0.182 in base year to 0.177 after diversification. The ROA declined from 0.118 in base year to 0.101 after diversification. The ROE declined from 0.179 to 0.136 after diversification.

This study used three efficiency ratios in aggregate analysis: fixed asset turnover ratio, total asset turnover ratio, and inventory turnover ratio. The fixed asset turnover ratio at aggregate level improved from 10.73 in base year to 11.37 after diversification. The inventory turnover ratio also improved from 9.55 times in base year to 10.74 times after diversification. But, total asset turnover declined from 2.06 in base year to 1.79 after diversification. This shows that post-diversification, firms are able to move inventory faster. Firms are also able to utilize fixed assets more efficiently. However, firm's ability to utilize short-term assets declined which resulted in decline in total asset turnover.

This study used three solvency ratios to assess impact of diversification on risk: debt-to-equity ratio, debt-to-asset ratio, and time-interest earned ratio. The debt to equity ratio increased from 1.74 in base year to 2.07 after diversification. The debt-to-asset ratio also increased slightly from 0.36 in base year to 0.38 post-diversification. The time-interest-earned ratio also increased from 13.41 in base year to 14 post-diversification. This study found that all solvency ratios deteriorated post-diversification. Diversification into unrelated business increases solvency risk of firms.

This study found that unrelated diversification improved cash-flow position of firms. The free cash flow to operating cash flow ratio improved dramatically from 0.66 in base year to 1.29 post-diversification. The operating cash flow ratio also improved from 0.23 in base year to 0.30 after

diversification. Increase in these two cash flow indicators show that after diversification into unrelated business, firm's capability to generate both operating cash flow and free cash flow improved.

5.2.2 Relationship between Degree of Unrelated Diversification and Corporate Performance

The studies conducted by Agrawal et al. (1992), Land & Slutz (1994), Lins & Servaes (1999), and other researchers found negative relationship between degree of unrelated diversification and corporate performance. But, these studies were conducted in developed countries and East Asian countries. Institutional structure of India is very different from the institutional structure of developed markets and East Asian markets. This study attempts to determine the relationship between degree of unrelated diversification and corporate performance in Indian market.

This study tests hypothesis "there is no relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance." A linear regression function is used to test this hypothesis. In this linear regression function, corporate performance is dependent variable and degree of diversification is independent variable. The corporate performance is measured using post-diversification five years average Return on Asset (ROA) of firms. The degree of diversification is measured using Herfindahl calculation based degree of diversification method which uses SIC code to find relatedness among industries.

The R square value of regression analysis is 0.063718 and adjusted R square value is 0.02301. Low value of R square tells that degree of diversification explains a small percentage of variation in corporate performance. There are other dominant factors that influence corporate performance. The coefficient b_2 of regression analysis is significant. So, null hypothesis cannot

be rejected. It means, there is some relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. The relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance is further investigated using correlation analysis. This study found correlation coefficient 0.2524 between degree of diversification and corporate performance.

This study found moderately positive relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. The finding of this study contradicts with the findings of majority of studies conducted in developed markets which found negative relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. The positive relationship between degree of diversification and can be attributed to the institutional structure of India which is quite different from the institutional structure of developed markets. Indian market has underdeveloped capital market, inadequate regulatory protection, and different social structure which create incentive for firms diversifying into unrelated businesses. Even after liberalization, success of firms is largely dependent on government policies and relationship with government. In India, firms do not operate in a competitive environment like they do in developed countries. The business and political environment in India create favourable conditions for firms to leverage its strengths, resources, and learning experience in new businesses.

5.2.3 Impact of Unrelated Diversification on Financial Performance of Firms

This study attempts to evaluate the impact of unrelated diversification on various aspects of firm's operating and financial performance. Four aspects of financial performance are evaluated in this study: liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and solvency. To study the impact of unrelated diversification on financial performance of firms, four hypotheses are tested. This study used one tailed t-test at 95% confidence level to test hypotheses.

To study the impact of unrelated diversification on liquidity of firms, post-diversification five years average current ratio is used with base year current ratio. The null hypothesis assumed that unrelated diversification deteriorated liquidity position of firms. The one-tailed t-value was -1.245 and p-value was 0.1096. The p-value was greater than significance level 0.05. The one tailed t-test could not find enough evidences to reject this null hypothesis. Thus, this study accepts the assumption made by null hypothesis that unrelated diversification deteriorates liquidity position of firms, which is in line with the findings of majority of studies conducted in developed markets. Entry into a new business forces a firm to use liquidity of existing businesses to finance operations of new business. This has negative impact on liquidity position of firms.

To study the impact of unrelated diversification on profitability of firms, post-diversification five years average ROE is compared with base year ROE. The null hypothesis assumed that unrelated diversification deteriorated profitability of firms. The one-tailed t-value was -1.3 and p-value was 0.10007. The p-value was greater than significance level 0.05. The one tailed t-test could not find enough evidences to reject this null hypothesis. Thus, this study accepts the assumption made by null hypothesis that unrelated diversification deteriorates profitability of firms. This study substantiates the findings of majority of studies conducted in developed markets.

To study the impact of unrelated diversification on profitability of firms, total asset turnover is used to measure efficiency of firms. The post-diversification five years average total asset turnover is compared with base year total asset turnover. The null hypothesis assumed that unrelated diversification deteriorated efficiency of firms. The one-tailed t-value was -0.462 and

p-value was 0.3232. The p-value was greater than significance level 0.05. The one tailed t-test could not find enough evidences to reject null hypothesis. Thus, this study accepts the assumption made by null hypothesis that unrelated diversification has negative impact on efficiency of firms.

To study the impact of unrelated diversification on solvency risk of firms, post-diversification five years average debt-to-equity ratio is compared with base year debt-to-equity ratio. The null hypothesis assumed that unrelated diversification increased solvency risk of firms. Debt-to-equity ratio is a measure of solvency risk of firms. Higher value of debt-to-equity ratio indicates higher solvency risk. The one-tailed t-value was 0.99 and p-value was 0.16345. The p-value was greater than significance level 0.05. The one tailed t-test could not find enough evidences to reject this null hypothesis. Thus, this study accepts the assumption made by null hypothesis that unrelated diversification increased solvency risk of firms. The studies conducted in developed countries also found that unrelated diversification increased solvency risk. Thus, the finding of this study is in line with findings of studies conducted in developed countries.

5.2.4 Relationship between Size of Firms and Corporate Performance

This study attempts to establish relationship between size of firms and post-diversification corporate performance. A linear regression function is used to determine the relationship. Post-diversification five year average of ROA is used as measure of corporate performance of firms. Post-diversification five year average of total revenue is used as a measure of size of firms. In this linear regression analysis, corporate performance is used as dependent variable and size of firm is used as independent variable.

The adjusted R square value of regression analysis was 0.0347 which means size of firm explain only 3.47% variation in the corporate performance. Further, regression analysis produced coefficient 1.12874E-07 which is insignificant. As coefficient is insignificant, there is no significant relationship between size of diversified firms and corporate performance. This study further investigated relationship between size of firm and corporate performance using correlation analysis. The correlation coefficient between size of firm and corporate performance was found to be -0.092. This study found weak negative relationship between size of firm and corporate performance. It means, large size firms do not get more benefits from unrelated diversification than small size firms. Rather, large firms are less likely to improve corporate performance by entering into unrelated business than a small size firm. However, there is not enough evidence to conclusively establish that large size firms are at more disadvantageous position.

5.2.5 Industry-wise Variation in Post-diversification Corporate Performance

This study attempts to find industry-wise variation in post-diversification corporate performance of firms. Null hypothesis assumes that there is no industry-wise variation in post-diversification corporate performance of firms. The sample is divided into five industries, each industry having five firms. Post-diversification five year average ROA is used as a measure of corporate performance. Single Factor ANOVA at 95% confidence level is used to test the null hypothesis.

The ANOVA analysis found F value 1.843 and p value 0.16. At 95% confidence level (or 0.05 significance level), Critical F value is 2.866. The F value was less than F crit value, and p value was greater than significance level 0.05. Thus, there was not enough evidence to reject

null hypothesis. This study could not find significant industry-wise variation in post-diversification corporate performance of diversified firms. The unrelated diversification has uniform impact across industries. No industry is at comparatively advantageous or disadvantageous position in entering into an unrelated business.

5.3 Conclusion

This study was conducted on Indian firms that diversified into unrelated businesses between 2001 and 2010. The studies conducted in developed countries found that unrelated diversification has negative impact on corporate performance. The researchers recommend that companies should focus on core businesses and avoid investing resources in unrelated businesses where there is little chance of creating synergy. But, unlike developed countries, unrelated diversification has mixed impact on various aspects of corporate performance in India. Contrary to the findings of researches conducted in Western countries, this research found mild positive correlation between degree of diversification and corporate performance. It means, a well-diversified firms can achieve better corporate performance than an undiversified firm. This finding is not in line with the findings of majority of researches conducted in the U.S. and other developed countries. However, R square value of regression between degree of diversification and corporate performance was low. Low R square value indicates low strength of regression between two variables.

India has different institutional structure and business environment from Western countries where majority of researches were conducted. The motivation of diversification in India may be different from the motivation of diversification in developed countries. The motivation for unrelated diversification in India can be explained using market power theory. Hill (1985)

argued that a firm having dominant position in greater number of markets enjoy greater market power. In developed countries, high level of competition and strong regulatory framework prohibits firms from misusing market power to raise price. But in India, regulatory framework has not matured yet. Firms can be motivated to diversify in unrelated businesses which allows them to raise price in industries where it has dominant position, and use this excess profit to subsidize the cost in other businesses.

This study also investigated impact of unrelated product diversification on various aspects of financial performance. This study found that unrelated product diversification has negative impact on liquidity position, efficiency, profitability, and solvency risk position. But, some specific measures of performance improved post-diversification. This study found positive impact of unrelated diversification on operating profit margin, fixed asset turnover ratio, inventory turnover ratio, and The time-interest-earned ratio. It means, unrelated diversification has mixed impact on financial performance of Indian firms.

This study also investigated impact of size on corporate performance of diversified firms. The regression analysis between size of firm (turnover) and corporate performance (ROA) found slightly negative correlation between size of firm and corporate performance. Though correlation coefficient was low, findings of this study indicate that a large size firm diversifying into unrelated business is less likely to be more successful than a small size firm diversifying into unrelated business. It can be safely concluded that large firms have no advantage by virtue of large size in extracting benefits from unrelated diversification.

This study also investigated variation in post-diversification corporate performance in various industries. This study could not find any significant variation in corporate performance of firms in various industries. It means, no industry has inherent advantage in diversifying into unrelated businesses.

Though this study broadly supports the findings of majority of studies conducted in developed countries, some findings of this study do not support the findings of major studies conducted in other countries. Some of the studies conducted in emerging markets also could not conclusively establish relationship between unrelated product diversification and corporate performance. The difference in findings can be explained using structure point of view of market power theory which argues that market structure determines the economic performance of a firm. The market structure of developing countries differ from the market structure of developed countries. As a result, all findings of researches conducted in developed countries may not be valid in the perspective of developing countries.

5.4 Contributions

Post World War II, diversification has been a dominant corporate strategy adopted by firms across world to create value for shareholders. Many firms diversified into unrelated businesses and created conglomerates. Some of the most successful companies such as GE and Samsung are conglomerates. But, not all unrelated diversifications are successful. Many unrelated diversifications failed and forced companies to divest unrelated businesses. Several researches were conducted on unrelated diversifications. Majority of researches found negative relationship between unrelated diversification and corporate performance. The researches conducted in this field found that unrelated diversification has negative impact on liquidity, profitability, and

efficiency of the firms. Post-diversification, solvency risk increases. The studies conducted on impact of unrelated diversification on stock price found that unrelated diversified firms trade at discount than undiversified firms.

Most of the researches in this field were conducted in the USA and Europe. Some researches were conducted in China and East Asian countries. The findings of these researches may not be valid in Indian perspective as India has different institutional structure than developed markets. In India, market is dominated by large business houses and public sector enterprises. The most successful business houses such as TATA, Reliance, Birla, Adani etc have interest in various unrelated businesses. Success of conglomerates in India suggest that unrelated diversification may not have similar impact on businesses in India as in developed markets.

This study builds a comprehensive framework to explain the unrelated diversification decisions made by Indian firms and its impact on corporate performance. This study asks specific questions: “what is the relationship between unrelated diversification and corporate performance?”, “what is the impact of unrelated diversification on liquidity, profitability, efficiency, and solvency risk of firms?”, “what is the relationship between size of firms and corporate performance of diversified firms”, and “is there significant industry-wise variation in post-diversification corporate performance of firms?”

To understand a great deal more about impact of unrelated diversification on corporate performance of firms in India, this study will not only provide new insight in academic level but also serve business decision making of Indian firms and policy making practices. The managers of Indian firms can get insight into factors influencing diversification decisions, and

how unrelated diversification can impact various aspects of performance of a firm.

One important merit of this study is to create awareness that the findings from literatures published in western countries, and experiences from developed markets would not be immediately applicable to businesses in developing markets. The researchers, educators, consultants, and business managers have been using received wisdom of western strategic management theories and findings of researches conducted in western countries. However, the institutional structure, and political and economic environment have strong influence on the way businesses perform. As institutional, economic, and political environment of India is different from those of developed markets, the findings of researches conducted in developed markets may not be immediately applicable in India. Similarly, the strategic management theories developed in western countries may not be immediately applicable in India. This study shows that contrary to the findings of researches conducted in developed markets which found that unrelated diversification deteriorates value of firms, unrelated diversification has mixed impact on performance of firms in India. For Indian firms, unrelated diversification may still be beneficial instead of value destroying. Indian firms can use unrelated diversification as a tool to improve efficiency and achieve organizational goals. The researchers, educators, and business managers have to be aware that there is no uniform pattern of how strategic management theories work and the outcome they result. Instead of working on received wisdom from western countries, they should work towards a direction to apply knowledge and experience to create wisdom valid in institutional environment of own country.

5.5 Limitations

This research has some limitations that must be considered. First and foremost, the main objective of this research is to study the impact of unrelated product diversification on Indian firms. The findings of this research may not be valid in other countries.

Second, since the diversification decision is an important strategic decision, there are a variety of elements influencing the decision-making process. The elements influencing diversification decisions are company specific.

However, due to data constraints and the limited scope of research, these limitations could not be addressed here and left for the future study.

5.6 Future Scope of Research

This research attempted to find relationship between degree of diversification and corporate performance. This study also attempted to evaluate the impact of unrelated diversification on various aspects of financial performance, and determine size-wise variation and industry-wise variation in corporate performance. There are areas that can be further explored.

A large number of studies have been conducted in the U.S., Europe and other developed countries in this particular area. This study has focused on impact of unrelated diversification on financial aspects of corporate performance. Further studies can be conducted on impact of unrelated diversification on stock performance. Similar studies were conducted in China and

Hong Kong, which found that stock of undiversified firms trade at premium to the stocks of diversified firms. But, capital market of India is quite different from the capital market of China and Hong Kong. The Indian market is experiencing tremendous changes in economic and institutional framework. The Indian capital market is more open and integrated to world capital market as compared to Chinese capital market. Hence, there is need to study the impact of unrelated diversification on stock price in Indian perspective.

In India, government policies play very significant role in the success of a firm. Government policies change with change of government at central as well as at state level. Further studies can be conducted with respect to impact of government policies on diversification decisions and corporate performance of diversified firms.

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Annexure-1

Sector-Wise Revenue of 25 Largest Industries

Revenue as per September 2013-14

Sr. No.	Sector Name	Revenue (Rs. in mn)	
		2014	2013
1	Oil and Gas	4225663.51	4392242
2	Information Technology	615815.21	575179.4
3	Steel	535391.6	494908.1
4	Automobiles	481236.5	426887.2
5	Engineering	452478.1	484993.4
6	Power	414187.4	381447.9
7	Financial Services	308834.22	269234.2
8	Telecom	287005.07	260473.1
9	Pharmaceuticals	224101.4	210249.7
10	Textile	196216.7	193768
11	Cement	194677.02	167800.9
12	Food Products	172993.8	163542.9
13	Non Ferrous Metals	149642.5	123963.1
14	Gems, Jewellery and watches	149050.4	115831.6
15	Diversified	139726.6	127904.1
16	Personal Care	136294.9	120686.9
17	Housing Finance	129900.6	114018
18	Mining	127192.7	146442.6

19	Agro Inputs	112243.4	102882.9
20	Others	100753.2	88094.7
21	Const/Bldg Material	99519.7	91843.52
22	Cigarettes	96869.7	85754.7
23	Auto Ancillaries	87028.6	74750.6
24	Chemicals	84295.9	79846.5

Annexure-2

**List of Ten Largest Companies in Five Largest Sectors with Unrelated Diversification
Details between 2001-2010**

Sector: Oil & Gas

Total Revenue (Rs. In Cr)

Company	FY 2013-14	Industry SIC	Diversified in industry (SIC)	Year of Diversification
Indian Oil Corporation Limited	479,527	192	201	2004-05
Reliance Industries Limited	398,641	192, 061,062, 201	47	2006-07
Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited	263,559	192	61	2006-07
Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Limited	224,793.65	Not diversified during specified period		
Essar Oil Limited	99,324.18	61	192	2008-09
Oil & Natural Gas Corporation Limited	90,499.19	No diversification		
Mangalore Refinery & Petrochemicals Limited	72,920.93	Not diversified during specified period		
GAIL (India) Limited	59,378.26	493	061, 062	2006-07
Chennai Petroleum Corporation Limited	49,455.55	Not diversified during specified period		
Petronet LNG Limited	37,831.33	Not diversified during specified period		

Sector: IT

	Revenue (Rs. in Cr)	Industry SIC	Diversified in industry (SIC)	Year of Diversification
Company	2013-14			
Tata Consultancy Services Limited	67,787.64		Not diversified during specified period	
Infosys Limited	46,917.00		Not diversified during specified period	
Wipro Limited	40,367.50		Not diversified during specified period	
H C L Technologies Limited	17,091.74		Not diversified during specified period	
H C L Infosystems Limited	17,091.74		Not diversified during specified period	
Tech Mahindra Limited	16,485.40		Not diversified during specified period	
Redington (India) Limited	11,429.03		Not diversified during specified period	
Oracle Financial Services Software Limited	3,780.39		Not diversified during specified period	
MindTree Limited	3,081.00		Not diversified during specified period	
Polaris Consulting & Services	2,012.03		Not diversified during specified period	

Sector: Steel

	Revenue (Rs. in Cr)	Industry SIC	Diversified in industry (SIC)	Year of Diversification
Company	2013-14			

JSW Steel Limited	44,180.57	Not diversified during this period		
Steel Authority Of India Limited	47,644.31	241, 243	239	2007-08
Tata Steel Limited	42,512.09	241, 243	051, 052	2007-08
Jindal Steel & Power Limited	14,304.84	241	351	2007-08
Jindal Stainless	11,456.57	241	711	2006-07
Bhushan Steel Limited	9,726.32	241	351	2005-06
Uttam Galva Steels Limited	5,291.04	Not diversified during specified period		
Jindal Saw Limited	5,277.69	Not diversified during specified period		
Welspun Corp Limited	4,543.28	Not diversified during specified period		

Sector: Automobile

	Revenue (Rs. in Cr)	Industry SIC	Diversified in industry (SIC)	Year of Diversification
Company	2013-14			
Maruti Suzuki India Limited	44,505.00	291	651	2002-03
Mahindra & Mahindra Limited	41,553.95	291, 282	291	2007-08
Tata Motors Limited	37,277.93	291, 292, 293	451	2008-09
Hero Motocorp Limited	25,713.49	3091		Undiversified
Bajaj Auto Limited	20,874.82	3091		Undiversified
Ashok Leyland	10,091.74	2910	251	2007-08

T V S Motor Company Limited	7,983.69	Not diversified during specified period		
Escorts Limited	6,393.97	Not diversified during specified period		
Amtek Auto	4,032.78	293	302	2009-10
Force Motors Limited	2,079.60	Not diversified during specified period		
Eicher Motors Limited	1,814.53	Not diversified during specified period		
Atul Auto Limited	1,307.40	Not diversified during specified period		

Sector: Engineering

	Revenue (Rs.in Cr)	Industry SIC	Diversified in industry (SIC)	Year of Diversification
Company	2013-2014			
Larsen & Toubro Limited	58,958.28	421,410, 422, 711	351	2007-08
Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited	39,667.46	Not diversified during specified period		
Punj Lloyd Limited	8,511.09	421, 271	410, 422	2006-07
Crompton Greaves Limited	7,678.06	271,432, 274, 275	351	2007-08
Bharat Electronics Limited	6,656.66	Not diversified during specified period		
Voltas Limited	5,163.61	Not diversified during specified period		
Havell`S India Limited	4,767.94	Not diversified during specified period		
Apar Industries Limited	4,494.53	271	192, 466	2007-08
Thermax Limited	4,370.54	251	422	2003-04

Bharat Forge Limited	3,563.07	Not diversified during specified period
Alstom T&D India Limited	3,559.28	Not diversified during specified period

Sector: Power Generation and Transmission

	Revenue (Rs.in Cr)	Industry SIC	Diversified in industry (SIC)	Year of Diversification
Company	2013-2014			
NTPC	74,708	351	461	2002-03
Power Grid	15,721	351	611	2001-02
Reliance Infra	12,581	351	422	2004-05
PTC India Ltd	11,551	351	649	2006-07
Adani Power	11,166	Not diversified during specified period		
TATA Power	9,283	351	461	2004-05
Torrent Power Ltd	8,817	Not diversified during specified period		
JSW Energy	5,687	Not diversified during specified period		

Annexure-3

Diversification Details of Sample Companies and Theory That Can Explain Diversification Decisions

S / N	Company	Existing Businesses	Diversified Into	Year of Diversif ication	Remarks	Theory used to Explain Diversification Decision
Sector: Oil & Gas						
1	Indian Oil Corporation Limited	Crude refining, oil and gas marketing, and oil and gas transportation	Petrochemicals	2004-05	Forward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
2	Reliance Industries Limited	Oil Exploration, Refining, and Marketing	Retailm Network	2006-07	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory
3	Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited	Oil and gas refining and marketing	Oil exploration	2006-07	Backward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
4	Essar Oil Limited	Oil Exploration, Refining, and Marketing	Oil refining, oil marketing	2008-09	Forward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
5	GAIL (India) Limited	Gas transportation, petrochemicals	Oil Exploration	2006-07	Backward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
Sector: Steel						

1	Steel Authority Of India Limited	Iron and Steel manufacturing	Cement manufacturing	2007-08	Forward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
2	Tata Steel Limited	Iron and Steel manufacturing	Mining of hard coal, Mining of lignite	2007-08	Backward Integration	Transaction Cost Theory, Resource-based Theory
3	Jindal Steel & Power Limited	Iron and Steel manufacturing	Power Generation	2007-08	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
4	Jindal Stainless	Iron and Steel manufacturing	Architectural and design solutions for stainless steel companies	2006-07	Leverage of intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
5	Bhushan Steel Limited	Iron and Steel manufacturing	Power Generation	2005-06	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
Sector: Automobile						
1	Maruti Suzuki India Limited	Manufacturing of motor vehicles	Selling motor insurance	2002-03	Selling complimentary product, cross-subsidizing	Market Power Theory

2	Mahindra & Mahindra Limited	Manufacturing of agriculture equipment, Manufacturing of commercial vehicles	Manufacturing of passenger vehicles	2007-08	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
3	Tata Motors Limited	Manufacturing of commercial vehicles, utility vehicles, and motor parts	Selling pre-owned vehicles	2008-09	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
4	Ashok Leyland	Manufacturing of heavy vehicles	Manufacturing of tanks, reservoir, and defence products	2007-08	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory, Agency Theory
5	Amtek Auto	Manufacturing parts and accessories for motor vehicle	Manufacturing of railway locomotives	2009-10	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory, Agency Theory
Sector: Engineering						
1	Larsen & Toubro Limited	Construction of building, construction of rail, roads and bridges	Power generation and distribution	2007-08	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory, Agency Theory
2	Punj Lloyd Limited	Construction of roads and railways, Manufacturing of electric equipment	Construction of urban infrastructure	2006-07	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory, Agency Theory

3	Crompton Greaves Limited	Manufacturing of electric equipment, Manufacturing of domestic appliances, Electrical and other construction activities	Electric power generation, transmission, and distribution	2007-08	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory, Agency Theory
4	Apar Industries Limited	Manufacturing of electric equipment	manufacturing of automotive lubricants	2007-08	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory, Agency Theory
5	Thermax Limited	Manufacturing of fabricated metal products	Construction and maintenance of power plants	2003-04	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
Sector: Power Generation and Transmission						
1	NTPC	Electric Power Generation	Power trading, Consultancy	2002-03	More control on distribution network	Transaction Cost Theory
2	Power Grid	Electric Power Transmission	Wired Telecommunication	2001-02	Leverage of tangible resources	Resource-based Theory
3	Reliance Infra	Electric Power Generation	Construction and maintenance of power plants	2004-05	Leverage of tangible and intangible resources	Resource-based Theory
4	PTC India Ltd	Power Trading Solution	Financial Services	2006-07	Creation of new line of business	Market Power Theory

5	TATA Power	Electric Power Generation	Power trading	2004-05	More control on distribution network	Transaction Cost Theory
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Annexure-4

Aggregate Analysis: Post-diversification five year average vs. base year

	Mean (base Year)	Mean (post-diversification average)
Liquidity		
Current ratio	1.08	0.86
Quick Ratio	0.64	0.48
Profitability		
Net profit margin	0.096	0.099
Operating Profit Margin	0.182	0.177
Return on Asset	0.118	0.101
Return on Equity	0.179	0.136
Efficiency		
Fixed asset turnover	10.73	11.37
Total asset turnover	2.06	1.79
Inventory turnover	9.55	10.74
Risk		
Debt-to-equity ratio	1.74	2.07
Debt-to-asset ratio	0.36	0.38
Time-interest-earned	13.41	14.00
Cash Flow indicator		
FCF/OCF	0.66	1.29
Operating cash flow ratio	0.23	0.30

Annexure-5

Impact of Unrelated Diversification on Financial Performance: Industry-wise Analysis

Liquidity: Current Ratio

Industry	Year 5	Year 4	Year 3	Year 2	Year 1	Base Year	Five year avg
Oil & Gas	0.69	0.67	0.55	0.63	0.59	0.65	0.62
Steel	0.92	0.79	0.63	0.76	0.77	0.89	0.77
Automobile	0.63	0.80	0.68	1.29	1.15	1.31	0.91
Engineering	1.24	1.07	0.92	1.01	0.98	1.27	1.04
Power gen & Trans	0.76	0.72	0.90	0.75	1.60	1.31	0.95

Liquidity: Quick Ratio

Industry	Year 5	Year 4	Year 3	Year 2	Year 1	Base Year	Five year avg
Oil & Gas	0.25	0.20	0.16	0.19	0.17	0.15	0.19
Steel	0.34	0.30	0.20	0.24	0.29	0.31	0.28
Automobile	0.30	0.41	0.36	0.84	0.71	0.82	0.53
Engineering	0.78	0.59	0.53	0.61	0.59	0.76	0.62
Power gen & Trans	0.63	0.59	0.78	0.60	1.42	1.14	0.80

Profitability: Net Profit Margin

Industry	Year 5	Year 4	Year 3	Year 2	Year 1	Base Year	Five year avg
Oil & Gas	0.040	0.046	0.056	0.067	0.059	0.049	0.053
Steel	0.126	0.143	0.111	0.137	0.157	0.146	0.135
Automobile	0.065	0.088	0.082	0.052	0.065	0.079	0.071
Engineering	0.054	0.077	0.076	0.060	0.068	0.057	0.067
Power gen & Trans	0.158	0.173	0.177	0.179	0.154	0.148	0.168

Profitability: Operating Profit Margin

Industry	Year 5	Year 4	Year 3	Year 2	Year 1	Base Year	Five year avg
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Oil & Gas	0.082	0.089	0.096	0.098	0.104	0.082	0.094
Steel	0.238	0.267	0.240	0.249	0.289	0.272	0.256
Automobile	0.140	0.153	0.159	0.140	0.123	0.126	0.143
Engineering	0.105	0.120	0.137	0.098	0.112	0.108	0.114
Power gen & Trans	0.277	0.269	0.274	0.275	0.286	0.322	0.276

Profitability: Return of Asset

Industry	Year 5	Year 4	Year 3	Year 2	Year 1	Base Year	Five year avg
Oil & Gas	0.060	0.065	0.086	0.100	0.096	0.108	0.081
Steel	0.064	0.072	0.058	0.105	0.139	0.142	0.088
Automobile	0.108	0.125	0.112	0.072	0.083	0.117	0.100
Engineering	0.149	0.207	0.184	0.140	0.175	0.135	0.171
Power gen & Trans	0.065	0.063	0.064	0.060	0.076	0.087	0.065

Profitability: Return of Equity

Industry	Year 5	Year 4	Year 3	Year 2	Year 1	Base Year	Five year avg
Oil & Gas	-0.113	0.002	0.140	0.150	0.125	0.151	0.061
Steel	0.153	0.177	0.074	0.214	0.251	0.262	0.174
Automobile	0.148	0.174	0.160	0.114	0.128	0.179	0.145
Engineering	0.175	0.239	0.215	0.170	0.215	0.183	0.203
Power gen & Trans	0.103	0.094	0.099	0.093	0.109	0.117	0.099

Efficiency: Fixed Asset Turnover

Industry	Year 5	Year 4	Year 3	Year 2	Year 1	Base Year	Five year avg
Oil & Gas	5.38	4.50	5.20	4.69	4.35	3.59	4.824
Steel	2.24	2.08	1.95	2.17	2.30	2.04	2.146
Automobile	4.00	4.44	4.11	3.51	3.80	4.19	3.973
Engineering	10.34	10.95	10.16	10.45	8.47	7.95	10.073
Power gen & Trans	49.28	38.94	29.47	16.11	45.28	35.89	35.816

Efficiency: Total Asset Turnover

Industry	Year 5	Year 4	Year 3	Year 2	Year 1	Base Year	Five year avg
Oil & Gas	2.937	2.399	2.407	2.431	2.620	2.051	2.559
Steel	0.560	0.541	0.596	0.819	0.964	1.042	0.696
Automobile	1.650	1.653	1.471	1.342	1.512	1.842	1.526
Engineering	2.264	2.851	2.782	3.106	2.554	2.491	2.711
Power gen & Trans	1.147	1.028	1.129	0.802	3.135	2.861	1.448

Annexure – 6
Degree of Diversification of Firms

Sector: Oil & Gas

Company	Degree of Diversification
Indian Oil Corporation Limited	0.852
Reliance Industries Limited	0.857
Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited	0.375
Essar Oil Limited	0.5
G A I L (India) Limited	0.8

Sector; Steel

Company	Degree of Diversification
Steel Authority Of India Limited	0.667
Tata Steel Limited	0.75
Jindal Steel & Power Limited	0.5
Jindal Stainless	0.5
Bhushan Steel Limited	0.5

Sector: Automobile

Company	Degree of Diversification
Maruti Suzuki India Limited	0.5
Mahindra & Mahindra Limited	0.469
Tata Motors Limited	0.833
Ashok Leyland	0.5
Amtek Auto	0.5

Sector: Engineering

Company	Degree of Diversification
Larsen & Toubro Limited	0.861
Punj Lloyd Limited	0.750
Crompton Greaves Limited	0.8
Apar Industries Limited	0.667
Thermax Limited	0.5

Sector: Power Generation and Transmission

	Degree of Diversification
Company	
NTPC	0.5
Power Grid	0.667
Reliance Infra	0.5
PTC India Ltd	0.5
TATA Power	0.5

Annexure – 7

Regression Analysis: Degree of Diversification vs Corporate Performance

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.252423334
R Square	0.06371754
Adjusted R Square	0.023009607
Standard Error	0.071279534
Observations	25

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	0.007952609	0.0079526	1.5652364	0.223477103
Residual	23	0.116857755	0.0050808		
Total	24	0.124810364			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	0.028783246	0.059523135	0.483564021	0.633267189	0.094349739	0.151916232
Degree of Diversification (X)	0.117770534	0.094134034	1.251094093	0.223477103	0.076960552	0.312501621

RESIDUAL OUTPUT

<i>Observation</i>	<i>Predicted Average ROA (Y)</i>	<i>Residuals</i>
1	0.129123741	-0.039864682
2	0.129712594	-0.017406831
3	0.072947197	-0.020723106
4	0.087668513	-0.111283993
5	0.122999674	0.053973888
6	0.107336193	0.042583523
7	0.117111147	-0.025554679
8	0.087668513	0.031215861
9	0.087668513	-0.064998634
10	0.087668513	-0.032508736
11	0.087668513	0.069565104

12	0.084017627	0.084564965
13	0.126886101	-0.084404429
14	0.087668513	0.016350959
15	0.087668513	-0.059802798
16	0.130183676	0.02921718
17	0.117111147	-0.078439357
18	0.122999674	0.168684691
19	0.107336193	0.010294197
20	0.087668513	0.15962695
21	0.087668513	0.004849002
22	0.107336193	-0.070614603
23	0.087668513	-0.028307958
24	0.087668513	-0.021148919
25	0.087668513	-0.015867595

Annexure 8

Regression Analysis: Size of Firm vs Corporate Performance

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.091700939
R Square	0.008409062
Adjusted R Square	0.034703587
Standard Error	0.073354656
Observations	25

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>
Regression	1	0.001049538	0.00105	0.195049
Residual	23	0.123760826	0.005381	
Total	24	0.124810364		

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.105158355	0.017329343	6.068225	3.45E-06
Average Revenue (X)	-1.12874E-07	2.55577E-07	-0.44164	0.662872

Annexure – 9

ANOVA: Industry-wise variation in post-diversification corporate performance

ANOVA : Single Factor

SUMMARY

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Oil & Gas	5	0.407147	0.081429	0.005508
Steel	5	0.43819	0.087638	0.002537
Automobile	5	0.500183	0.100037	0.004127
Engineering	5	0.854683	0.170937	0.01022
Power gen & Trans	5	0.32692	0.065384	0.000409

ANOVA

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	0.03361	4	0.008403	1.84267	0.160255	2.866081
Within Groups	0.0912	20	0.00456			
Total	0.12481	24				